

BD4OPEM

Big Data for OPen innovation Energy Marketplace

Deliverable 7.2

Pilot 1 – Spanish pilot description and results

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
A	Amperes
AMI	Advanced Metering Infrastructure
BAU	Business-as-usual
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
BRP	Balance Responsible Party
CEC	Citizen Energy Community
CIM	Common Information Model
CIS	Customer Information System
DAM	Day-Ahead Market
Dx	Deliverable x
DCU	Data Concentrator Unit
DB	Data Base
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EV	Electric Vehicles
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIS	Geographical Information System
HVAC	Heating Ventilation Air Conditioning
ITC	Information Technology and Communication
kA	kiloamperes
KNX	KoNneX protocol
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LV	Low Voltage
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
MDMS	Meter Data Management System
MV	Medium Voltage
NTL	Non-Technical Losses
P2P	Peer-to-peer
PED	Power Electronic Device
PQ	Power Quality

Acronym	Description
PS	Primary Substation
PV	Photovoltaic
REC	Renewable Energy Community
RTU	Remote Terminal Unit
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SM	Smart Meter
SS	Secondary Substation
Tx	Task x
TSO	Transmission System Operator
UI	User Interface
WP	Work Package

1 Executive summary

The current deliverable documents all the work performed within Task 7.2 (T7.2), related to the Spanish demonstration site (Pilot 1).

It follows the methodology of implementation described in Deliverable 7.1 (D7.1) “Large Scale pilots’ methodology” [1].

The services implemented in this pilot are the following:

Table 1. List of services tested in the pilot.

Service ID	Name of service (name of approach when relevant)	Service developer
S1.1	Topology	ODT
S1.2	Observability	ODT
S1.3	Predictive maintenance in electrical power systems (Predictive maintenance applied to smart meters (SM))	JSI
S3.1	Grid disturbance simulations (Congestions forecast for day ahead)	UPC, WEP
S3.1	Grid disturbance simulations (Congestions control in distribution grids)	VUB
S3.1	Grid disturbance simulations (PQ-related disturbances)	JSI, WEP
S4.1	Inconsistencies in energy balance and power voltage	ODT
S4.2	Fraud patterns detection (UPC approach)	UPC, WEP
S4.2	Fraud patterns detection (JSI approach)	JSI
S5.1	Flexibility forecast (UPC approach)	UPC, ICOM
S5.1	Flexibility forecast (JSI approach)	JSI
S5.2	Flexibility aggregated services for BRPs	UPC, ICOM

Service ID	Name of service (name of approach when relevant)	Service developer
S5.3	Flexibility aggregated services for DSOs (Flexibility-based AC OPF)	UPC, ICOM
S5.3	Flexibility aggregated services for DSOs (Flexibility services for DSOs based on neural networks)	JSI
S6.1	Energy management at household or at community level	UPC, ICOM
S6.2	Forecasting services	UPC, ICOM
S7.1	P2P trading	ATOS
S8.1	Asset and investment planning	UPC, WEP
S8.2	Asset estimation optimization for microgrid	VUB, WEP

First, each service is presented succinctly, and the use cases are reminded, based on WP4 inputs. The results of each service implemented in this pilot are then shown. These results may vary in terms of quality, depending on the quality of data collected on the pilot site. This is why a data quality assessment has also been performed in order to bring insights and explanation on why those results were found.

2 Introduction

2.1 Purpose and intended audience

The BD4OPEM project aims to design, develop, and deploy a marketplace in order to provide innovative energy services for the reliable operation of the smart grid. These energy services will be provided through a marketplace, acting as an open, modular data analysis toolbox and facilitating data exchange and advanced usage. In this way, the data coming from the diverse energy domain sources will be put at the disposal of advanced energy service developers through a marketplace.

The main objective of WP7 is to oversee the implementation and demonstration of the services developed in the previous WPs. Through this implementation, the aim is to prove two points:

- That the tools developed are compliant with the given objectives and, if not, analyse and identify the reason for the difference and provide recommendations about the tool optimization to reach better results.
- That the Marketplace platform and the Analytics toolbox permits flexibility, replicability, and scalability of the services between data providers and service users with adapted features.

Overall, this work package consists in providing the input for the analysis of the impact of the whole system developed during BD4OPEM project and giving recommendation to optimize its use and management. It is as well the opportunity to gather feedback from different demonstration sites and their respective leaders upon the platform, the services, and the customer experience.

This document describes the results of the implementation of the services for the Spanish demonstration site.

The main audience of this document is:

- WP7 partners themselves, to know the results of the project for the Spanish demonstration site.
- WP9 partners for the description of the processes and methodology which can be used in the latter exploitation of the platform.
- Future data providers or service users that want to interface with the BD4OPEM platform.
- Future algorithm developers or service providers that want to propose their own services to EYPESA.

2.2 Relationship with other BD4OPEM tasks

This deliverable is related to different tasks within the BD4OPEM project:

- T7.1, Pilot Methodology and preparation of large-scale pilots, as this implementation is a first demonstration of the methodology described in this task.
- T7.3, T7.4, T7.5, as they are similar tasks.
- T7.6, in which the results of each demonstration site are tested and validated.

- WP9, which will be able to use the results of each demonstration site for exploitation and replication purposes.

2.3 Structure

This document is divided into three main sections:

- The final description of the demonstration site, with the global perimeter, the specifics of the pilot and a recap table of the services implemented in this demonstration.
- The services results for this demonstration site, with a reminder of the use cases, a data assessment, and the services implementation conclusions.
- A monitoring of project KPIs.

Then a final part will conclude with lessons learned from the pilot and from the service developers' perspectives.

Finally, two annexes will detail the storylines of each service as well as the results of services testing in the Marketplace.

3 Final description of the Spanish demonstration site

3.1 Global perimeter (update from D7.1)

The Spanish pilot of BD4OPEM is hosted in the electrical grid of EyPESA Distribució, a Catalan Distribution System Operator (DSO) located in the regions of Vallés Oriental, Osona and Ripollés. In total, EyPESA owns more than 1000 km of Low Voltage (LV) grid and 1100 km of Medium Voltage (MV) grid, that distribute electricity through 31 Primary Substations (PS) and 840 Secondary Substations (SS), reaching around 60.000 supply points.

However, for feasibility reasons and due to the technical infrastructure limits in data collection and sharing, only a portion of the whole grid will be used for testing BD4OPEM services. Three main areas have been identified for testing the solutions developed, based on the specific problems and assets present in the areas (i.e. high penetration of self-consumption, important losses, controllable loads, etc.).

To have a geographical vision of those locations, the three areas are presented in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. EyPESA demonstration sites.

Granollers city center

The first area selected is the city centre of Granollers, the main city belonging to EyPESA's grid. The headquarters of EyPESA are also located in this densely populated area. The location was chosen for most of the services due to the availability of flexibility asset and data from different parts of the grid.

Three MV lines, connected to the same PS, for a total of 10.4 km of line will take part in the pilot. The details of the 3 circuits represented in Figure 2 can be seen in the following Table 2:

Table 2. Details of the circuits in Granollers.

Circuit	MV (km)	SS	LV (km)	SMs	Power (MW)
Blue	4.5	21	19.6	3024	21.4
Pink	2.9	14	15.8	1625	10
Purple	3	14	9	1330	9.4

In total, data will be shared from 1 PS, 49 SS, 10 km of MV and 44 km of LV line and almost 6000 meters.

Figure 2. MV lines and SS in Granollers pilot.

Figure 3. LV Lines and Smart Meters in Granollers.

Furthermore, some specific assets that will be used in the flexibility and P2P services (S5.1, S5.2, S5.3, S6.1, S6.1 and S7.1) are located in this area, more specifically in the headquarters of EyPESA:

- Shared self-consumption PV installation of 37 kWp in total, situated on the roof of different buildings. The installation is shared between 4 different buildings (in Figure 4 in yellow) by using static self-consumption coefficients.
- Battery of 210 kWh capacity + PED
- Private Electric Vehicles (EV) charging point (3 chargers)
- Controllable Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) in two of the buildings (offices). The total contracted power of the buildings is 140 kW and 70 kW

Figure 4. Flexibility pilot.

Rural area LV grid

Another area was chosen especially for services S4.1 and S4.2, focused on Non-Technical Losses (NTL) detection. In this case, only LV grid is considered. This area comprises of 4 different municipalities: l'Ametlla del Valles, Bigues, Santa Eulalia de Ronçana (all in Figure 5) and Seva (Figure 6). Compared to the previous area, it is a more rural environment, where both technical and non-technical losses are a frequent problem.

Furthermore, in one of these municipalities, Santa Eulalia, there is a high penetration of PV self-consumption. The site was therefore chosen also for S3.1, aiming to detect congestions in the LV grid.

In total, this second area consists of 208 SS and 9645 supply points. Electricity is distributed through 336 km of LV lines, and the total power delivered is 52.7 MW.

Figure 5. LV Network in l'Ametlla del Vallès, Bigues, Santa Eulàlia de Ronçana.

Figure 6. LV Network in Seva.

Rural area MV grid

The last area was defined for service S8.1 Asset and Investment planning, focusing only on MV grid. Three PS and their dependent 84 SS were chosen to be part of the pilot. The MV grid measures 84 km and supply 16 MW of power. Population and industries are growing in this area, and EyPESA foresees the need of grid reinforcement and expansion.

The 3 PS, in red in the [Figure 7](#), are:

- ER 1013 Sant Pere Torrelló
- ER 1014 Roda de Ter
- ER 1028 L'Esquirol

Figure 7. Rural area MV grid demonstration site.

3.2 Specifics of the pilots (update from D7.1)

3.2.1 Data Sources

Figure 8. EyPESA Data Sources.

The updated data flow diagram that was previously presented in D3.1 and D7.1 can be seen in Figure 8. Different data sources will interface with the Marketplace with different information model, data format and protocol of communication. Hereafter the data sources are presented:

- **Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI)**

The platform used by EyPESA to collect data from meters is Breo [2]. The system allows the remote collection of data from more than 60 000 SMs, by communicating with the Data Concentrator Unit (DCUs), located in the SS. Furthermore, the AMI also manages the data coming from the grid meters,

installed in most of the SS. In normal operations, the data from the SMS collected and stored in EyPESA database are hourly consumption curves (active and 4 reactive quadrants), as it is what is needed for billing purposes. However, in the pilot, several other queries will be created and used to collect higher frequency power data, voltages and currents.

- **Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA)**

The SCADA system used in the pilot is TEDISnet from Sitel [3]. Grid connectivity and grid measurements from PS and SS arrive from the RTUs located in the substations. Voltages and current data from entrance and exit lines and transformers voltages in all PS, and from the SS where the RTUs are installed. Furthermore, the SCADA receives a set of alarms coming from the substations for not normal operations and when values are outside the operation limits. Furthermore, the SCADA also receives measurements from the PED connected to the 200kWh battery.

- **Geographic Information System (GIS)**

The GIS manages all grid assets and their specifications. EyPESA uses QGis 3.16. The topology of the grid and the interconnection between assets are modelled and represented in the software, along with geographical information. Furthermore, asset characteristics as length, maximum current, electrical parameters of the lines, nominal power of the transformers etc. are stored in the database (DB).

- **EV platform**

EyPESA started managing the electrical charging point with its own platform. This platform was called "EyPESA mobilitat". Through its API, it was possible to give signals to the charging points for start, stop or re-start the charge of the EV. Historical values of charging are also stored in the platform DB. EyPESA mobilitat was a very simple platform with limited actions and a lot of restrictions, also very useful to start quickly operating but not optimal for daily operation. This is the reason why the company pivoted to a more compact and robust solution from an external provider, which in this case is Place-to-Plug Connect [4].

- **HVAC platform**

To control the HVAC of EyPESA's offices, which are part of the flexibility pilot, a platform using the KNX communication standard is used. The platform is able to send control signals to each of the heating/cooling machines, by giving either a cold or hot temperature setpoint (or both if it is necessary to operate within a range). Furthermore, historical of total energy consumption and temperatures are available. The plan to collect this data was to create an API to communicate with the Marketplace, but such actions could not be completed due to reasons alien to the pilot site.

- **Self-consumption control platform**

The self-consumption platform collects generation data coming from PV's inverters and from an advanced parallel meter that is also installed (Wibeee) [5]. On the other hand, the platform also collects consumption data from the 4 areas of EyPESA's building that are part of the shared self-consumption site.

The consumption data are collected also by the advanced smart meters Wibeee, with 1 min granularity and provide disaggregated consumption.

- **Internal DB**

Some data is stored in internal databases, which are manually updated. Therefore, the collection and sharing of data is not automatized. This is the case of frauds database, which comprises of historic frauds and ones under investigation, or of the Balance Responsible Party (BRP) imbalances and demand estimation data.

Table 3. Data sources for Spanish pilot.

Data source	Data identification	Additional description	BD4OPEM ontology	Reference to standards	In repository
AMI	Test cycles: Historical data from Voltage; Current; Active Power consumed and injected; Reactive Power consumed and injected; and Power Factor	All contained in the same file, a csv inside a zip. Every zip is a SS and inside there are all the SM contained in these SS. The nomenclature of the files are: CT-(number of SS)_(from date)_(to date).zip	bd4op:Measurement	CIM: meterMeasurements	eypesa-dp / CiclesTest
AMI	Supervisor data	Consumption data at a substation level for predictive maintenance and observability through a device called supervisor which is a Smart Meter for the substations.	bd4op:Smart Meter	bd4op:Smart Meter has not direct references to any standard but it is a subclass of bd4op:FieldDevice that is based on saref:Device, fiware:Device, fiware:Device Model and cim:EndDevice	eypesa-dp / Services / S1.2 Observability / Supervisors

Data source	Data identification	Additional description	BD4OPEM ontology	Reference to standards	In repository
AMI	Supervisor data	Aggregated consumption data at a substation level for fraud detection and congestion management matters through a device called supervisor which it is a Smart Meter for the substations.	bd4op:Smart Meter	bd4op:Smart Meter has not direct references to any standard but it is a subclass of bd4op:FieldDevice that is based on saref:Device, fiware:Device, fiware:Device Model and cim:EndDevice	eypesa-dp / Services / S4.2 Frauds
AMI	List of Smart Meters of every SS	The list of Smart Meters linked to every SS is inside of every SS document. The documents are identified with lbt + the name of the SS (eg: lbt CT 010)	bd4op:Measurement	CIM: meterMeasurements	eypesa-dp / Services / S1.1 Topology
AMI	Historical data: building consumption data	Active and reactive power from the EyPESA's building	bd4op:Measurement	CIM: meterMeasurements	eypesa-dp / Services / S5.1 Flexibility Forecast / CLIMA
AMI	Historical data: PV generation	PV generation from panels of EyPESA's building: Active and reactive power	bd4op:Measurement	CIM: meterMeasurements	eypesa-dp / Services / S5.1 Flexibility Forecast / PV
AMI	Historical data: EV active and reactive power	Active and reactive power of EV chargers, timestamp of EV consumption, type of measure (hourly, quarter, etc.), readings date	bd4op:Measurement	CIM: meterMeasurements	eypesa-dp / Services / S5.1 Flexibility Forecast / EV

Data source	Data identification	Additional description	BD4OPEM ontology	Reference to standards	In repository
AMI	Historical data: EV consumption and charging time	Location, charging start time and charging end time, Consumption, charging time, town id	bd4op:Measurement	CIM: meterMeasurements	eypesa-dp / Services / S5.1 Flexibility Forecast / EV
GIS	Coordinates, cable longitude, cable tipus, cable material, nominal tension of cable, nominal current of cable, Resistance, Reactancy	GIS files are downloaded in 4 diferent extensions (see the format). To open the information, it has to be used the ".shp" file but the other files must be in the same folder. For the project it has been shared 3 lines of our grid each one identified with a colour (Cian, rosa and vino), and each line has a group of files (remember the format) with cable information in medium voltage and the secondary substations attached to the line. Finally, a group of files with the Primary substation for these 3 lines.	As Gis data is not time series data, the information cannot be cleansed and included in the Marketplace.		eypesa-dp / QGIS

Data source	Data identification	Additional description	BD4OPEM ontology	Reference to standards	In repository
GIS	Voltage primary, Voltage secondary	GIS files are downloaded in 4 different extensions (see the format). To open the information, it has to be used the ".shp" file but the other files must be in the same folder. For the project it has been shared 3 lines of our grid each one identified with a colour (Cian, rosa and vino), and each line has a group of files (remember the format) with cable information in medium voltage and the secondary substations attached to the line. Finally, a group of files with the Primary substation for these 3 lines.	As Gis data is not time series data, the information cannot be cleansed and included in the Marketplace.		eypesa-dp / QGIS
SCADA	Ekors: instantaneous voltage and current data from SCADA	Instant and also average values taken from SCADA. Not uploded to AZURE, another process must be done.	bd4op:Measurement	CIM: meterMeasurements	Eypesa/SCADA
SCADA	Historical data: Battery power and battery state of charge	State of Charge, Battery power, timestamp of battery readings, Type of element (SS, trafo, etc.), tag class of the device (Analogic Input of the device).	bd4op:Measurement	CIM: meterMeasurements	eypesa-dp / Services / S5.1 Flexibility Forecast / BATTERY / Battery SoC AND eypesa-dp / Services / S8.2 Asset degradation modelling / BATTERY / Battery SoC

Data source	Data identification	Additional description	BD4OPEM ontology	Reference to standards	In repository
AMI	Smart Meter active and reactive consumption data	<p>Same data in different folders, for two different services:</p> <p>There is a file per day, including all consumption points included in the services analyzed.</p> <p>For frauds. For this service, it is analyzed specific cases that are hanging of different substations. Then, the curves are in a folder with the name of the SS (Frauds[nameOfTown]CT[nameOfSS]). (UPC: File per day)</p>	bd4op:Measurement	CIM: meterMeasurements	eypesa-dp / Granollers AND eypesa-dp / SantaEulalia
CIS	List of frauds	Excel file identifying the real cases of fraud detected by EYPESA's daily operation	Historic fraud BD4OPEM data model	Self-made, based on EYPESA data	eypesa-dp / Services / S4.2 Frauds
AMI	Historical data: Aggregated consumption of smart meters	<p>Aggregated consumption of all smart meters hanging of a transformer. Years: from 2016 to 2021. Documents are in separate folders containing two years per folder (inside every folder, there's a document per SS).</p>	bd4op:Measurement	CIM: meterMeasurements	eypesa-dp / Services / S8.1 Asset and Investment planning / Historics s8.1 / [confidential] Consumos agregados v2 2017-2020
Internal DB	Aggregated consumption forecast, deviations, real consumption	For the whole portfolio and per year.	bd4op Market data model	cim:Market	eypesa-dp / Services / S5.2 BRP

Data source	Data identification	Additional description	BD4OPEM ontology	Reference to standards	In repository
-	Historical data: weather data	From Meteoblu.	bd4op:WeatherObserved that is based on SmartHome Weather and on bd4op:Property	SAREF:Property CIM:ReadingType	eypesa-dp / Weather Data
Assets	Transformers data	Age, power and technology of transformers. This information is in a document named "Años trafos.csv". Information for Asset and Investment planning	bd4op:Asset	CIM:asset	eypesa-dp / Services / S8.1 Asset and Investment planning
BOE	Asset Costs	List of different transformer and cable costs regulated by the Spain government.	bd4op:Asset	CIM:asset	eypesa-dp / Services / S8.1 Asset and Investment planning
Market data	Spanish electricity Market data (Esios API)	OMIE data, Spanish consumption curve			Not in Azzure

3.2.2 Constraints identified and specific needs

The major problem encountered in the pilot development phase regards the availability and quality of data coming from the DSO's grid. For the development of several services, service developers requested data that are nearly impossible to collect in EyPESA distribution grid.

In the case of S1.3 Predictive Maintenance almost all the assets evaluated to develop the service did not have the available measurement. This was the case of circuit breakers for example. In the end, it was decided to share the data from DCUs, but to get the most interesting data for the service, the data had to be shared after the summer, since it is with the heat when most of the failures occur.

Furthermore, the majority of SS are not remotely controlled. Voltage and current measurements on the MV side are not available in all the SS within the pilot perimeter. This could cause issues for the development of some of the services, such as S1.2 Observability. In the end, this difficulty could be sorted.

Another issue regards the data quality of the SMs. The PLC communication between SMs and DCUs is often not able to provide a complete dataset, especially in the case

of high density of SMs in the area, high granularity requests, and when there is high penetration of PV inverters in the grid which interfere with the communication. These holes in the dataset might affect services S1.1 Topology, S3.1 Grid congestion subservice in LV grid and S4.1 Inconsistencies in power-voltage.

The last constraint encountered was due to the communication of some SMs in the EyPESA headquarters that were going to be used for the S7.1. Unfortunately, due to the noise in the communication system at that point of the grid, some special filters were needed to lower the noise but, because of the shortage of materials that affected worldwide on the year 2022, the filters took too long to arrive and could not be used in the service. The service was finally completed with 3 SMs instead of 5, as it was initially planned.

3.2.3 Legal requirements

In the project framework, EyPESA, as DSO and retailer, provides data from metering, operation and control devices, and smart systems for analysis to meet the objectives of BD4OPEM.

In addition, to respect Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR), all the data coming from metering is either anonymized (by aggregation) or pseudonymized.

In the first case, as the aggregated data is not linked to any specific user, its use respects therefore the privacy of EyPESA users and can be considered not personal data. Regarding the pseudonymization of the personal data, the access and process of the EyPESA data are regulated by the multi-lateral NDA agreement signed between EyPESA and all the data processors. The NDA defines the type data considered personal that the processors are allowed to access, as well as the purpose of processing them, which falls within the purpose of improving and operate the service of electricity distribution.

EyPESA, in the application of the principle of data protection by design (Article 25 GDPR), considers from the beginning of the project design, and throughout the project, the privacy requirements, incorporating technical and organizational measures to ensure that the rights of data subjects are guaranteed.

3.3 Recap table of services to be implemented

The services tested in the EyPESA pilot, along with their respective algorithm developers responsible for creating algorithms for each service, are presented in Table 4 below.

Table 4. Recap table of services to be implemented.

Service ID	Name	Algorithm Developer
S1.1	Topology and network analysis	ODT
S1.2	Observability	ODT
S1.3	Predictive maintenance in electrical power systems	JSI
S2.1	Detection of Measurement Errors	UPC
S3.1	Grid disturbance simulations for MV grid	UPC
S3.1	Grid disturbance simulations for LV grid	JSI
S3.1	Congestion control in LV distribution grids	VUB
S4.1	Inconsistencies in energy balance and power-voltage	ODT
S4.2	Fraud patterns detection	UPC
S4.2	Fraud patterns detection	JSI
S5.1	Flexibility Forecast	UPC
S5.1	Flexibility Forecast based on price signals	JSI
S5.2	Flexibility aggregated services for BRPs	UPC
S5.3	Flexibility Request for Congestions	UPC
S5.3	Flexibility services for DSOs based on neural networks	JSI
S6.1	Energy management at household or at community level	UPC
S6.2	Energy forecasting	UPC
S7.1	P2P trading	ATOS
S8.1	Asset and investment planning	UPC
S8.2	Asset estimation optimization for microgrids	VUB

4 Services results for the Spanish demonstration site

This section presents the outcomes for each use case of the services assessed in the EYPESA pilot.

4.1 S1.1 – Topology results

Introduction of the service

Name: Topology

Category: Operation and maintenance

Task: T4.2

Location on the grid: LV

This service aims to retrieve the network topology (smart meters' substation, feeder and phase associations), and evaluate network analytics (overloads, imbalances...) using such information.

Table 5. Use cases for the S1.1 service.

Use case	Description
UC1	As a DSO, I want to identify associations between meters and substation. So that I can estimate the loading rate of my secondary substations. Acceptance criteria: Give associations between meters and secondary substations
UC2	As a DSO, I want to identify associations between meters and phase's feeder. So that I can estimate the current imbalance and the voltage excursion on my feeders and estimate the loading rate per phase of my substations. Acceptance criteria: Give associations between meters and phase's feeder
UC3	As a DSO, I want to correct associations between meters and secondary substations So that I can update my assets database. Acceptance criteria: The service receives a list of meter's attributes, data from GIS and meters' data. The service provides a file with corrected meter's attributes about their substation association with corresponding confidence level
UC4	As a DSO, I want to correct associations between meters and phase's feeder. So that I can update my assets database. Acceptance criteria: The service receives a list of meter's attributes, data from GIS and meters' data. The service provides a file with corrected meter's attributes about their feeder's phase association with corresponding confidence level

Use case	Description
UC5	<p>As a DSO, I want to Analyse my network regarding voltage and load rates. So that I can locate voltage constraints and locate bottleneck.</p> <p>Acceptance criteria: Meters with passed voltage excursion appear on my screen. Substations or feeders with passed overloads appear on my screen.</p>
UC6	<p>As a DSO, I want to qualify voltage level for constrained points Qualify load level for constrained points. So that I can decide and rank reinforcement.</p> <p>Acceptance criteria: I can access to statistical analysis of my network:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Substations and feeders load rate - Substation and feeder imbalances - Voltage plan

Topology Use Cases results

The service objective is to address the DSO's need of retrieving the topology (meter-to-substation, meter-to-feeder and meter-to-phase associations), but also to analyse in depth the voltage plan and load levels of the LV grid to be able to know where to reinforce the grid or not, and prioritize the needed reinforcements.

For the Spanish demonstration site, the results in the deployed webapp were the following:

Figure 9. Mapping of the MV/LV substations for the Spanish demonstration site, sorted by number of smart meters with voltage out of range.

This first screenshot (Figure 9) shows the mapping of the LV grid for which data has been collected. In this case, the substations are sorted by number of smart meters with voltage out of range, but many other sorting possibilities do exist:

- Mean imbalance rate of smart meters on their imbalance periods
- Number of three-phased smart meters voltage imbalanced
- Time spent overload
- Time spent underload
- Time spent out of voltage range for all smart meters

- Max consecutive hours of fuse overload
- Max power imbalance referred to nominal power (referred to S_n)
- Load max rate
- Occurrences voltage out of range for all smart meters
- Cumulative time fuse overload
- Assured PV available in kW
- Installed PV load
- Number of smart meters allowing a PV domestic install
- Secondary substation max theoretical capacity
- PV load validated and waiting for connection
- Installed PV load reported to P_n

Some of those classifications are only available when the service S3.2 is deployed (tab “Impact assessment PV” in the screenshot above).

Then, the topology use case itself is more detailed in the “Network Analysis” tab:

Figure 10. Network analysis tab with CT-0115 selected.

When going into the “Network analysis” tab and selecting the CT-0115, the web page displays the Figure 10 above, with different types of data on screen.

The first thing to be noticed is that the topology has been retrieved, with 5 different feeders identified (CT-0115_10, CT-0115_4, CT-0115_7, CT-0115_8 and CT-0115_9) and a phase attributed to each single-phase smart meter.

A mapping of the smart meters is also available in the bottom left part of the screen, but in this case, the geographical coordinates of those meters were not available, hence they could not be displayed on the map. The “equipment list smart meters” is available though (Figure 11):

Identifler	GPS	Feeder	Phase
83634		CT-0115_7	1
118226		CT-0115_9	2
89552		CT-0115_7	1
83339		CT-0115_7	2
118206		CT-0115_7	2
85586		CT-0115_7	2
100948		CT-0115_7	1
100934		CT-0115_7	2
85796		CT-0115_7	2
130005		CT-0115_7	1
88137		CT-0115_7	2

Figure 11. Equipment list smart meters for CT-0115.

We can then deep dive into each widget available in this tab with this service:

Figure 12. Topology widget for CT-0115.

This widget (Figure 12) allows to visualize the meter-to-feeder, meter-to-phase associations: each branch represents a feeder, and each colour represents one phase.

Figure 13. Imbalance current radar for CT-0115.

This widget (Figure 13) allows the DSO to visualize the imbalance between the three phases of its substation (CT). In this case, the current shows that there is indeed an imbalance on this substation: the phase 2 appears to be more loaded than the two others.

Figure 14. Voltage distribution widget for CT-0115.

The following widget (Figure 14) shows the voltage distribution for CT-0115. On this specific substation, voltage excursions have been identified, in particular for CT-0115_9 with values of voltage below 207 V (230 V -10%). In particular, phase 2 seems to be more affected by those low voltage excursions, which could be in line with the imbalance identified on the previous widget. The other feeders all stay within the limits of 230 V +/-10%.

Figure 15. Load distribution widget for CT-0115.

The widget above shows the load distribution for the CT-0115. The red boxplots show the sum of the power of the three phases for each feeder and also at substation level.

In this case, the substation seems to be pretty highly overloaded, with the sum at load level exceeding pretty often the nominal power of the substation (250 kVA).

It is also interesting to note that negative loads are displayed on this figure, showing that some PV production does exist on this substation, especially on feeder CT-0115_9.

Figure 16. Voltage duration curve widget for CT-0115.

The above widget (Figure 16) shows the duration curve of the CT-0115. This is a different representation of the Figure 14, in terms of occurrence. It enables the user to identify how often each phase is at which voltage level. In this case, the DSO will be able to see that the voltage excursions identified on its substation are not very frequent (around 1% of the time for phase 2).

Figure 17. Load duration curve widget for CT-0115.

The above widget (Figure 17) is another way to represent the Figure 15, in terms of occurrence. Here, the DSO can see that the substation appears to be overloaded (above the nominal power of 250 kVA) around 88% of the time, which is a lot. It would be interesting for this substation to check that the nominal power of the substation is correct. If it is, it would be a priority for the DSO to reconfigure the grid at this level (change some loads from this substation to another, or change the transformer with a bigger one, with a nominal power of at least 600 kVA).

All the widgets presented above are also available for each feeder, to enable the DSO to see the details of its LV grid (Figure 18):

Figure 18. Network analysis tab at CT-0115_9 level.

Data assessment

Table 6. Data assessment table for the Topology service.

Data source needed	BD4OPEM ontology	Data quality assessment	Impact of the quality on the service
For each SM: Voltage profiles per phase	Smart_Meter	Low: instantaneous data with low density of data	High impact
For each SM: Active power profile per phase	Smart_Meter	Low: instantaneous data with low density of data. Current per phase and summed power.	Low impact
Supposed level 1 topology: Smart meters / substations connectivity	Service_parameters	Good quality	High impact
Substation voltage profile	Secondary_Substation	Medium quality. Not available for all substations	Low impact
Facultative: Reactive power profile per phase	Smart_Meter	Low: instantaneous data with low density of data. Summed power.	Low impact
Facultative: Geographical coordinates of meters	Location	Not available	Low impact
Facultative: Number of feeders per substation	Grid_Assets	Good quality	High impact
Facultative: GIS information, such as a priori meter-to-feeder mapping (to be corrected by algorithm)	Service_parameters	Good quality	High impact

Data source needed	BD4OPEM ontology	Data quality assessment	Impact of the quality on the service
Facultative: Substation power profiles	Secondary_Substation	Medium quality, not available for all substations.	Low impact

Service conclusions

As a conclusion, the service S1.1 Topology has been successfully deployed in the Spanish demonstration site. The confidence indexes of the topology itself (see Appendix B) could be highly improved by having averaged voltages instead of instantaneous voltages, but overall, the data received enabled Odit-e to deploy a user-friendly interface that contains useful information for the DSO.

To recap the results on the scope of the demonstration site, this service enabled to retrieve the topology of 30 substations. 2 of them face voltage excursions, most of them seem to be overloaded to a certain extent.

The retrieved topology can be summed up with the following figure:

Poste	SM change from	Number	Source feeder	Number before algo	Number after-algo	Target feeder	Number before algo	Number after-algo
254	CT-0254_2 to CT-0254_1	38	CT-0254_2	49	11	CT-0254_1	80	118
303	CT-0303_8 to CT-0303_7	3	CT-0303_8	12	9	CT-0303_7	18	21
403	CT-0403_1 to CT-0403_6	1	CT-0403_1	18	17	CT-0403_6	12	13
513	CT-0513_7 to CT-0513_3	3	CT-0513_7	22	19	CT-0513_3	38	43
	CT-0513_8 to CT-0513_3	2	CT-0513_8	8	6			
573	CT-0573_2 to CT-0573_1	5	CT-0573_2	15	0	CT-0573_1	9	10
	CT-0573_1 to CT-0573_4	4	CT-0573_1	9	10	CT-0573_4	12	30
	CT-0573_3 to CT-0573_4	4	CT-0573_3	4	0			
	CT-0573_2 to CT-0573_4	10	CT-0573_2	15	0			
CT-0665_3 to CT-0665_4	10	CT-0665_3	10	0				
665	CT-0665_2 to CT-0665_4	12	CT-0665_2	12	0	CT-0665_4	21	62
	CT-0665_5 to CT-0665_4	18	CT-0665_5	18	0			
	CT-0665_1 to CT-0665_4	1	CT-0665_1	1	0			
727	CT-0727_1 to CT-0727_6	6	CT-0727_1	6	0	CT-0727_6	20	56
	CT-0727_7 to CT-0727_6	1	CT-0727_7	1	0			
	CT-0727_5 to CT-0727_6	5	CT-0727_5	5	0			
	CT-0727_4 to CT-0727_6	19	CT-0727_4	19	0			
	CT-0727_8 to CT-0727_6	5	CT-0727_8	5	0			
779	CT-0779_8 to CT-0779_4	5	CT-0779_8	17	12	CT-0779_4	42	47
791	CT-0791_6 to CT-0791_8	1	CT-0791_6	2	1	CT-0791_8	9	10
805	CT-0805_1 to CT-0805_5	6	CT-0805_1	6	0	CT-0805_5	13	26
	CT-0805_2 to CT-0805_5	6	CT-0805_2	6	0			
	CT-0805_3 to CT-0805_5	1	CT-0805_3	1	0			
820	CT-0820_2 to CT-0820_1	14	CT-0820_2	21	7	CT-0820_1	23	37
854	CT-0854_2 to CT-0854_5	23	CT-0854_2	23	0	CT-0854_5	28	69
	CT-0854_3 to CT-0854_5	18	CT-0854_3	18	0			
877	CT-0877_1 to CT-0877_3	10	CT-0877_1	10	0	CT-0877_3	22	56
	CT-0877_5 to CT-0877_3	9	CT-0877_5	9	0			
	CT-0877_6 to CT-0877_3	9	CT-0877_6	9	0			
	CT-0877_2 to CT-0877_3	6	CT-0877_2	6	0			
913	CT-0913_5 to CT-0913_4	7	CT-0913_5	7	0	CT-0913_4	8	28
	CT-0913_3 to CT-0913_4	7	CT-0913_3	7	0			
	CT-0913_2 to CT-0913_4	6	CT-0913_2	6	0			
949	CT-0949_4 to CT-0949_1	1	CT-0949_4	1	0	CT-0949_1	7	9
	CT-0949_2 to CT-0949_1	1	CT-0949_2	1	0			
968	CT-0968_5 to CT-0968_3	4	CT-0968_5	14	10	CT-0968_3	37	44
	CT-0968_4 to CT-0968_3	2	CT-0968_4	4	2			
	CT-0968_2 to CT-0968_3	1	CT-0968_2	7	6			
982	CT-0982_3 to CT-0982_4	8	CT-0982_3	8	0	CT-0982_4	12	31
	CT-0982_2 to CT-0982_4	11	CT-0982_2	11	0			
990	CT-0990_1 to CT-0990_2	5	CT-0990_1	11	6	CT-0990_2	12	17
Total changes		308						

Figure 19. Sum up of the retrieved topology for the Spanish demo site: comparison with the initial topology.

Figure 19 details the smart meters that have been changed from one feeder to another for each substation. These modifications have been proposed by the algorithm developed by ODT, with a high confidence index (over 78% on average). In total, the algorithm proposed 308 changes to correct the topology sent ahead of the data analysis by the local DSO EypESA.

In the future, other functionalities could be implemented on this demonstration site and included in the S1.1 Topology service such as rebalancing propositions to solve imbalances and voltage excursions. These propositions could be a way for the DSO to avoid costly reconfigurations of their LV network.

4.2 S1.2 – Observability results

Introduction of the service

Name: Observability

Category: Operation and maintenance

Task: T4.2

Location on the grid: LV

The objective of the observability service is to provide an estimation of the low voltage network state in real-time, by applying an artificial intelligence model to a real-time SCADA and optional weather data feeds. The network state, displayed in a dedicated user interface, includes smart meter voltages, as well as the loads of MV/LV substation and LV feeders. The artificial intelligence model is trained on historical smart meter, SCADA and weather data. The objective is to improve the network's operation and allow adequate flexibility management.

Table 7. Use case table for S1.2.

Use case	Description
UC1	<p>As an Operation technician, I want to know in real time the status of the grid. So that I can visualize an estimation of the load of MV/LV substations, LV feeders and the voltages of smart meters.</p> <p>Acceptance criteria:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I can visualise the real time (refresh rate to be defined according to real time data frequency) load at each distribution transformer & phase. 2. I can visualise the real time load at each feeder & phase. 3. I can visualise the real time voltage for each monitored meter.
UC2	<p>As an Operation technician, I want to know in real time when there is an issue on the grid. So that I can react accordingly.</p> <p>Acceptance criteria:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I can visualise in real time how close the power load of each distribution transformer is to the substation nominal value. 2. I can visualise in real time how close the current of each LV feeder & phase is to the corresponding fuse nominal value. 3. I can visualise in real time how close each meter is from a voltage excursion

In Table 7 are reminded the user story as designed and developed in the framework of the WP4 and reported in D4.3 [6].

Demonstration site specificity and deployment perimeter

In the case of EyPESA's demonstration site, SCADA data have been available at a point of the project which prevented to perform the service testing on the demonstration site data. The testing session and results provided in Annex B. Service testing & Service KPIs have been performed on the ELCE service's instance by the EyPESA's expert, please refer to D7.3 [7] for additional information on this instance.

The work depicted hereafter refers to the observation that the complexity of the machine learning models and their management through MLOps practices already presented in D4.3 makes it difficult to maintain, fine tune and scale the service. This made the study of simpler big data techniques necessary in order to obtain a better trade-off between performance and scalability/maintainability. The information hereafter reports on this study and should be considered as an addition to D4.3 documentation. It describes the algorithms and their performances and enables to reduce the complexity of the solution for deployment at a larger scale like in EyPESA demonstration site case.

The perimeter of this analysis for the service S1.2 has been the 33 secondary substations for which data was acquired from September 2021 to July 2023. Only substations with a dataset length longer than 6 months were kept for performances assessment. From those 33 secondary substations “Test cycles” from the AMI were analysed, see Table 3 for additional description.

To perform the state estimation the approach developed in D4.3 and deployed in ELCE demonstration site consist in the use of SCADA real time data to train a model to predict the (not online) smart meters voltages and secondary substation loads. Once the model has been trained offline, it can then be used online to compute the grid voltage.

The analysis hereafter relies on the fact that current voltage of a smart meter (and by extension the whole grid) can be predicted from the past known values of this smart meter. Similarly, the aggregated power at the secondary substation can also be predicted using the same methods. This prediction can be performed through different naïve model which are compared here, depending on the size of the past known values and the number of timesteps ahead to be predicted. On one hand the known window is either **one week** or **four weeks**. From these known values, the trained models must either predict the **next coming timestep** of the data or the **whole next day** (i.e. 24 hours) to come.

Dataset

For each substation, a rolling window of 6 days is swept over the given data in order to generate numerous (smaller) time windows with different start time.

For instance, this rolling window allows for the generation of 4876 One week/one day pairs of smart meter voltage timeseries for the CT-0259 electrical transformer. Table 8 shows the number of extracted time series for each substation and both for smart meter voltage and power at substation, it is calculated for each size of input window (known timesteps, 336 for one week and 1344 for four weeks) and label window (timesteps to be predicted, 1 for next timestep and 48 for next day).

Table 8. Number of time series extracted by substation.

Smartmeter voltage count	input size	label size	CT-0259	CT-0573	CT-0854	CT-0877	CT-0638	CT-0299	CT-0157	CT-0727	CT-0980	CT-0968	CT-0990	CT-0738	CT-0500	CT-0982	CT-0779	CT-0756	CT-0805	CT-0886	CT-0614	CT-0913	CT-0949	CT-0254	CT-0303	Total
			336	1	4876	2784	7395	3712	11078	4662	897	5916	2784	4524	1798	6496	3773	2146	2668	6960	2900	1584	11880	2204	1102	15180
1344	48	4876	2736	7310	3712	10887	4536	897	5916	2752	4524	1798	6496	3773	2146	2668	6960	2900	1584	11880	2204	1102	15180	3591	110428	
	1	4508	2592	7055	3456	10314	4158	858	5508	2656	4212	1674	6048	3542	1998	2484	6480	2700	1512	11556	2052	1026	14766	3402	104557	
	48	4508	2592	7055	3456	10314	4158	845	5508	2656	4212	1674	6048	3542	1998	2484	6480	2700	1512	11556	2052	1026	14766	3402	104544	

Sec. sub-power count	input size	label size	CT-0259	CT-0573	CT-0854	CT-0877	CT-0638	CT-0299	CT-0157	CT-0727	CT-0980	CT-0968	CT-0990	CT-0738	CT-0500	CT-0982	CT-0779	CT-0756	CT-0805	CT-0886	CT-0614	CT-0913	CT-0949	CT-0254	CT-0303	Total
			336	1	53	58	87	58	58	37	69	58	87	58	58	58	49	58	58	58	58	58	88	110	58	58
	48	53	57	86	58	57	36	69	58	86	58	58	58	49	58	58	58	58	58	88	110	58	58	110	57	1496
1344	1	49	54	83	54	54	33	66	54	83	54	54	54	46	54	54	54	54	54	84	107	54	54	107	54	1414
	48	49	54	83	54	54	33	65	54	83	54	54	54	46	54	54	54	54	54	84	107	54	54	107	54	1413

The performances are measured through four naïve methods which are highly scalable and maintainable for large demonstration sites:

- Copy last value: The last known value of the signal is predicted to be the output over the whole span to be predicted. The prediction is thus constant. For the prediction to be true, it would mean that the voltage/power consumption does not change until the next timestep or in the next 24 hours.

- Copy last n values: The last n known values are copied to the prediction. This means that if the voltage/power consumption for the next 24 hours is expected to behave the same at each timestep. In particular, for a prediction length of one timestep, it is the same as the copy last value model.
- Copy mean of input: The output is computed constant to the mean of the input signal
- Mean of the same timesteps on previous weeks: This model considers that the consumption of consumers depends on the day of the week. Thus, if the next day to predict is a Monday, consumer is expected to behave as previous Monday, or more like the average of the past Mondays.

The performances of these models are measured with the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) between the prediction and the ground truth value. The lower the MAE, the better the prediction.

In the box plot, see Figure 20, each point is the average MAE of each smart meter of a given secondary substation. The input size is fixed on a line (1st line has a 1-week input, 2nd a 4-week) and size to be predicted on a column (1st column is next step and 2nd next day). MAE for the copy last value and copy last n values are the same since only the next step is to be predicted, resulting in the same value copied one time. It also shows that these methods show the best results, even compared to models taking into account more than the last timestep of the time series. The value of voltage at next timestep is more likely to be similar to the previous voltage value than the mean of the voltage value or than the voltage value at the same timesteps on previous same days.

The performances of the models for the prediction of the next day are shown on the second column of Figure 20. It shows that the two best models are the mean of the input or the previous day: the voltage of a given day is more likely to look like the one of the previous days than the one of all the previous known same day of the week. Copying the last n values shows better results than replicating the last value for the next 24 hours as it considers for a variation of the voltage over 24 hours.

This figure shows that the prediction can be obtained with a 1V MAE over more than 50% of smart meters with a predictor as simple as the copy of the previous day – and therefore highly scalable.

Figure 20. Boxplots of the prediction MAE of the 4 naïve prediction models.

For the prediction of the power load at substation, a fifth, non-naïve method is proposed: using random forest regression as an autoregressive model for forecasting. This solution is long to compute and need to train a model for each time series predicted.

Figure 21 uses the same pattern as Figure 20, with input size fixed on the line and size to be predicted fixed on the columns. For next step prediction, it shows the same results as for voltage prediction: considering power values in the past does not improve the results of the prediction since the best model (the one with the best median) is the one copying the last values of the signal to the next step. However, on the second column, we see that this model does not suit the prediction of the load over the next 24h as it does not consider the load variation throughout the day. On this task, the two competitive model are the naïve copy of the last 24h hours and the Random Forest Regressor with median MAE of respectively 3.6kW and 3.2kW when the 4 previous weeks are known.

The random forest regression prediction is obtaining results with the similar order of magnitude for computational cost larger by roughly 60 times. For further forecast we would therefore recommend using the naïve solution which gives similar results than the more advanced one but at a way lesser computational cost.

Figure 21. Boxplot prediction MAE for the aggregated power at substation.

Figure 22 and Figure 23 below show all the algorithms in one example. The first task is to estimate the next day smart meter voltage given the previous week (for display purpose, only 2.5 last day are shown). The second task is to estimate the next day power load at substation level given the previous week (for display purpose, only 2.5 last day are shown)

Figure 23 shows that both “copy last n values” and “random forest regression” seem equally good.

Prediction of sm 100342 (Phase 1) of substation CT-0259

Figure 22. Example of all the algorithms on one time series of smart meter voltage.

Prediction of aggregated power at substation substation CT-0259

Figure 23. Example of all the algorithms on one time series of aggregated power at substation.

Data assessment

The EyPESA dataset is both asynchronous and instantaneous, meaning that the smart meter measurements are not equally spaced in time. In order for the data points to be processed, they need to be equally spaced in time.

This is why the dataset is pre-processed by re-aligning the datapoints and averaging smart meters voltage over the points acquired during a 30min period. Moreover, the voltage measured (unevenly as stated) is also an instantaneous value that might not be representative of average value at the smart meter since the last measure.

The dataset generated is therefore of poor quality, which has a great impact on the quality both of the observability model and the study presented in this deliverable.

Table 9. Data assessment table for S1.2.

Data source needed	BD4OPEM Ontology	Data quality assessment	Impact of the quality on the service
For each SM: Voltage profiles per phase	Smart_Meter	Asynchronous & instantaneous resulting in poor data quality through preprocessing to average and synchronize it	High impact Imperfect evaluation of the proposed models
For each SM: Active power and / or current profiles per phase	Smart_Meter	Asynchronous & instantaneous resulting in poor data quality through preprocessing to average and synchronize it	High impact Imperfect evaluation of the proposed models
For each SM: Reactive power profiles per phase (optional)	Smart_Meter	Asynchronous & instantaneous resulting in poor data quality through preprocessing to average and synchronize it	Not included in the analysis Medium impact
Geographical coordinates of meters (optional)	Location	Not available	Low impact on algorithm performance Improved quality of the user experience
Service S1.1 Topology	Service_parameters	Poor quality due to the poor quality of the time series	High impact LV Topology is used to compute the aggregated power at secondary substation level. Missing smart meters or wrong topology lead to poorly reliable aggregation
Training phase: Association of MV/LV substations with the MV assets monitored by SCADA	Service_parameters	Good	High impact Not used in the depicted approach
Training phase: Weather data (optional)	Weather data	Not available	Medium impact
Training phase:	Primary_Substation	Good	High impact

Data source needed	BD4OPEM Ontology	Data quality assessment	Impact of the quality on the service
From the SCADA and each upstream medium voltage feeder: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power and / or current profile per phase • Voltage profile per phase 			Not used in the depicted approach
Operation phase: Real-time and recent historical weather data (optional)	Weather data	Not available	Medium impact
Operation phase: Real-time and recent historical SCADA data and MV data (power profiles per phase, voltage profiles per phase)	Primary_Substation	Not available	Simulation of a real time data feed, by running the service in the past

Service conclusions

The analysis of EyPESA data within the framework of S1.2 offers a performance assessment for models which could be included in the service parametrization and which output are compatible with the service deployed in ELCE demonstration site. While reducing performances compared to more advanced techniques, taking into consideration such alternatives is necessary to reach the best trade-off between performance and scalability/maintainability requirements. Such analysis are necessary to answer the main expected outcome of the service - enhancing the knowledge of the operating conditions of the network offering insights into smart meter voltages and substation loads - in a scalable manner.

The user interface provides a functional display of network states; however, it would require ergonomic improvements to refine the user experience and reach higher exploitability potential for a more intuitive and efficient utilization of the service by operators. Importantly, the project, and especially EyPESA's collaboration, has served as a valuable opportunity to collect premium datasets. These datasets consist in synchronous smart metering data and MV feeder SCADA measurements. They will contribute to future research activities and participate in fortifying the robustness of the service's approach. This data represents an asset for continuous improvement and evolution of the service, in order to make it ready for market reach when dynamic management of low voltage network will arise.

4.3 S1.3 – Predictive maintenance in electrical power systems results

Introduction of the service

Name: Predictive maintenance in electrical power systems

Category: Operation and maintenance

Task: T4.1

Location on the grid: LV grid

The service planned in the EyPESA pilot was the predictive maintenance through classification. Classification of the equipment into maintenance classes. Roughly the classes are divided in one that has high probability of failure and the other with lower probability. The equipment is classified according to the features that are available for a particular class of the system. For example, networking and energy grid equipment like smart meters, are often accompanied by an Information Technology and Communication (ITC) system collecting and monitoring the state of the equipment. Several logs and error logs are available, internal registers state, together with some sensor information like temperature, etc. All these information can be utilised together with time as features that make classification possible. On the other hand, to train the models that could be used for classification, targets are needed as well. The targets tell which equipment has failed, when and at what conditions. The features of failed equipment are needed as well. As a general requirement, more information is available on failed equipment, better will be the classification model for the equipment still in use.

The solution is then extended with features prediction in the next period and maintenance cycle. The classification is performed again on predicted features and the equipment classified in a class with a high probability of failure is then flagged in the service report and returned to the service user.

Table 10. Use case table for S1.3.

Use case	Description
UC1	Use classification and prediction of the grid related equipment state to detect possible future failures of the equipment

Use Case 1

For the collection of data, the service has counted on performance measurements of the concentrators like CPU utilization, fan speed and cooling, temperature of processing components, power supply voltage and status, network failures, etc. The smart metering data transmitted by concentrators was planned as another dimension to check the reliability of transmitted data and for extraction of additional features like load on the network and potential spikes in measurements. Additional data was expected for historical weather reports together with forecasts.

The crucial element of service were the times of failures which indicate when the status of the concentrator has change. The problem is, that the change of the status is only roughly noted. It can pass a few days or more to note the status. The status is still processed by hands, through reports and not in an automated manner. The status time change is essential for the service since it defines the operating conditions at the time of and before the failure.

During the 6-month period it has been realized that the concentrator performance measurements are not available in the part of the network available for the project trials. The notice of the failures has been still done by hand and we were not sure in the exact time of the failures.

As a fallback, we had tried to implement the service based on weather data, smart metering data and the indicated failures. We have tried to estimate more exact time of the failure through the smart metering data.

Some experimental data from the past has been collected for this purpose. The first case was in EyPESA network, related to the failure of concentrator with a tag CT0513. The smart metering data flowing through the concentrator is presented in [Figure 24](#). The gap of almost 20 days is clearly visible in the data. The noted time of the replacement is 12th of July 2022. The concentrator was supposed to fail a week before. Analyse of the data has indicated that the concentrator had failed to transmit the data already on 22nd of June at one o'clock in the morning. The transmission failures are obvious as well in [Figure 25](#) where each successful 15-minute transmission is indicated with a black bar and failed with a white one. Besides the general failure some other failures in transmission can be spotted as well.

Figure 24. S1.3 EyPESA pilot - Concentrator CT0513 failure and related smart meter measurements.

Figure 25. S1.3 EyPESA pilot - success of smart metering data transmission at concentrator CT-0513.

Additional concentrator cases have been studied to estimate if the failure of the concentrator could be estimated from smart metering data. The cases have been studied for concentrator with a tag CT0964, CT0416 and CT0029. Unfortunately, no additional indications have been found from these cases that the estimation of the failure of the concentrator could be estimated from the smart metering data. An example of the smart metering profiles in the period of the concentrator CT0964 failure is presented in [Figure 25](#).

Figure 26. S1.3 EyPESA pilot - Concentrator CT0964 failure and smart metering measurements.

From the figure the gaps in smart metering data can be assumed but in fact the look at the transmission success, as is shown in Figure 26 we cannot see any drops in transmission. It could be that the concentrator has been replaced fast enough and the values have been partially restored from the data stored at the smart meter.

Figure 27. S1.3 EyPESA pilot - success of smart metering data transmission at concentrator CT-0964.

Data assessment

The data needed depends on the equipment maintained. Below is provided an example for data concentrators.

Table 11. Data assessment table for S1.3.

Data source needed	BD4OPEM Ontology	Data quality assessment	Impact of the quality on the service
Smart metering historical management	Smart meter	Adequate	High
Concentrator performance measurements	Performance measurements	Missing	High
Weather parameters	Weather measurements	Available	High
Failure times and reason	Failure data	Not adequate	High

Service conclusions

Similar observations have been concluded from other studies as well. It has been concluded that we cannot estimate the time of the concentrator failures accurately and therefore the service in the fallback manner cannot be implemented successfully.

4.4 S3.1 – Grid disturbance simulations results

UPC approach: Congestions forecast for day ahead

Introduction of the service

Name: Grid Disturbance Simulations.

Category: Operation and maintenance.

Task: T4.1

Location on the grid: MV grid, LV Grid

This service predicts possible congestion scenarios for the day-ahead operation planning on a low-voltage and/or medium-voltage grid by applying machine learning techniques (e.g., Linear Regression, Neural Networks). The output contains information such as the location and time of possible congestions in the grid and suggests improvements by means of swapping between phases at connections or consumers where problems occur.

Table 12. Use cases for the S3.1 service, UPC approach.

Use case	Description
UC1	As a grid analyst, you wish to know in advance the forecast of the demand you are facing in your loads for the next day
UC2	As a grid analyst, you want to know if you are going to have congestions in your lines, following the forecasted loads. This is necessary to plan the flexibility dispatch (if available) for the next day

Use Case 1

Reviewing the forecasted demand, the service offers the deterministic forecasted demand for aggregated sources, the total amount of power in the grid for each hour, as shown in Figure 28. This is an interesting result as the analyst can now where is going to be the peak hour in a first glance to the service UIs, which in this execution there are two peaks at 14:00h and 21:00. It is also possible to check and analyse the forecasted demand for each of the loads in the grid, with the help of the dropdown in the right. The analyst can select a specific load, which can be of more interest to the DSO, for any specific reason. In Figure 29, we can observe the profile of the load CT 500 Pedrals in a day-ahead. This can be done with any other load. Additionally, the analyst can download the table in excel form, as seen in Figure 30, of the results for all the loads in case they wish to generate more detailed reports.

Figure 28. Aggregated demand.

Figure 29. Forecast Demand for Load CT-500 Pedrales.

Figure 30. Table of Demand forecast in excel form.

Use Case 2

For the analysis of the congestions, this tool offers a congestion where the analyst can see the forecast current, in kiloamperes (kA), for each of the lines in the distribution grid. Figure 31 shows the behaviour for the first line of the grid. The limit of the line, calculated with the required data to contract the service, is also shown for the analyst to know if there is going to be a congestion.

Figure 31. Line 0 forecast.

Additionally, in the report tab, the analyst can observe line by line the probability of congestions and this value translated to kA. Also, the report shows the number of total congestions in the grid, which for this particular case is 0.

Hour	Probability [%]	Overload [kA]
00:00	0	0.01990406742268807
01:00	0	0.01796783402086223
02:00	0	0.0165797352349756
03:00	0	0.0153753063605134
04:00	0	0.01457970768703727
05:00	0	0.0138122971478377
06:00	0	0.01373853501425942
07:00	0	0.01466836853417304

Figure 32. Report tab.

Data assessment

The data required to establish the service comprehends topology and grid parameters of the grid, as well historical measurements from either transformers or loads within the grid. The specific data files for this service can be observed in [Table 13](#).

Table 13. Data Assessment for S3.1, UPC approach.

Data source needed	BD4OPEM ontology	Data quality assessment	Impact of the quality on the service
Grid Topology	Service_parameters	Good quality	High
Historical measurements	Smart_Meter	Missing values and Low energy consumptions	High

Service conclusions

The results of the service are highly useful for DSOs. This type of information is especially useful in highly congested grids. However, it is very sensitive to the input data. Also, the fact that the machine learning models are trained with a fixed topology, can be a drawback in grids that change their topologies often. In the case of the Spanish pilot, there are not many historical congestions. As a matter of fact, it is difficult to measure congestions in lines, which is an opportunity area for this service. The approach could be different by exploring congestions in voltages. Additionally, it is a very data intensive service, so adding features and prediction variables adds more complexity to its execution.

Additionally, some feedback raised during the testing of the service is as follows:

1. The forecast figures could benefit from actual measurements of the loads, to help the analyst with past days investigations.
2. Lines results should be given in Amperes (A), instead of kiloamperes (kA)
3. Information about the conductor should be given, as this helps the analyst with the decision making. This also applies to transformers with different cooling systems.
4. In the Report Tables, the maximum thermal limit should be given, to provide reference.

VUB approach: Congestion control in distribution grids

Introduction of the service

Name: Grid disturbance simulation

Category: Operation and maintenance.

Task: T4.1

Location on the grid: LV grid

This service predicts possible congestion scenarios for the day-ahead operation planning on a low-voltage and/or medium-voltage grid by applying machine learning techniques (e.g., Linear Regression, Neural Networks). The output contains information such as the location and time of possible congestions in the grid and suggests improvements by means of swapping between phases at connections or consumers where problems occur.

Table 14. Use cases for the S3.1 service, VUB approach.

Use case	Description
UC1	As system operator/grid planner, you want to acquire insights on the actual grid topology in terms of which user affects one another.
UC2	As a grid analyst, you can monitor the extent to which voltage violations occur in your grid, and at the same time determine how many of these can be reduced by applying phase rebalancing.
UC3	Grid analysts may also want to evaluate the influence of new assets such as solar photovoltaics and/or electric vehicles.

Use Case 1

By analysing the consumption and voltage profiles provided, the service offers insights into which consumer ID will affect another consumer (neighbouring ID), based on the phase to which the consumer is connected. For instance, if the analyst select a consumer "ID 10" (phase A) connected in a feeder embracing households with IDs 1 to 20, results from the algorithm will provide an overview of the affected IDs in terms of voltage deviation per kilowatt of extra consumption at consumer 10, see [Figure 33](#). In this specific example, a deviation in the consumption of consumer 10 will mainly affect consumers 11 and 13, which are both connected to phase A. Other consumers, such as 5 or 20, will be less affected.

On the other hand, next to the impact at consumer level, a grid operator may wish to get an overview of how the grid topology is, and thus which consumers are connected within the same feeder. Using correlation matrices and other clustering techniques, an estimation at feeder level is visualized ([Figure 34](#)). The grid operator can now identify at grid level which consumers influence each other. Furthermore, the UI summarizes the different feeders that the algorithm has detected (displayed left of the plot).

Finally, the results from the analysis can be exported (in a zip file format). Since all the graphs are interactive, the exported version of these graphs are in html format. An example output file is shown in [Figure 35](#).

Figure 33. Individual impact of consumers.

Figure 34. Feeder impact of consumers.

Figure 35. Exported files.

Use Case 2

Grid analysts and operators need to run power flows in order to evaluate the feasibility of expanding the low-voltage networks or to integrate renewable energy sources, electric vehicles and heat pumps. In order to facilitate this aspect, the UI provides a rapid indication of the amount of voltage violations that can be expected on the studied network, Figure 36.

Figure 36. Voltage violation estimation.

The UI allows the grid operator to select the scenario of interest, e.g. 50% PV penetration and 0% EV penetration etc. A visual representation of the number of violations is given on the right side of the UI, here the impacted IDs are represented with the number of violations before a phase swap (red) and the remaining violations after introducing a phase rebalancing (blue). The right side of the UI shows the

number of violations recorded during the giving timeframe of the dataset, and the case if a phase swap¹ would be introduced.

NOTE: Appending the stochastic consumption and/or generation profiles on top of the historical data provides valuable insights to the grid planner. However, it remains an estimation and for real cases will highly depend on the EV charging and the weather data.

The 'export results' function provides all the required information from the UI, such as the 'violations_start', 'violations_after', 'swap_id', 'neighbour', 'start_phase' and 'target_phase' within a json file.

Figure 37. Export voltage violations results.

Use Case 3

Finally, the last use case is interesting for grid planners as they may wish to get a better understanding of how the voltage profiles of the consumers within their network evolves for different scenarios, especially for the integration of electric vehicles and PV-systems. To help the grid operator in this task, the UI allows to select a specific ID and analyse the network's bottlenecks, Figure 38.

¹ The phase swap algorithm suggest another phase based on the no. of violations.

Figure 38. Voltage profiles for a specific scenario.

Here, the planner can distinct the predicted voltage (dashed line) with the actual historical voltage (solid line).

To conclude the 'Results' tab summarizes the grid congestion reduction and provides an 'Export all results' button that downloads the previous .html and .json documents.

Data assessment

Table 15. Data assessment table for service 3.1, VUB approach.

Data source needed	BD4OPEM ontology	Data quality assessment	Impact of the quality on the service
Voltage	Smart Meter	Not adequate	High
Current	Smart Meter	Not adequate	High
Active Power	Smart Meter	Missing	High
Reactive Power	Smart Meter	Missing	High
Power Factor	Smart Meter	Not adequate	High

Service conclusions

Feedback provided during the testing of the service highlighted the effectiveness of the service and the degree to which the results are useful for DSOs. The outcome of the congestion forecasting helps grid operator to plan, and also assess the feasibility

of incorporating new assets such as EVs or PV systems. Nevertheless, as generic PV profiles and EV profiles are utilised in the service, this limits the accuracy of the studied case. Furthermore, the integration of these assets is associated to a complete distribution of these assets at each household with a certain scaling factor. While DSOs might be more interested in specific cases where they can select the amount of EV and or PV a specific household ID.

During the testing of the service some interesting feedback was provided for which DSOs and other service users could benefit from:

- Although the exported result provide the information on the phase to be swapped, it should also be added to the UI.
- The UI could greatly benefit from a function to add another voltage profile in the 'Voltage profiles' tab in order to compare different consumer IDs.
- The representation of the correlated consumers could be more intuitive by providing a tree diagram (topology representation) instead of a correlation matrix which is not as easy to understand (a lot of information on the first sight).
- Another aspect that could be added is a 'zone' where the congestion occurs.

JSI approach: PQ-related disturbances

Introduction of the service

Name: Grid disturbance simulations.

Category: Operation and maintenance.

Task: T4.1

Location on the grid: LV grid

Due to load fluctuations and intermittent power generation at various locations, distribution systems are susceptible to line and transformer overloads. In addition, excessive simultaneous energy consumption in a specific part of the network can lead to an undervoltage problem. On the other hand, excessive simultaneous generation can lead to an overvoltage problem. This service aims to solve the above problems by performing the LV grid simulations and identifying possible solutions to improve power quality (PQ).

Table 16. Use cases for the S3.1 service.

Use case	Description
UC1	As DSO you want to analyse LV grid to increase ingestion capabilities for RES.
UC2	As DSO you want to analyse LV grid to improve voltage profiles at the end-user
UC3	As DSO you want to analyse LV grid to minimize investment costs for reinforcing the grid

Use Case 1, 2 and 3

As a DSO, the primary objective is to improve the capabilities of the existing low-voltage grid to increase the feed-in of renewable energy with minimal investment costs while complying with PQ requirements or addressing potential existing PQs.

Most critical are the voltage levels at the end consumers/prosumers. In the worst-case scenario, the largest voltage fluctuations are observed at the end consumers/prosumers that are furthest away from the substation or have high loads or generators.

During the analysis of the LV grid, we have found that there is the lack of PQ issues on the selected grid, Figure 39. Voltage profile histogram,

Figure 40, show distribution of voltages at different nodes of LV grid. The worst-case voltages are already well below the PQ requirements.

Figure 39. Selected voltage profiles at consumers of selected LV Grid.

Figure 40. Voltage profiles – histogram.

Data assessment

Table 17. Data assessment for S3.1, JSI approach.

Data source needed	BD4OPEM ontology	Data quality assessment	Impact of the quality on the service
Grid Topology	Service_parameters	Good	High
Historical measurements	Smart_Meter	Good	High

Service conclusions

Service was executed on the pilot. However, absence of PQ issues suggests that the initial focus on addressing load fluctuations and intermittent generation may not have been necessary. The system is already performing adequately in terms of PQ. The lack of PQ issues was a key factor in the decision not to deploy the service in a pilot.

4.5 S4.1 – Inconsistencies in energy balance and power voltage results

Introduction of the service

Name: Inconsistencies in energy balance and power voltage

Category: Fraud detections

Task: T4.1

Location on the grid: LV

This service gives the insight to locate non measured energy in low voltage networks. It will identify substations with missing energy (performing an energy balance), smart meters with nearby missing power probability, and smart meters with a significant bypass probability.

Table 18. Use cases for service 4.1.

Use case	Description
UC1	<p>As a Grid operator, I want to quantify non-technical losses at substation level. So that I can investigate more deeply on substations with significant non-technical losses.</p> <p>Acceptance criteria: A statistical analysis of the energy balance between metering data and substation data is displayed (boxplots, time duration curves)</p>

Use case	Description
UC2	<p>As a Grid operator, I want to locate meters that are likely to be bypassed. So that I can send a team on the field, at the right location, to verify the meter.</p> <p>Acceptance criteria: A list of the meters with their probability of being bypassed is displayed Meters are displayed on a map with a radius proportional to their probability of being bypassed</p>
UC3	<p>As a Grid operator, I want to locate meters that are likely to have NTL nearby. So that I can send a team on the field, at the right location, to verify the meters.</p> <p>Acceptance criteria: A list of the meters with their probability of having NTL nearby Meters are displayed on a map with a radius proportional to their probability of having NTL nearby</p>

Service Use Case results

The service 4.1 – Inconsistencies in energy balance and power voltage was impossible to deploy on the Spanish demonstration site, because of data collection challenges. The Spanish partner EyPESA did everything possible to collect as much data as possible, as described in the D4.2.

The smart meter infrastructure of EyPESA does not allow the collection of the voltage profile at smart meter level. To work around this issue, EyPESA designed a data collection strategy which request per cycle the instantaneous voltage seen by all the smart meters of the studied substation.

The absence of synchronized data makes the calculation of energy balance less precise. The precision of this energy balance can be estimated by comparing the current measured at the transformer to the sum of currents of smart meters. The latter should always be smaller than the former assuming there is no production. In the studied dataset, the fraction of nightly negative energy balance time steps during the night is $\sim 40\%$, however the average value of negative missing energy balance divided by the transformer energy is ~ 0.001 , which is acceptable for the study.

The energy balance and nightly energy balance for each transformer are indicated below:

Table 19. Energy balance and nightly energy balance for each transformer.

Transformer	Energy balance	Nightly energy balance	Number of smart meters with nearby missing energy	NTL_nearby
TR1	-0.03	-0.05	2	4%
TR2	0.16	0.4	0	0%
TR3	0.06	0.14	1	2.3%

The bypass detection algorithm detected no bypass with high confidence on all smart meters.

The nearby missing energy detected one smart meter with nearby missing energy. No such smart meters were detected in the TR2 transformer, which was selected to evaluate the accuracy of nearby missing energy detection. The application of the previously described methodology on TR2 show that in 48% cases (NTL_nearby_accuracy), the algorithm did detect the missing smart meter.

This energy balance is only a part of the service S4.1, as described in D4.2. In order to still give the opportunity to test the full service to EyPESA, access to ELCE results was made available in the eypesa_user of the web app. The data from ELCE was anonymized.

The results from ELCE for service S4.1 are available in the D7.3.

Data assessment

Table 20. Data assessment for S4.1.

Data source needed	BD4OPEM ontology	Data quality assessment	Impact of the quality on the service
For each SM: Voltage profiles per phase	Smart_Meter	Low: instantaneous data with low density of data	High impact
For each SM: Active power profiles per phase	Smart_Meter	Low: instantaneous data with low density of data. Current per phase and summed power.	High impact
Substation power profiles	Secondary_Substation	Medium quality, not available for all substations.	High impact
Reactive power profile per phase (optional)	Smart_Meter	Low: instantaneous data with low density of data. Summed power.	Low impact
Geographical coordinates of meters (optional)	Location	Not available	Low impact
GIS information (optional)	Grid_Assets	Good quality	High impact on topology, so high impact on S4.1
Substation voltage profile (optional)	Secondary_Substation	Medium quality. Not available for all substations	Low impact

Service conclusions

As a conclusion, the data collected from EyPESA was unfortunately not sufficient to fully deploy the service S4.1, mainly because of instantaneous data (voltage and active power) at smart meter level, instead of averaged and synchronized data. As stated before and in the data assessment table, this “low quality” data had a high impact on service deployment.

To still provide some results, an energy balance has been made and the results were presented above.

Also, the results from ELCE demonstration site were anonymized and made available to EyPESA so they were able to test it. Those results are available in D7.3.

4.6 S4.2 – Fraud patterns detection results

UPC approach: Fraud patterns detection

Introduction of the service

Name: Fraud Patterns Detection

Category: Fraud Detection

Task: T4.1

Location on the grid: LV Smart Grid

This service detects, classifies and identifies fraud based on the Non-Technical Losses (NTL) curve pattern by applying machine learning algorithms for clustering and classification. The output contains valuable information for the DSO, such as the magnitude, the duration and the type of fraud. The system also flags possible culprits and includes a graphic of each NTL case detected. The recent results are presented in one tab, while the historical frauds are displayed separately. The user can verify or deny each instance after a field inspection to calculate the accuracy and improve the service.

Table 21. Use cases for the S4.2 service.

Use case	Description
UC1	<p>As a DSO, I want to have practical information about the frauds in my grid. So that I can carry out field inspections and calculate the corresponding fines without allocating many resources.</p> <p>Acceptance criteria: Identify current transformers with NTL, classify the fraud by type, find magnitude and duration of fraud and flag possible culprits, if any.</p>
UC2	<p>As a DSO, I want to have a quick and clear overview of the frauds in my grid. So that I can calculate and assess losses, prepare reports and take decisions accordingly.</p> <p>Acceptance criteria: Summarize total number of frauds, recovered power and show a distribution of frauds by type.</p>

Use Case 1

The service runs periodically, displaying the latest results in the “Recent Results” tab of the Visualization section, as shown in Figure 41. This screen shows a table with various information about the detected frauds. Among this information, we find the magnitude of the NTL in kW, obtained with statistical methods, as well as the duration in days. This allows the operator to calculate the corresponding fine. It also shows the type of fraud and the probability of it being correctly identified by the probabilistic classification algorithms. Finally, in some cases of fraud due to squatting, smart meters with anomalous patterns are indicated, with a probability that they are committing fraud. This flagging is done using clustering algorithms to detect abrupt pattern changes. With all this information, the DSO can optimize field inspections and alert the police if necessary.

These same results can be downloaded by the user in Excel and CSV. Figure 42 shows the table of recent results in Excel format.

When the NTL detection system is executed again, the frauds that were previously in "Recent Results" are moved to the table in the "Historical" tab. As shown in Figure 44, this table contains the same elements as the recent results table, with the addition of the date of detection. Both tabs allow the user to sort and filter the frauds by probability, type, magnitude or duration. Figure 43 displays the historic frauds sorted by magnitude (descending), while Figure 44 shows the historical frauds due to squatting.

Finally, the service allows the user to explore the load curve pattern of the detected fraud by clicking on "View Graph". Figure 45 shows the graph of one of the frauds due to squatting in the EyPESA grid, which resembles a typical residential load curve.

Figure 41. Service S4.2_UPC_Recent Results.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	SM ID	Trafo ID	Probability [%]	Type	Magnitude [kW]	Duration [dd]	Verified
2		CIR4621546083	-	Other	217.8	30+	null
3		ORM1149910124	51	Squatting	94.623	30+	null
4	SM: ZIV0040336439,73.05 %	ORM4991063500	68	Squatting	4.323	29	null
5		CIR0308247054	62	Mining	55.272	22	null
6	SM: CIR0141238191,61.24 %	CIR2081651126	70	Squatting	5.002	29	null

Figure 42. Service S4.2_UPC_Table of recent frauds in Excel form.

The screenshot shows a web interface for 'Fraud patterns detection' with a sidebar on the left containing 'Dashboard', 'Visualization', and 'KPIs'. The main content area has tabs for 'Recent Results' and 'Historical', with 'Historical' selected. A 'Filter' button is in the top right. Below the tabs, it says 'Show 10 entries'. The table below has columns: Detection Date, Trafo ID **, Probability [%], Type, Magnitude [kW], Duration [Days], Graph, and Verify. The data is sorted by Magnitude [kW] in descending order.

Detection Date	Trafo ID **	Probability [%]	Type	Magnitude [kW]	Duration [Days]	Graph	Verify
4/9/2023	CIR4621546083	-	Other	217.8	30+	View Graph	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
5/9/2023	CIR4621546083	-	Other	217.8	30+	View Graph	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
7/9/2023	CIR4621546083	-	Other	217.8	30+	View Graph	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
4/9/2023	ORM1149910124	52	Plantation	94.623	30+	View Graph	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
5/9/2023	ORM1149910124	52	Squatting	94.623	30+	View Graph	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
7/9/2023	ORM1149910124	61	Squatting	94.623	30+	View Graph	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

Figure 43. Historical frauds sorted by magnitude in descending order.

The screenshot shows the same web interface as Figure 43, but the table is filtered to show only 'Squatting' incidents. The 'Type' column is sorted in ascending order.

Detection Date	Trafo ID **	Probability [%]	Type	Magnitude [kW]	Duration [Days]	Graph	Verify
4/9/2023	ORM4991063500	71	Squatting	4.323	29	View Graph	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
5/9/2023	ORM4991063500	64	Squatting	4.323	29	View Graph	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
7/9/2023	ORM4991063500	52	Squatting	4.323	29	View Graph	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
5/9/2023	ORM1149910124	52	Squatting	94.623	30+	View Graph	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
7/9/2023	ORM1149910124	61	Squatting	94.623	30+	View Graph	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
4/9/2023	CIR2081651126	60	Squatting	5.002	29	View Graph	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

Figure 44. Historical Results filtered by type 'Squatting'.

Figure 45. Load curve of fraud due to squatting.

Use Case 2

Sometimes, the DSO may want a quick and clear view of fraud in his network for loss calculation, reporting and strategic decision-making. That is why the service offers a KPIs tab, as shown in Figure 46, with a summary of the detected frauds, the total power of these and a distribution according to typology. This same screen also shows the algorithm's accuracy, which considers the frauds verified and denied by the user. The user can download this summary of the results in PDF format.

Figure 46. Service S4.2_UPC_Service KPIs.

Data assessment

The data assessment can be observed in Table 22.

Table 22. Data assessment for service 4.2, UPC approach.

Data source needed	BD4OPEM ontology	Data quality assessment	Impact of the quality on the service
For each SM: Active power profile	activeEnergy	Inconsistencies in the format of the data delivered (changes in columns' names, sometimes there was one file per day...). Some NaNs and missing values.	Medium. The code had to be adapted several times for the data format. NaNs and missing values posed some hurdles.
Substation power profile	activeEnergy	Inconsistencies in the columns' names.	Low. Minor code changes had to be made to read the data correctly.
Historical frauds detected with a classification label	Historic_Fraud	There are relevant data, although there are few cases and little variety of type.	High. Few historical frauds have led to a small training dataset, with possible overfitting. Controlled oversampling was done to have enough samples to train the algorithm. Only three types of fraud (plus the "Other" type) are included since they are the ones provided. In practice, more types of fraud may exist in a network.

Service conclusions

In a distribution grid, frauds can differ in type, magnitude and duration, and knowing these characteristics can facilitate the DSOs' task of preparing field inspections.

Upon testing the service with the use cases, it is proven that the service performs well in classifying the type of fraud, providing valuable information for the user. However, due to the lack of cases of cryptocurrency mining fraud and other types of fraud, the algorithm has not been tested with a large number of cases.

After testing the algorithm with EyPESA employees, the following feedback points were proposed to improve the user experience:

- In the "Visualization" tab, frauds should be indicated with the number and/or name of the TC they are associated with. Currently, the serial number of the meter or concentrator with which the data is obtained is displayed.

- In the Magnitude column, refine the way the numbers are displayed. Each value should have the same number of decimal places. It would also be interesting to explain what this power means and in which period.
- As for the graph, it should be explained in more detail what this daily graph indicates. An advantageous alternative would be to display an interactive graph using, for example, the *plotly* library.
- It is necessary to indicate better what the probability refers to.

In the future, we plan to incorporate the feedback given by EyPESA and improve the algorithm with the following points:

- Expand the training database with more and more diverse frauds.
- Calculate the technical losses using the network topology.
- Improve the formula for calculating the probability of the correct type.
- Make an algorithm with dynamic training that allows adding newly detected frauds to the training dataset.

JSI approach: Fraud patterns detection

Introduction of the service

Name: Non-Technical losses

Category: Operation and maintenance

Task: T4.1

Location on the grid: LV grid

The Non-technical losses service developed by JSI is intended to support an investigator of the non-technical loss in his/her research. The tool requires bubble data for its processioning. The bubble data is the data of all the smart meters and related transformer station in each timeframe. The tool should be able to compute the loss as a difference between the substation meter consumption and the sum of all consumption of related smart meters. Besides, the data should cover a substantial period before the loss and the period till after the discovery of source of the losses. Of course, the tool can provide the results before discovery of the loss source.

Table 23. Use cases for the S4.2 service.

Use case	Description
UC1	As a DSO, I want to use network region bubble data to detect, analyze and report on non-technical losses in the network and their potential sources. So that I can provide analysis results that can be used as evidence in the NTL case. Acceptance criteria: Identify current areas with NTL. Current area: Balenyà.
UC2	As a DSO, I want to use network region bubble data to detect, analyze and report on non-technical losses in the network and their potential sources. So that I can provide analysis results that can be used as evidence in the NTL case. Acceptance criteria: Identify current areas with NTL. Current area: Canovelles.

Use Case 1

This service runs on demand and for the EyPESA pilot was deployed in five different cases. The results are presented in a report format which shows different tables and graphs that allows the system operator to potentially bring forth necessary materials and clues for forensic investigation of the loss. Some of the report results could be used as evidence in further police and prosecution investigation of the case.

At the top of the report is a summary of the findings in the report, giving quick overview of potential report findings. The data overview is given in next section by visualization of all metering points consumptions in the target period in a compact and easy to overview way. The loss is visualized and start of the loss period estimated, if not given among input parameters. The data summary of the dataset is provided.

Study of the loss provides basic insight into structure of the loss. The differences in consumption statistics allow to compare metering points consumption before and after the loss occurrence. The sliding differences provide an insight how the difference in basic metering point statistics have been progressing in time. The data insight provides basic information about the dataset, descriptive statistics per metering point and a visualization of the dataset allowing for quick searching and filtering within the report.

On the end more documentation is provided about the results calculation and potential interpretation.

NTL data overview

The plot below presents the NTL case data summary visualization. The visualization is done on data resampled per day. All the smart meters together with the Loss are plotted in the same timeframe.

Figure 47. NTL case data summary for Balenya case.

The loss visualisation is presented below. An estimated start of the loss is indicated with a vertical line at the time when the loss has become greater than 3.0 of the overall consumption, or the values of the loss start and end are given in the case data.

Figure 48. NTL loss visualization for Balenya case.

Study of the loss

	count	mean	std	min	25%	50%	75%	max	sum	days
Loss	4856.0	27.909214	26.552638	-0.933	6.15125	18.735	43.55825	105.075	157720.8	270

Figure 49. Loss summary statistics for Balenya case.

The study of the loss clusters daily loss samples regarding their statistical properties like daily mean, maximum, minimum, standard deviation, and peak-to-peak value. Clustered values are reconstructed and plotted as a time series as is presented below. The presentation can be used to detect patterns related to usage of electricity resulting in the loss, like marihuana growing. The presentation below is result of clustering the loss daily samples in 3 groups.

Figure 50. Clustered loss function for Balenyà case.

	Start	End	Span
1	2021-08-26	2021-08-04	22 days
2	2021-09-21	2021-08-26	26 days
3	2021-10-23	2021-09-21	32 days
4	2021-11-26	2021-10-23	34 days
5	2022-01-12	2021-11-26	47 days
6	2022-02-05	2022-01-12	24 days

Figure 51. Clustered loss time spans.

The differences in consumption statistics compares several statistics of the consumption before and after the occurrence of the loss. In this way changes in consumption patterns can be detected, potentially due to occurrence of the loss. More information on used statistics can be found in this report documentation on the end of the document.

Below first the entire table of the statistics is presented for all measurement points, together with labelling information based on K-Mean clustering of the data. Next the most exposed measurement points are indicated. Visualisation of the clustering is presented in the figure below.

The differences in consumption statistics can indicate a source of the NTL. Larger are the differences, more likely is that the smart meter consumption has changed at the time of the loss occurrence. It must be noted that the changes are not necessarily related to NTL. Other reasons, like changing regular consumption at the meter approximate at the same time.

	mean	std	max	min	ptp	kml
120765	0.760954	0.697280	0.913210	0.526890	1.115011	2
137985	2.877723	1.273051	1.396261	0.000000	1.396261	1
138321	0.136042	0.025879	0.057970	0.950832	0.033164	0

Figure 52. Loss summary statistics for Smart Meter.

Figure 53. K-mean clustering for Balenyà case.

The score can be calculated according to the observed differences and pondering of the statistical variables:

	mean	std	max	min	ptp
Score	8	2	3	2	2

Figure 54. Scores of the NTL for Balenyà case.

The measurement points with highest probability to be the source of NTL according to differences in consumption statistics are:

	Score
137985	15
138321	2

Figure 55. NTL score of probability.

Figure 56. Sliding differences graphs.

Sliding scores as are presented in Figure 54 and have been applied for maximum values in statistics for all 51 time points the scores have been calculated. Sliding scores have been given to 5 out of 3 metering points.

The graph below shows how the scores have changed in time for the metering points given the score. With the vertical dashed line, the time of loss start is indicated. The graph of scoring is presented below:

Figure 57. Sliding scores graph for selected period of fraud.

Detection based on consumption prediction

The detection based on consumption prediction uses predictions to be able to detect potential non-technical losses culprits. During the loss period the consumption of each smart meter is predicted and then compared to the actual consumption. Based on the differences the smart meters are then ranked and compared to each other's. The ones with the most differences are considered to have more potential to be the source of NTL.

The detection technique is important for cases when some of the pre-loss consumption is moved from behind the meter to direct bypass the meter connection. For example, heating can be moved from behind the meter to direct connection.

The method is not suitable for cases when the consumption has not been changed at all, for example, when somebody builds and connects a plant farm directly, bypassing the meter.

The observer can assess each meter metering changes separately.

The label 137985 contains NaNs, skipping
 The label 138321 contains NaNs, skipping

Figure 58. Fraud forecast versus actual consumption.

Below is a matrix presenting the differences between predicted and real consumption for the smart meters in the area. The differences are presented with the following parameters:

- diff: a difference sum between prediction and consumption
- absdiff: an absolute difference value sum between prediction and consumption
- mean: mean value of the difference values
- absmean: mean value of absolute difference values
- sqroot: a square root value of the differences

The largest differences in the matrix per SM and per parameter are highlighted.

	diff	absdiff	mean	absmean	sqrt
120765	29.552485	38.917279	0.109050	0.143606	3.224732

Figure 59. Smart Meters with largest differences.

The descriptive statistics per metering point is presented in the table below. The values of the statistics are highlighted with a heatmap, the darker is the colour, the larger is the value.

	71613	73553	120765	137985	138321	Loss
count	9459.000000	9395.000000	9502.000000	4019.000000	5255.000000	7275.000000
mean	0.216990	0.764642	1.011506	4.228948	0.761994	21.679836
std	0.235629	0.404211	1.054736	4.532593	1.809830	24.932385
min	0.019000	0.263000	0.000000	0.000000	0.014000	-0.933000
25%	0.090000	0.495000	0.001000	0.126000	0.064000	0.092000
50%	0.146000	0.658000	0.263000	1.854000	0.088000	12.905000
75%	0.259500	0.901000	2.083000	7.678000	0.482500	36.880000
max	3.556000	3.719000	2.582000	18.117000	8.961000	105.075000

Figure 60. Descriptive statistics per metering point.

Use Case 2

Service Results

The service results are presented in a document accessible through the service results web page as explained in the previous Section. The results table of content is presented in. The report is split into 8 major sections. At first there are sections on service instance information and introduction into the report. The service instance section provides information when and on which data the service instance has been run. The introduction section explains the goals of the service and briefly introduces the results.

The last sections are related to a potential examination of the data directly in the report through in HTML based spreadsheet visualization libraries that enable the examiner to quickly check the profiles for potential evidence. The last section is the documentation of the methods and procedures used in the preparation of the report.

NTL data overview

The next section is on NTL data overview where the substation data together with the loss in the observed time frame is presented as can be seen in [Figure 61](#). The profiles are visualized in a way that they are quickly cross comparable over the entire period.

Figure 61. Profiles in the Balenya case, EyPESA pilot, with the loss.

Study of the loss

The next section is concerned with a study of the loss. The days of the loss are clustered according to basic statistical variables, namely mean, max value, min value, standard deviation and peak-to-peak value. Values are calculated for each day and the clustered by K-Means clustering algorithm. Results of clustering is presented in Figure 62. The clustered day consumptions are plotted on original loss curve and coloured per their cluster membership.

Figure 62. Study of the loss, EyPESA pilot, Balenya case.

The method is useful in cases when the loss is related, for example, to detecting pot growing plantations. The clustered days of the loss are well related to the growing cycles of the plants, as can be seen in Figure 62. The clusters time spans in days are given in Figure 63. The clusters time spans correspond to plantation cycles. The cycles result in different statistical variables and thus clustering to different clusters.

The method enables the investigator to understand what the loss consumption has been used to and narrow the investigation in the field for the loss.

	Start	End	Span
1	2021-08-26	2021-08-04	22 days
2	2021-09-21	2021-08-26	26 days
3	2021-10-23	2021-09-21	32 days
4	2021-11-26	2021-10-23	34 days
5	2022-01-12	2021-11-26	47 days
6	2022-02-05	2022-01-12	24 days

Figure 63. Loss clusters time span, EyPESA pilot, Balenya case

Differences in consumption statistics at appearance of the loss

To study the substation profiles further the profiles consumption statistics is compared as the statistic before the occurrence of the loss and the statistics after occurrence of the loss. The comparative combined statistics is calculated according the following equation:

$$combined = \frac{statistics_before_{t < t_{loss}}}{0.01 + statistics_after_{t > t_{loss}}}$$

The combined statistics is then calculated for all observed statistics, mean, standard deviation, maximal, minimal and peak-to-peak value. The profiles are clustered according to these values in three clusters and then plotted in mean/std plane as is seen in Figure 64. The method results in three clusters, where two profiles stand out and are grouped in separate clusters. Please note that the clustering in this plane can look weak but real clustering has been done in all five variables dimensions. Weak exposure in two dimensions does not means that the profiles are not well separated in other dimensions. The profiles are candidates for closer inspection and are suspicious as a culprit for the NTL loss.

Figure 64. Clustered profiles regarding combined statistics comparing behavior of the profile before and after occurrence of the loss in EyPESA pilot, Canovellas case.

Sliding differences

A step further from the previous statistics are the sliding differences. The combined statistics as explained in the previous section is used on data split between one before the slider and the other after the slider. The slider is a virtual time on the time axis that shifts from left to right in on a week interval. Each dot on the individual graph presents the sliding difference between the consumption being observed so far and the consumption that will follow. All the dots values are calculated according to the formula given in the previous section. With the vertical lines the start of the loss and end of the loss are indicated. The investigator should be interested in the profiles which sliding statistics changes most at the time of occurrence of the loss.

In Figure 65, the sliding statistics for mean is presented. It can be seen that there are two profiles with a peak of changes close to the occurrence of the loss. They are marked in the picture with one and two. These two profiles are primary suspects for investigation in the NTL case.

The report provides sliding differences plot for each statistic separately.

Figure 65. Sliding statistics for mean, EyPESA pilot, Canovellas case.

Sliding scores

The results in previous section can be further explored with sliding scores. Sliding scores are given to profiles at each time of the split as is presented in Table 24. The scores are given to the profiles with max value for each statistics at each split of the data. The table proposes scoring according to each statistics. The top score is given to changes in mean value, the others are valued more equally.

Table 24. Sliding scores.

	mean	std	max	min	ptp
Score	8	2	3	2	2

If the scores are applied to the profiles the most exposed/different profiles get the highest scores. For the profile with number 121148 we can see that the sliding score got the highest at the time of the loss start (first dashed vertical line) and remained as such after this time. The second suspicious profile with number 76305 indicated in previous section didn't get higher scores till latter in the loss period.

Figure 66. Sliding scores, EyPESA pilot, Canovellas case.

Detection based on consumption prediction

Another set of indicators for the source of the NTL loss detection is a forecast of the consumption of the individual profiles. For each profile the consumption is predicted week by week according to previous consumptions. An example prediction for the profile number 121148 is presented in Figure 67. In the figure it can be well seen why the sliding scores in the previous section were the highest for the smart meter in question.

Figure 67. Example profile consumption prediction, EyPESA pilot, Canovellas case.

For all the predictions the following scores have been observed:

- diff: a difference sum between prediction and consumption
- absdiff: an absolute difference value sum between prediction and consumption
- mean: mean value of the difference values
- absmean: mean value of absolute difference values
- sqroot: a square root value of the differences

Based on these scores in Canovellas case the two smart meters indicated in Table 25 have the highest rank based on the prediction differences. Again, these two meters should be considered as potential culprit for further investigation.

Table 25: Highest scores based on profile consumption predictions, EyPESA pilot, Canovellas case.

	diff	absdiff	mean	absmean	sqroot
130768	58.149629	67.857385	0.252824	0.295032	6.753825
133308	-8.227456	126.892140	-0.035772	0.551705	11.709931

Data assessment

Table 26. Data assessment for service 4.2, JSI approach.

Data source needed	BD4OPEM ontology	Data quality assessment	Impact of the quality on the service
Network region bubble data (all meters and transformer station measurement)	Smart meter	Low	High

Service conclusions

The application of S4.2 service implementation - JSI Fraud patterns detection in Spanish pilot shows that the service is suitable for the Spanish environment and use case of illegal plantation detection. The service provides a number of statistical analysis and results that can support NTL cases investigation and even serve as evidence in court.

Due to lengthy report and amount of results the content could be a bit hard for to understand for untrained personnel. One of the challenges in Spanish pilot was calculation of the loss; not all the cases data has the "bubble" properties and the loss itself didn't exhibit typical patterns in all cases as would be expected from plantation electricity demand.

4.7 S5.1 – Flexibility Forecast results

UPC approach: Flexibility forecast

Introduction of the service

Name: Flexibility forecast

Category: Flexibility and demand response

Task: T4.3

Location on the grid: LV grid and/or MV grid (UPC)

This service aims to forecast the available flexibility within an aggregator’s portfolio in order to know how much flexibility can be activated in a specific time horizon. The objective is to provide the aggregator with a tool to estimate flexibility and provide this service to different stakeholders, such as the Distribution System Operator (DSO) or the Balance Responsible Party (BRP) in later stages and services.

Table 27. Use cases for the S5.1 service.

Use case	Description
UC1	<p>As an aggregator, you want to know in advance the flexibility available on the grid. I want to know in advance the flexibility available on the grid for the next day. So that I can: optimise my portfolio (BRPs?).</p> <p>Acceptance Criteria: When I run the flexibility forecast service I obtain the hourly flexibility forecast for the next day.</p>

Use Case 1

The end user then accesses the prediction of the available flexibility for the next day hour by hour with the “forecast” section.

Figure 68 shows the graph on the UI representing the forecast, with the KPIs used to interpret the curve on the right. We can observe there is for instance a prediction of three peaks of Flexibility Availability at 12h, 16h and 19h. It means we can only use flexibility during these hours.

The user analyst can download the graph (it will be downloaded as in Figure 69) and the data as an excel file (as in Figure 70).

Figure 68. Forecast 24h ahead of Flexibility Availability (“Forecast” section of the UI).

Figure 69. Plot downloaded from the UI.

timestamp	prediction
2019-10-31 00:00:00	0,0134274
2019-10-31 01:00:00	0,0134274
2019-10-31 02:00:00	0,45338205
2019-10-31 03:00:00	0,43592584
2019-10-31 04:00:00	1,51570117
2019-10-31 05:00:00	1,63864255
2019-10-31 06:00:00	1,36912298
2019-10-31 07:00:00	1,85296607
2019-10-31 08:00:00	1,69188488
2019-10-31 09:00:00	1,47584176
2019-10-31 10:00:00	1,02557373
2019-10-31 11:00:00	0,50470513
2019-10-31 12:00:00	1,29387319
2019-10-31 13:00:00	0,01437109
2019-10-31 14:00:00	0,01437109
2019-10-31 15:00:00	0,01437109
2019-10-31 16:00:00	0,01437109
2019-11-01 00:00:00	0,01378833
2019-11-01 01:00:00	0,25734276

Figure 70. Excel view of the data downloaded from the UI (actual values y and prediction).

The “model info” section can also provide insights for the aggregator to better understand the data and compare possible future models (metrics available) as it is presented on Figure 71.

Figure 71. "Model info" section of the UI.

Data assessment

Table 28. Data assessment for S5.1, UPC approach.

Data source needed	BD4OPEM ontology	Data quality assessment	Impact of the quality on the service
Battery Storage	SOC,Battery	Good	High
EV charging power	activaImport	Medium	High

Service conclusions

The results are useful for DSOs and BRPs as an additional tool to be able to monitor which flexibility they should buy or not.

Nevertheless, the grid doesn't have enough storages available to allow a real flexibility.

Indeed, there are only few hours by day where flexibility is available, this misleads the model in the prediction.

Further improvement thanks to the feedback from the testing of the service can be an automatization of the service allowing the user to have the KPIs without running the model manually every day, also the possibility to zoom in the plot of the UI to better understand and interpret the forecast and training predictions.

JSI approach: Flexibility forecast

Introduction of the service

Name: Flexibility forecast based on price signals

Category: Flexibility and demand response

Task: T4.3

Location on the grid: LV grid

Being able to predict a customer's reaction to a price change is useful in a real-time power pricing setting where consumers are sensitive to changing rates. This study suggests estimation of aggregated load flexibility based on the historical price-response dynamics of consumers and demonstrates how one-way price signals can be utilized to control the aggregated electricity consumption.

The proposed approach requires aggregated historical consumption data along with the historical and current weather information to estimate "price-based" demand-side flexibility.

Table 29. Use cases for the S5.1 service, JSI approach.

Use case	Description
UC1	As a aggregator I want to forecast a flexibility potential during future flexibility events based on network price change in a network region.

Use Case 1

Flexibility model

In the section the day selected for estimating the flexibility is presented, as can be seen in the figure below. The modelling of the flexibility is briefly explained.

The region consumption for the target day and region, Thursday, 8th of October 2021, in EyPESA network shows the daily profile in the network. The daily profile is based on combined consumption at CT-525 and CT-886 transformers with 1 hour resolution. The daily profile shows atypical consumption for a household region with quite late evening peak.

Please note the flexibility numbers provided are not properly scaled. The service needs pilot population numbers to be scaled properly.

Figure 72. Consumption for event day 8-oct in EyPESA pilot.

Forecasted flexibility event

To model the harvested flexibility on the scheduled events, the event data is removed from the dataset. This dataset is further used for forecasting the consumption of users at the time of the events. The real consumption during the event time period is then subtracted from the predicted consumption to estimate the flexibility harvested from the event.

After modelling the flexibility harvested and acquiring the weather data, event data (such as day of week, season), the normalized flexibility during the events can be calculated. These features can be further used to predict the aggregated price-based demand response flexibility that can be achieved by changing the price or by increasing the target population.

The flexibility event of two hours has been estimated in the figure below. The event itself is marked with the shaded area. In all six hours of the consumption are presented, two hours before the event, two hours after the event and 2 hours of the event itself. All in all, 24 15-minute values of flexibility are estimated. The event is modelled as the data is available in 15-minute intervals. If the data was available at 1-hour intervals the data values are filled in with extrapolation.

In Figure 73 can be seen that the flexibility prediction is quite uniform over the event interval with somehow extended effect also after the event. There are no indications of the before or after event larger consumption due to reduced consumption during the event.

Figure 73. Flexibility prediction during the event day.

Figure 74 shows the effect of the price change on the user's response on demand flexibility. The price scale has a significant effect on the user's demand flexibility. However, further increase in the price will not add much more to the flexibility harvested. Thus, price change should be designed according to the arctan function as after a certain point, consumers become numb to the further price change.

Figure 74. Effect of the price change on user's response on demand flexibility.

Figure 75 shows the effect of the change in pilot strength on the harvested demand flexibility. The increase in the pilot strength has a significant effect on the amount of flexibility harvested. The prediction of the flexibility harvested is linearly related to the number of smart meters involved in the event implementation.

Figure 75. Effect of the change due to harvested flexibility.

Service KPIs

The section on service KPIs reports two major KPIs:

- Total flexibility in a given time frame: with selected event day, the total flexibility provided under 120 minutes time frame is 36.36 kWh at population 3500 and price scale 20.
- Average flexibility availability in a given time frame: with the selected event day, the average flexibility availability under 120-minute time frame is 3.51%.

Data assessment

Table 30. Data assessment for S5.1, JSI approach.

Data source needed	BD4OPEM ontology	Data quality assessment	Impact of the quality on the service
Historic smart metering measurements in network region (TR level)	Smart meter	High	High
Historic and forecasted weather measurements (temperature, radiation, precipitation)	Weather data	Adequate	High

Service conclusions

Service results show that the model developed in the Slovenian pilot has potential to be transferred and implemented also in Spanish environment. The method developed can be applied with a low cost to the target environment. What is still needed are price incentives that are compatible with the ones available in original pilot.

4.8 S5.2 – Flexibility aggregated services for BRPs results

Introduction of the service

Name: Flexibility aggregated services for BRPs

Category: Flexibility and demand response

Task: T4.3

Location on the grid: LV

Flexibility aggregated services for BRPs are predictive tools to assist the operational decisions of the BRPs. The “Day-Ahead Portfolio Optimization” use case aims at minimizing electricity purchase costs on the day-ahead market by activating flexibility requests at a cheaper price to supply the BRP’s portfolio. The second use case, “Self-Balancing portfolio” forecasts TSO’s and BRP’s schedule deviations, predicting periods for which it is advised to activate flexibility, avoiding deviations against the system.

Table 31. Use cases for the S5.2 service.

Use case	Description
UC1	<p>As a Balance Responsible Party (BRP), I want to: Predict the profile of the total costs related to electricity purchase on the day-ahead market and know how much flexibility I need to activate. So that I can minimise the total electricity related costs of my portfolio by activating flexibility.</p> <p>Acceptance criteria: When I run the forecasting service for my portfolio, I know how much flexibility I should buy for the next day to reduce the costs on the day-ahead market.</p>
UC2	<p>As a Balance Responsible Party, I want to predict the deviations from the declared energy schedule of the Transmission System Operator and of my portfolio. So that I can be prepared to activate flexibility when deviations against the system are predicted.</p> <p>Acceptance criteria: When I predict the deviations of BRP’s and TSOs portfolio I want to know when to activate flexibility to avoid deviations against the system.</p>

Use Case 1: Day-Ahead Portfolio Optimization

The Day Ahead Portfolio Optimization predicts the total costs and energy provision for the next day, as well as showing records of historical predictions. Figure 76 provides an example of the UI, showing the choice of the target date, the required input parameters as well as the calendar interactivity and access to historical forecasts. The service can be easily executed multiple times with different input parameters, allowing the user to analyse the sensitivity to the flexibility price and max cost inputs.

ESTABANELL

Forecast Target Date: Flexibility Price: Max Cost:

Service Contract: Market Data Contract:

« < febbraio 2021 > »

LUN	MAR	MER	GIO	VEN	SAB	DOM
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10	11	12	13	14
15	16	17	18	19	20	21
22	23	24	25	26	27	28

■ Successful
 ■ Failed
 ■ Pending

Figure 76. User interface, input parameters, historical and target date choice.

For successful execution, the BRP needs to provide the two inputs “Flexibility price” and “Max cost”. “Flexibility price” expressed in €/MWh represents the price at which flexibility can be activated for the next day, chosen by the BRP according to the contracts with the aggregator or the internal flexibility activation costs. The second parameter, “Max Cost”, expressed in €, represents the maximum hourly cost that the BRP is willing to pay on the day-ahead market (DAM) before activating flexibility. If, for a given hour, the total cost of electricity purchase on the DAM is forecasted to be above the threshold, then, the flexibility request is made. On the DAM electricity is bought only until the “Max cost” is reached, then, it is purchased via flexibility request.

Figure 77 shows the results of the execution of the service for the day 24/02/2021, selecting a Flexibility Price of 25 €/MWh and an hourly Max cost of 2200 €. The plot “Predicted DAM vs flexibility costs” indicates how electricity is purchased, according to the chosen input values. It is obtained by multiplying the results of the DAM electricity price predictions with the BRP’s portfolio demand prediction. For the displayed day, the “Max cost” effectively is able to identify the peaks of the total costs. The line in blue, “Total costs DAM”, represents the costs of electricity purchase on the DAM, limited by the “Max cost”. The line in green “Total cost flex” displays the total costs to supply the BRP’s portfolio, adding to the costs on the DAM the costs of the flexibility request, purchased at the previously input “flexibility price”.

Figure 77. Costs of electricity on the DAM and with flexibility purchase.

Having evaluated how much daily costs should be allocated to the purchase of flexibility, the algorithm computes the equivalent amount in energy, as shown by the plot “Predicted demand vs Flexibility request”, displayed in Figure 78. The blue line “Predicted demand” represents the predicted consumption of the BRP’s portfolio before the implementation of the strategy, whereas the green line “Flexibility request” shows the amount of energy recommended to be purchased via flexibility activation, instead of being acquired on the DAM. It can be seen how it is only activated when the operational costs are forecasted to exceed the threshold defined by “Max cost”.

Figure 78. BRP’s portfolio energy demand and suggested flexibility request.

Finally, the KPIs are computed to show how the service performs for a given day. Show in Figure 79, are summarized the sums of the hourly profiles calculated, namely the total amount of flexibility requested and its cost, the total costs of DAM electricity purchase and the estimated savings by following the suggested strategy. Overall it can be noticed that the proposed strategy is beneficial for the BRP, successfully identifying cost reduction opportunities.

FLEXIBILITY OPTIMIZATION METRICS

Figure 79. Day ahead portfolio optimization KPIs.

Use Case 2: Self-balancing Portfolio Optimization

Although energy schedules are made as accurately as possible, the final delivery of electricity is seldom congruent to what initially declared. This is true for both the program of the Transmission System Operator (TSO) and the BRP’s portfolio. The Self-balancing Portfolio Optimization aims at improving the BRP’s assets management by studying the sign of the deviations from the declared energy schedules of both his portfolio and of the TSO, trying to avoid imbalance penalties that occur when the declared schedule is not respected, incrementing the system instability.

The results of two forecasting algorithms are combined to suggest action signals to the BRP on the day ahead of electricity delivery. The first is to predict the TSO deviations and the second the BRP portfolio deviations. Figure 80 shows the results of the imbalances predictions, with binary values being shown. The value of 1 means that there is an excess of electricity, for the TSO represents an excess of production whereas for the BRP an excess of demand. The value of 0, on the other hand, represents a negative deviation. Lack of electricity production from the TSO side and lack of consumption from the BRP.

Figure 80. TSO and BRP deviations forecast.

The directions of the deviations, then, are compared to generate action signals in the hourly periods when the deviations bring to a further imbalance of the overall electricity system. The plot shown in Figure 81 displays the periods of suggested flexibility activation, indicated by the value of “1”. When the value is “0”, then no flexibility activation is required. Furthermore, the Key Performance Indicator (KPI) shown below the plot summarizes the daily predicted deviations, indicating the percentage of deviations against the system.

PERIODS ACTIVATE FLEXIBILITY

PERCENTAGE OF DEVIATIONS AGAINST SYSTEM
58.33 %

Figure 81. Suggested flexibility activations to restore electric system balance and daily percentage of deviations against the system.

Data assessment

Table 32. Data assessment for S5.2.

Data source needed	BD4OPEM ontology	Data quality assessment	Impact of the quality on the service
BRP demand	Market_Data	Good quality	High
BRP portfolio imbalance	Market_Data	Good quality	High
TSO imbalance	Esios API	Good quality	High
Market generation sources	Esios API	Good quality	High
SPOT electricity prices	Esios API	Good quality	High

Service conclusions

The service comprised of the Day-Ahead Portfolio Optimization and Self-balancing Portfolio Optimization use cases offers valuable tools for BRPs. The Day-Ahead Portfolio Optimization service allows them to make informed decisions by predicting total costs and energy provision for the next day. By inputting flexibility prices and maximum cost thresholds, the BRP can strategically manage electricity purchases on the DAM through flexibility requests, optimizing cost savings. The visualization of results, such as the breakdown of DAM costs versus flexibility costs and suggested flexibility requests, empowers the BRP to make efficient choices. On the other hand, the Self-balancing Portfolio Optimization service addresses the challenges of balancing electricity delivery schedules. By identifying excesses and shortfalls in

electricity supply and demand, the service generates action signals for the BRP to avoid imbalance penalties while enhancing system stability.

Future work includes the improvement and personalization of the inputs for the Day Ahead Portfolio Optimization, such as the possibility of adding a 24h profiles instead of constant daily values. In addition, the flexibility provisions can be further investigated, including a study specifying the flexible resources required to supply the energy requests.

Additionally, the following feedback was raised during the testing:

- UI improvement with automatization of inputs (they are reset after every execution)
- Further sign of flexibility activation (upward or downward)

4.9 S5.3 – Flexibility aggregated services for DSOs results

UPC approach: Flexibility-based AC OPF

Introduction of the service

Name: Flexibility Aggregated services for DSOs

Category: Flexibility and Demand Response

Task: T4.3

Location on the grid: MV/LV network

DSOs are one of the main stakeholders to purchase flexibility services instead of changing the network topology or curtailing power for congestion management. This service calculates the flexibility request for the DSO for a correct operation of the network and sends that request to the aggregator, the entity providing the flexibility. This section considers two different approaches for mitigating and managing distribution network operation. UPC approach presents a methodology for mitigating distribution network congestion based on a flexibility-based AC-OPF approach, while JSI approach presents a methodology for congestion management based on neural networks and LSTM.

Under the network operation timeframe, the DSO faces two main problems, which are congestion management based on over currents, and voltage/reactive power control based on under and over voltages. The first one consists in avoiding the thermal overload of system components by reducing peak loads where a failure due to overloading may occur. The latter, voltage/reactive power control, is based on using load flexibility by increasing or decreasing loads and generation sources to avoid exceeding the voltage limits, typically, when PV systems generate significant amounts of electricity.

This tool provides DSOs the possibility to calculate the required flexibility to be activated in a specific time period and location. The objective is to aid the DSO in efficiently managing the expected congestion. Additionally, this service provides a tool for DSOs to calculate flexibility within the grid, generating insights for future management of the grid. Thus, using this service, DSOs can reduce investments in grid reinforcements by profiting from the available flexibility.

Table 33. Use cases for the S5.3 service.

Use case	Description
UC1	<p>As a DSO analyst, I want to: generate a congestion management plan for the next day. So that I can gain insights into congestion management and the efficiency of flexibility sources.</p> <p>Acceptance criteria: The system displays flexibility source values, congestion percentages, and detailed flexibility insights for selected days.</p>
UC2	<p>As a DSO analyst, I want to: evaluate the grid I managed before and after my dispatch of flexibility. So that I can directly assess the impact of the flexibility request on line loading and voltage improvements.</p> <p>Acceptance criteria: The system displays snapshots of the grid pre and post-flexibility request for any chosen hour and allows downloading of these images, along with the power injection of flexibility sources per bus throughout the day.</p>

Use Case 1

After the service is executed for a specific day, we can observe several interesting values for the flexibility of the flexible sources as shown in Figure 82. The service offers the possibility to observe values related to the flexibility sources. In this case, we can see that the flexibility sources capacity needed to clear congestions is 0.60% of 4.80 kVA of flexible power available. Also, we can observe the usage of the flexibility sources, in terms of times instances (for EyPESA is a frequency of 1 hour). For most of the sources is 2 hours of usage, given that there are not many instances in the day where the grid is stressed. However, we observe that the congestion clearing is 100%, so for that specific case, the sources installed in the grid are enough to cover and avoid congestions, as seen in Figure 83.

Figure 82. Service UI Execution Home.

Figure 83. Period flexibility statistics.

When selecting the specific day, we can retrieve more information about the needed flexibility. As seen in Figure 84, from the requested flexibility field, we can observe that the flexibility available in this case is 4.80 kVA. Also, we can observe the most loaded lines and hour with higher load, which is at 21:00h. Additionally, we can observe the statistics for each of the flexibility sources used.

Figure 84. Forecast Day results.

Use Case 2

One important feature that this service offers, is the possibility to see the grid before and after the application of the Flexibility Request (FR) calculated by the algorithm. This is important as the analyst can see the reduced loading of the lines and improvement of voltages, if any. In Figure 85, we can see the snapshots of the grid before and after of the FR, for any desired hour. The EyPESA pilot is a MV grid and figure shows the FR at 21:00h. The images can be downloaded for any posterior purpose desired by the analyst. Additionally, the analyst can also observe the injection of power of the flexibility sources per bus during the whole day, as shown in Figure 86.

Figure 85. Flexibility Request.

Figure 86. Flexibility sources injection by the bus they are connected to.

Data assessment

The data required to establish the service mainly comprehends topology and grid parameters of the grid, and forecast calculations. The specific data files for this service can be observed in Table 34.

Table 34. Data Assessment for service S5.3, UPC approach.

Data source needed	BD4OPEM ontology	Data quality assessment	Impact of the quality on the service
Grid topology	Featurecollection	Full information of topology	High

Service conclusions

The service offers interesting results and information to the analyst and user. However, its functionality is subjected to the regulations and configuration of flexibility markets where the DSOs is. The service’s objective is to present the user information regarding flexibility procurement, however, there are many details regarding this type of procurement. However, the service’s current output is very interesting to have a first look to flexibility needs within the grid. For future iterations, the service could benefit from more details regarding the flexibility sources in the grid as input. For the development, the service can add more explanation on the flexibility request, aligned with current strategies of the DSO.

Additionally, feedback raised during the testing of the service is as follows:

- The red values for weekends in the calendar in the UI home calendar can be misleading.
- The values of the flexibility sources should be given in KW and not KVA.
- In the last figure (Figure 86) the indices should relate to the actual name of the buses, as then it is difficult to recognize to which bus they flexibility sources are connected.

JSI approach: Flexibility services for DSOs based on neural networks

Introduction of the service

Name: Flexibility Aggregated services for DSOs

Category: Flexibility and Demand Response

Task: T4.3

Location on the grid: MV/LV network

Flexibility services for DSOs provide necessary services for the DSOs to schedule flexibility events in a region of their network. The services provide a prediction of consumption in the target region and propose an event schedule at the time of the peak.

Table 35. Use cases for the S5.3, JSI approach.

Use case	Description
UC1	As a DSO, I want to be given support in preparation of flexibility events with a forecast of consumption profile in the target region and selection of potential time slots of the events.

Use Case 1

The predictions are based on a subsection of the transformer station smart metering data from the year 2017 to 2021 for the substations CT-525 and CT-886. The complete profile is shown below. Though the profile was very carefully selected it has some periods of bad data in early summer 2021.

Figure 87. Predictions for SS CT-0525 and CT-0886.

The predictions section reports on the importance of the features and errors in fitting the predictions to the train and test set. The results could be used to understand how good the algorithm is for predictions based on the provided data and which features are considered most important.

Figure 88. Load predictions for SS CT-0525 and CT-0886.

From the features we can see that the most important is the temperature which is followed by consumption shifted for one week. The fitting of the test and train set shows that the predictions won't be great, the data is not optimal for the algorithm selected by the developer.

Below are given the predictions for the selected week. We see the amplitudes of the predicted consumptions, in red, are well off the consumption realization, in blue. The peak times seem to be mostly matched, the amplitudes are off for date from 6th to 8th of November.

Figure 89. Accuracy of prediction: Realisation versus prediction.

The accuracy of the results is given in the next table. The most important parameter for the service is the Peak hour difference. Based on this parameter the event intervals for the flexibility events are chosen. From the results we can see similar picture as from the figure, the peak error is quite substantial for some days, but the peak hour prediction is on spot, all the peak times have been predicted correctly.

Table 36. Accuracy figures for the prediction calculations.

date	peak error [%]	min error [%]	corr	ptp [%]	std [%]	mean [%]	error [kW]	MAE	MSE	RMSE	Peak hour difference
2021-11-03	-10.77	-13.14	0.934821	-9.91	4.33	-3.51	0.0	4.641538	37.314058	6.108523	0 days
2021-11-04	-5.35	-14.34	0.967061	-6.71	-9.18	-4.70	0.0	3.632779	22.427085	4.735724	0 days
2021-11-05	-26.76	-9.97	0.952300	-35.20	-15.16	-7.35	0.0	4.900546	40.714004	6.380753	0 days
2021-11-06	-8.78	-11.67	0.944490	-7.89	-1.91	-0.83	0.0	4.005701	26.777493	5.174697	0 days
2021-11-07	19.43	-16.23	0.906599	30.60	31.93	6.17	0.0	7.380340	87.237505	9.340102	0 days
2021-11-08	-3.21	-18.86	0.905763	1.67	2.89	-5.49	0.0	5.974332	68.640189	8.284937	0 days
2021-11-09	9.35	-21.29	0.961973	17.56	20.63	4.50	0.0	5.812400	47.442573	6.887857	0 days

An example event day presented below is Thursday, 4th of November 2021. In the table above we can see the peak prediction is spot on the hour and the proposed interval fits the realization consumption well. The suggestion of the event for the DSO seems to be correct.

Figure 90. Accuracy of predictions for a given day.

Data assessment

Table 37. Data assessment for S5.3, JSI approach.

Data source needed	BD4OPEM ontology	Data quality assessment	Impact of the quality on the service
Historic smart metering measurements in network region (TR level)	Smart meter	High	High
Historic and forecasted weather measurements (temperature, radiation, precipitation)	Weather data	Adequate	High

Service conclusions

The service testing in EYPESA pilot has proved that the service developed in the Slovenian pilot can be replicated in the other pilots as well. The service is adequate for support of flexibility event organization and can be used in the Spanish environment in the future, if the price-based incentives will be available.

4.10S6.1 – Energy management at household or at community level results

Introduction of the service

Name: Energy management at household or at community level

Category: Smart house, buildings and industries

Task: T4.4

Location on the grid: LV

The Energy Management System (EMS) service is a control and monitoring system for optimal operating of electrical assets at community level. The objective is to minimize the overall energy community electricity bill.

Table 38. Use cases for the S6.1 service.

Use case	Description
UC1	<p>As a renewable energy community operator, I want to optimise the behaviour of a centralised battery with renewable generation. So that I can: Minimise the electricity bill, seeking the common benefit of a group of buildings.</p> <p>Acceptance criteria: When I run the EMS for an energy community, I get the optimal control signals of the centralised storage unit and PV generation, if flexible, that minimise the community energy cost.</p>

Use Case 1: Renewable energy community cost minimization

This use case aims to minimize the overall electricity bill, enhancing the energy efficiency as well, of a renewable energy community (REC) located in Granollers, Spain.

This REC comprises four buildings, encompassing office spaces and server facilities. The core components of this community include a centralized battery and photovoltaic generation infrastructure, both co-located within a single smart meter exclusively dedicated to managing generation assets. This smart meter is equipped for bidirectional energy flow, enabling the community to either export excess energy to the grid or procure additional energy as needed. For a visual representation of this renewable energy community's layout, please refer to Figure 91.

Figure 91. EyPESA renewable energy community scheme simplified.

Step 1. Creation of a new project

To display the results, the initial step entails creating a project and furnishing vital details regarding the energy community. This encompasses comprehensive information about the buildings, including their respective electricity tariffs. Additionally, it encompasses data pertaining to the flexible elements that can be utilized to activate flexibility, such as the battery in this specific use case. Furthermore, it necessitates the inclusion of input data necessary for making accurate predictions regarding both consumption and generation.

To show the results, you must first create a project and provide information about the energy community: about the buildings, the electricity tariffs that each of them have, information about the flexible elements available to activate flexibility (the battery in this use case), information about the input data to make the consumption and generation predictions.

Figure 92. S6.1 User interface. Creation of a new project.

Before starting with the service's results obtained, the centralized battery parameters selected for this case study are shown in Table 39 below. It would be possible to modify some of them, if necessary.

Table 39. EyPESA energy storage system parameters for Use Case 1.

Battery parameters	Values	Units
Maximum charging power	90	kW
Maximum discharging power	90	kW
Maximum state of charge allowed	189.9	kWh
Minimum state of charge allowed	31.65	kWh
Initial state of charge	150	kWh
End of state of charge	150	kWh
Efficiency charging	0.955	-
Efficiency discharging	0.922	-

Table 40 provides a comprehensive overview of the fixed parameters associated with each building within the REC. Among these parameters, the generation coefficient rate represents the proportion of electricity associated with each building concerning the total electricity generated by the PV and battery. To illustrate, consider Building 1, which contributes 35% of the total electricity supplied by the shared generation.

Table 40. Building parameters: tariff type, contracted power and sharing coefficient.

Input Parameters	Building 1	Building 2	Building 3	Building 4
Spanish Electricity tariff type	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
Maximum Contracted Power Period 1	70	43.65	20.785	75
Maximum Contracted Power Period 2	70	43.65	20.785	75
Maximum Contracted Power Period 3	70	43.65	20.785	75
Maximum Contracted Power Period 4	70	43.65	20.785	75
Maximum Contracted Power Period 5	70	43.65	20.785	75
Maximum Contracted Power Period 6	70	43.65	20.785	140
Generation coefficient rate	0.35	0.15	0.02	0.04

Previous considerations:

- Same price tariff for all buildings.
- The state of charge of the battery is the same at the beginning and at the end of the optimisation.

Step 2. Renewable energy community optimization results

The tool operates for the next 24 hours. In this case study, it runs at 14:00 hours and gathers actual electricity buying and selling price rates through the Spanish electricity market API, Esios.

Figure 93 illustrates the consumption predictions for the four buildings and photovoltaic generation for the next 24 hours. This task is performed by *S6.2 Energy forecasting*, as presented in next section. Both services are connected, forming a composition of services, which will act as one.

Regarding the office buildings consumption forecasting results, a significant decrease in consumption is noticeable in Building 4, remaining constant during the final hour of the day and into the night. The other buildings exhibit lower associated consumption, which remains relatively consistent throughout the day. It can be seen that building 3 has a significantly lower consumption than the rest.

Figure 93. PV generation and buildings consumption forecasting for the next 24 hours.

The prices for the sale and purchase of electricity to the grid are shown in Figure X. The purchase price considers all associated taxes and 21% VAT for this case study. The sale price is based on the SPOT market.

It shows that the highest prices occur between 18:00-23:00 and 07:00-11:00 am, as expected.

Figure 94. Next 24 hours electricity price for buy and sell electricity.

Given that the primary aim is to minimize the expenses associated to grid electricity purchase, it is imperative to underscore the pivotal role of the prices depicted in Figure 95, as they exert significant influence over the REC optimization results. The solitary variable that can be actively managed is the battery, which will either charge or discharge based on the optimization findings. The chart in Figure 95 illustrates the optimal operational behaviour of the battery.

The results show that the battery discharges during periods with high electricity purchase prices (18:00-22:00) and takes advantage of this to charge during hours with lower prices (4:00-6:00), in order to be able to discharge again during expensive periods (9:00-10:00). It should be noted that the battery charging periods are done with PV surpluses or by purchasing directly from the grid.

Figure 95. Optimization results for battery charging and discharging.

As an energy community, the generation associated with each building (imposed through the sharing coefficients) is used to obtain the final net electricity, which is the one associated with the electricity bill, and therefore, during the periods of photovoltaic generation and battery discharge, the total electricity associated with each building decreases. However, when the batteries are charged by buying energy

from the grid, this cost is associated to each participant of the energy community, using the associated sharing coefficient (see period 5-6 am).

Figure 96. Optimization results. Final net electricity bought to the grid considering shared generation.

In Figure 97, the electricity sold to the grid is shown (meaning that more energy is injected into the grid than is consumed). Only building 3 sells energy to the grid. The explanation is as follows: Building 3 has been allocated a distribution coefficient of 2% of the total generation. However, Building 3 consumes less electricity than what is associated with its distribution coefficient. Therefore, it has a surplus for sale during periods when the battery discharges to the grid or during periods with photovoltaic generation.

Figure 97. Optimization results. Final electricity sold to the grid considering shared generation.

Step 3. Service's KPIs assessment

Finally, to assess the outcome of the service, the results of the KPIs proposed in WP4 D4.5 [8] are presented and displayed in Figure 98.

- Electricity cost reduction (€/day): Electricity bill savings thanks to the REC optimization tool.
- Percentage of electricity cost reduction (%): Percentage of electricity bill savings daily.
- Self-consumption (%): Percentage of total electricity consumed coming from local energy community's own generation sources (PV and batteries).

Figure 98. KPIs for Use Case 1

Data assessment

The following their associated name in CIM (if applicable), and the quality and impact it has on the service's outcome.

Table 41 collects and summarizes the primary input data needed to run this service, their associated name in CIM (if applicable), and the quality and impact it has on the service's outcome.

Table 41. Data assessment for S6.1

Data source needed	BD4OPEM ontology	Data quality assessment	Impact of the quality on the service
Buildings consumption forecast	None (S6.2 output already included in S6.1)	Good quality	High
PV generation forecast	None (S6.2 output already included in S6.1)	Good quality	High
SPOT electricity price for buy	None (data obtained directly through an external API)	Good quality	High
SPOT electricity price for selling	None (data obtained directly through an external API)	Good quality	High

Service conclusions

This service demonstrates the feasibility and satisfactory performance of the approach proposed in the BD4OPEM project. The price-based optimization achieves savings of approximately 23% on average compared to the REC baseline consumption. The contribution of photovoltaics compared to consumption is lower than this percentage; therefore, the battery plays a crucial role in achieving these savings.

The user interface provides an easy way to calculate the energy community optimization, providing the optimal storage control signals for the next 24 hours. The end-user can utilize this tool in order to control the centralized storage unit or as a

consulting tool to edit the parameters of the energy community and see if the optimization results and savings obtained would compensate for the implementation of the same with those parameters of the battery, building consumption or installed photovoltaic generation.

However, to implement this service, some challenges still need to be addressed, such as regulatory barriers due to the complex framework required to obtain the necessary permits and approvals for installation and operation. This can make it difficult for REC to secure financing and access to the energy grid, as conventional investors may need more certainty about investing in short-time tested business models. Additionally, technical challenges associated with integrating renewable energy sources into the energy grid and storage systems are common.

Despite these obstacles, this service demonstrates the multiple benefits to neighbourhoods and the environment, providing promising investment opportunities. One main advantage is the reduction of dependence on fossil fuels, resulting in a decrease in greenhouse gas emissions. By generating and consuming energy locally, RECs avoid losses due to the Joule effect and costly long-distance energy transmission and distribution lines. Furthermore, RECs can enhance energy security by reducing the vulnerability of areas to power outages and disruptions. They also promote community engagement and empowerment by enabling end-users and small groups to participate in the energy system, offering communities the possibility of generating income and having a more significant influence on the electricity market.

Future functionalities that could be added to this service are:

- Apply dynamic sharing coefficients that vary hourly and have different values daily.
- Add flexible elements within each building belonging to the energy community could optimize their behaviour alongside the centralized battery.
- Explore the participation of a REC in a Flexibility Market, where it can offer its flexibility in exchange for economic remuneration.

4.11S6.2 – Forecasting services results

Introduction of the service

Name: Energy forecasting

Category: Smart houses, buildings and industries

Task: T4.4

Location on the grid: LV, at smart meter level.

This service aims to predict the baseline consumption, flexible assets demand and generation curves at the household or community level within a short-term horizon.

Table 42. Use cases for the S6.2 service.

Use case	Description
UC1	<p>As an end-user/Renewable energy community operator, I want to make predictions of PV generation for the next 24 hours. So that I can optimise the renewable energy community energy bill.</p> <p>Acceptance criteria: if acceptable range error, use the predictions as input in the Energy Management System service.</p>
UC2	<p>As an end-user/Renewable energy community operator, I want to: Make predictions of office buildings consumption for the next 24 hours. So that I can optimise the renewable energy community energy bill.</p> <p>Acceptance criteria: if acceptable range error, use the predictions as input in the Energy Management System service</p>

As previously mentioned in the preceding service's section, the energy forecasting service is a mandatory input for S6.1 Energy Management system. Both services are connected, forming a **composition of services**, which will act as one. Therefore, the user interface used to display the prediction results will be the same as the one shown in section S6.1 Energy management systems, since both services are integrated in the same platform.

This section will show the results of the predictions made for the EyPESA demonstration site, both at the consumption level of each building and at the generation level. These predictions are mandatory input data for the energy community optimization service (S6.1), as shown in Figure 99.

Figure 99. Service's composition between S6.2 Energy forecasting and S6.1 Energy management system.

Use Case 1: PV generation forecast

The goal of the PV generation forecast is to provide a prediction of the power output for the next 24 hours. This is achieved by combining meteorological forecast and historical PV generation as inputs for the prediction model.

This case study shows the prediction results for the next 24 hours (from 14:00 to 13:00 the following day), using data from September 26, 2023.

Figure 100. PV generation forecasting for the next 24 hours.

Use Case 2: Office buildings consumption forecast

The following Figures illustrate the forecasting consumption for each building. The Y-axis shows significant variations in consumption magnitudes. Notably, buildings 4 and 1 exhibit the highest consumption levels in that respective order. Building 3, however, displays a consistent consumption pattern over 24 hours, indicating its likely function as a computer/server room. In contrast, the office buildings demonstrate a noticeable decline in consumption during non-working hours (evening and night), followed by an increase after 8 am.

Figure 101. "Building 1" consumption forecasting for the next 24 hours.

Figure 102. "Building 2" consumption forecasting for the next 24 hours.

Figure 103. "Building 3" consumption forecasting for the next 24 hours.

Figure 104. "Building 4" consumption forecasting for the next 24 hours.

Figure 105 presents predictions for all four buildings and PV generation. This comparative chart provides a more insightful perspective on the different consumption levels in buildings.

Figure 105. All buildings and PV generation forecasting for EyPESA renewable energy community.

Data assessment

The following Table 43 collects and summarizes the primary input data needed to run this service, their associated name in CIM (if applicable), and the quality and impact it has on the service's outcome.

Table 43. Data assessment for S6.2 Energy forecasting.

Data source needed	BD4OPEM ontology	Data quality assessment	Impact of the quality on the service
Temperatute	WeatherData; "temperature"	Good quality	High
Irradiance	WeatherData; "solarIrradiance"	Good quality	High
Historical PV generation	PV; "activeEnergyExport"	Good quality	High
Historical buildings consumption	Smart_Meter; "activeEnergyImport"	Good quality, but not much historical data available	Medium

Service conclusions

These results should be compared with the consumption and photovoltaic generation once the day has concluded, and these data have been obtained. This allows us to quantify the error metric associated with each prediction. If this metric consistently exceeds the expected error over a period of time, the prediction model should be retrained with more recent historical data or explore the input features to verify if they remain equally significant or if other features could be added.

As the developed tool does not receive daily updated data on new metered consumption and generation, it is not possible to display in the user interface real metrics comparing predictions with actual measurements. It will be the user himself who, with the results obtained, will be able to compare these estimates with their real values.

Some functionalities that would be interesting to add in this service are:

- Near real-time data acquisition from the energy community would allow to continuously optimize our operations in response to forecasting errors and unforeseen events.
- Automatically re-training models according to specific indicators, comparing predictions with actual measured.

4.12S7.1 – P2P trading results

Introduction of the service

Name: P2P energy trading

Category: Smart house, buildings and industries

Task: T5.4

Location on the grid: LV

Citizen Energy Communities (CECs) provide prosumers, consumers and small-scale community producers with the ability to locally trade their energy among its members. The P2P Trading service enables these transactions in a trusted and

automated fashion, through the use of smart contracts on the blockchain. The aim of this is to provide trusted trading between these end user CEC members and importantly also facilitate the trusted billing reconciliation between the CEC Administrators (that set up the CEC on behalf of its members) and the DSOs.

Table 44. Use cases for the S7.1 service.

Use case	Description
UC1	As a CEC Administrator I want to set up a CEC so to provide trusted trading in an automatic fashion on behalf of its members.
UC2	As a CEC Administrator I want to be able to contract a smart meter data set for P2P trading over a marketplace from the DSO concerned and benefit from trusted billing reconciliation

Use Case 1

In the Spanish P2P Trading pilot, a retailer acted as a CEC Administrator to setup and initialize the service for 3 smart meters.

The contracted service making use of an automatic fair trading cooperative algorithm for its 3 members is shown in Figure 106.

Figure 106. CEC Administrator setup & initialize view of P2P Trading Service.

Data assessment

Table 45. Data assessment for S7.1.

Data source needed	BD4OPEM ontology	Data quality assessment	Impact of the quality on the service
Smart meter	activeEnergyExport, activeEnergyImport	Good quality	High

Service conclusions

This P2P Trading service makes use of blockchain to provide a way for not just retailers but new entrants in the energy market to be able to provide CECs. The solution is flexible also to consider alternative models such as the retailer acting as Service Provider to new players in the market representing CECs and the blockchain can further be of benefit for sharing trading data between other retailers where the CEC Members may be subscribed to other retailers. This latter case was not piloted and only the basic first prototype was piloted and only for a cooperative trading algorithm. The service was successful, and the trading algorithm manage to determine the energy that should be equally traded among members of the Energy Community. As an upgrade, it would be very useful to set percentages or priority coefficients to have the possibility to stablish different sharing schemes.

4.13S8.1 – Asset and investment planning results

Introduction of the service

Name: Asset and Investment Planning

Category: Planning

Task: T4.5 Asset and Investment Planning

Location on the grid: MV and LV grid

This service aims to develop optimal investment strategies that contribute to the long-term planning using traditional assets combined with flexible assets to drive into an optimal decision-making. The objective is to minimize the capital expenditure and operational expenditure costs for DSOs.

Table 46. Use cases for Service 8.1.

Use case	Description
UC1	As a grid analyst, I want to evaluate the impact of integrating new loads into the MV Network by specifying the incremental growth percentage of a transformer.
UC2	As a grid planner, I want to determine the best techno-economic reinforcement strategy that mitigates congestions in lines and transformers.

Use Case 1: Impact study of demand growth

In this use case, the DSOs assess the impact of integrating new loads into the grid by specifying the transformer's incremental growth percentage. Figure 110 provides an example of a stress test using real energy data from the EYPESA Network. The steps to execute this service are as follows: firstly, DSO needs to select a transformer expansion loading percentage. In this example the secondary substation 03 is increased by 300% (to create congestion events). Then, a type of power flow analysis must be selected, in this case, time series power flow, from 05/02/2019 00:00 to 08/02/2019 23:00. The next step is to click the Run Power Flow button. Figure 111 shows the results of the power flow in a table format considering the worst-case hour from the selected date time range. Figure 112 shows the asset congestion of SS03 filled in red colour, which indicates that this asset is above the maximum rated capacity, which is 100 %. The DSO can run different scenarios to stress the network to simulate different horizon expansions.

Figure 110. Stress test scenario.

Figure 111. Power flow results of assets.

Figure 112 presents a colour GIS map showing the power flow results. The lines and transformers exceeding the 100% loading limit are in red colour, for example, the SS03 transformer. On the other hand, the assets in blue colour mean that asset

loading is below 50%. The nodes are also coloured depending on the voltage deviation. This colour style provides an immediate overview of the power flow simulation results to the grid analyst.

Figure 112. Transformer congestion in red colour.

Use Case 2: Best techno-economic planning solution

In this use case, we assume that the DSO has already identified the asset congestions in the distribution network. The planning service executes four planning strategies — two passive and two flexible planning alternatives. The asset list results box prints the most cost-effective and technically suitable solution, see Figure 113. This tool aims to assist the DSO grid planner in evaluating the impact of reinforcement decisions. In this instance, installing a transformer in parallel at SS03 with equivalent capacity and power emerges as the best techno-economic solution. The table results indicate that asset loading levels are now reduced by 50%. This enhancement ensures greater reliability and improved quality of the energy service.

Figure 113. Execution of planning actions.

Figure 114 and Figure 115 display the KPI results for the reinforcement solutions. Users can view the total percentage of decongestions for each asset and observe

voltage deviations for each node in per unit terms. Additionally, the total cost of the asset reinforcement solutions is provided. The results for these KPIs can be downloaded in a .csv format.

Figure 114. Asset decongestions results.

Figure 115. CAPEX and OPEX of planning solutions.

Data assessment

Table 47. Data assessment table for S8.1.

Data source needed	BD4OPEM ontology	Data quality assessment	Impact of the quality on the service
Grid Topology	Service_parameters	Good quality	High

Data source needed	BD4OPEM ontology	Data quality assessment	Impact of the quality on the service
Historical measurements	Smart_Meter	Missing values and Low energy consumptions	High
Asset Costs	Service_parameters	Missing Costs from DSOs	High

Service conclusions

The use of this service was interesting for the DSOs, especially in the simulation of the stress scenarios for future demand growth. In their opinion, the time series power flow simulation permits considering the peak values of a selected range of date-times. Also, the DSO can interact with the platform to provide more precise information regarding the expansion of the network based on new contract requests and vegetative projections. The quality of the historical data is important, and also a pre-processing module is recommended in this tool to ensure the harmonization of the data and the good performance of this service.

Feedback from DSOs is as follows:

- GIS map: Change the transformer icon to a square with the name displayed on the map. Display the name of the node in the GIS map.
- User interface: Date-time modification manually.
- Algorithm: Integration of EV charging stations in the Stress Test Scenario with real profiles. Integration of new feeder routes and substations to test the impact on the grid.
- Network: Modelling and Simulation of the LV network to analyse the voltage deviations.

4.14S8.2 – Asset estimation optimization for microgrids results

Introduction of the service

Name: Asset estimation optimization for microgrids

Category: Planning

Task: T4.5

Location on the grid: LV grid

This service is oriented towards highly reliable and redundant local energy systems or microgrids, such as hospitals or manufacturing plants, whereas the operational limits, the remaining capacity and the chance on critical failure of different assets are of major importance for a fail-safe operation of the grid.

The service should allow the pilot grid operators to explore new operational strategies and business cases. For example, semi-traction UPS-systems could be used for external (e.g. R1) or internal (e.g. voltage regulation) grid services. However, the safety prerequisites of the grid should never be violated, whereas an accurate state of health estimation is of major importance.

Table 48. Use cases for the S4.1 service.

Use case	Description
UC1	As a grid operator or asset operator, you wish to check the current state of health of your assets as well as the historical degradation profile of these assets.
UC2	The grid investment planner can check the remaining useful life of the different assets within his grid.
UC3	Microgrid operators you want to acquire knowledge on the different operational regimes of your assets and the impact it has on the degradation.

Use Case 1

Given the provided data of an asset, the service offers grid operators or asset operators' valuable feedback on the current state-of-health (SoH) of the asset under investigation. This by designated indexes such as (i) the capacity degradation (for the provided period), (ii) the percentage of expected lifetime reached and (iii) the expected remaining useful lifetime by conducting a similar behaviour/regime of the asset. This can be for both, a PV system (not a part of the Spanish pilot) or for a battery energy storage system (BESS - Figure 116). The analyst (i.e. grid operator or asset operator) gets an overview of the measured degradation, based on the provided data, as well as a forecasting. Furthermore, this is displayed as a function of the typical lifetime of such assets. For instance, a PV system will be reviewed based on the warranty time, while a battery energy storage system will be reflected towards the end-of-life capacity which is typically at a SoH of 80%.

Figure 116. Data analysis from a battery energy storage system.

Use Case 2

In order to help the grid planner with thoughtful choices towards future investments, the graphs (Figure 116) display the expected remaining useful lifetime. This by displaying the intersection between the forecasted capacity (i.e. maximal production or battery capacity for respectively the PV system and the BESS) and a 20% decrease compared to the maximum value.

Next to the graphs, the grid planner can also retrieve this information on the top of the UI, where the values are written as well. This is in case the PV system and/or battery maintain their current degradation. In other words, if the business-as-usual (BaU) applies.

Use Case 3

Finally, operators of distribution networks (or assets owner) whom includes a battery energy storage system may wish to know which impact the operational regime of their BESS might have on the degradation. To acquire this knowledge, the tool allows the operator to visualize the different regimes via a dropdown menu on the UI, Figure 117. This high-level degradation analysis differentiates in between parameters like: cycles/year, depth of discharge and power rating. Figure 118 shows the last step where an operator can even go in more detail to see how a specific operational profile affects the battery degradation. Because of the lack of variations in the battery history, the degradation model of the battery can't be trained accordingly, so the results as shown in Figure 117 and Figure 118 are very limited.

Figure 117. Degradation prognosis for different regimes.

Figure 118. Daily profile analysis.

Data assessment

Table 49. Data assessment table for S8.2.

Data source needed	BD4OPEM ontology	Data quality assessment	Impact of the quality on the service
Battery data: State of Charge	Storage data: State of Charge	Excellent	Quality is good. A higher sample rate and a higher data variability will increase accuracy
Battery data: Power	Energy meter data: Charged or discharged power [kW] or Energy [kWh]	Excellent	Quality is good. A higher sample rate and a higher data variability will increase accuracy

Pilot deployment:

The service will be tested on 1 grid battery system in the Spanish pilot.

Description of pilot set-up:

The set-up of the service in this pilot is adapted to the specific use case:

- Time series data is available for one battery system:
 - Battery ESS:
 - Data available from 2022-01-01 until 2022-03-31
- No solar systems or other assets are part of the pilot demonstration site or no data is available

Specific adaptations and remarks for pilot set-up:

No adaptations are needed. The length of the time series data is more than 1 year and should be sufficient, however the service will not generate any results because the battery is not used during the period of the data monitoring. The state of charge is fixed at 95% and the power is 0.0 at all timestamps. This means the algorithm cannot learn any behavior of typical operational profiles as well is not able to calculate a degradation profile based on operational choices.

Results for Spanish pilot:

Figure 119 shows the assets of the Spanish pilot that are modelled in this service. Because of the stationary regime of the real Spanish pilot battery (with ID: EYPESA_ESS), a battery from the VUB database is also included in the testing set-up such that the full working of the algorithm could be shown during the user testing process.

Figure 119. Overview of the Spanish pilot assets.

Figure 120 and Figure 121 show the service results for ESS1. The first one shows a summary of the battery behaviour based on the historical data. The second shows the results of the degradation model built on this historical data and shows the future projection.

Figure 120. Battery data analysis.

Figure 121. Battery degradation modelling.

As stated before, due to a lack of variability in the operational profiles, no effective degradation model could be built, trained and tested. For this reason, the results show only the initialized values without the ability to fit battery specific data on it. Without a more varying operational regime, no real conclusions can be drawn, except for the fact that the algorithm can currently run with the provided data. As the battery is used in the future and the dataset grows, the service is fully operational to process this data and generate new (and more useful) results.

Service conclusions

During the service testing, the service user had a positive feeling on the usage and applicability of the service. As a distribution system operator with multiple assets located on different places, the tool allows the system operator to keep track of the status of the different assets. Other feedback related to the UI can be summarized as follows:

The tool will provide valuable insights in the performance of the BESS systems connected to the network.

5 Project KPIs to be monitored in this deliverable

5.1 KPI 1.2: Dimension of data providers and volume of data managed

Table 50. KPI 1.2.

KPI Name: Dimension of data providers and volume of data managed	
KPI ID	1.2
Global objective	Large-scale dimension of demonstrator activities
Owner	EyPESA
Definition	<p>This KPI is targeting the dimension of data providers and volume of data managed, and aiming to include the following objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • O1.1. Relevance of pilot activities with respect to involved users, making sure there is a clear impact both in terms of technology/equipment and with respect to number of users involved. • O1.2. Involvement of different actors and impact on multiple stakeholders in the energy value chain. • O1.3. Scalability and replicability analysis to provide the needed means to both scale up from demo to large scale solutions and prove the same solution on multiple and different scenarios. <p>As stated in the GA, the initial 1.2 KPI statement was the following: “Data providers that are DSOs have to provide data from at least 50.000 smart meters”.</p> <p>However, during the development of the project it was detected that due to the huge variety of services needing other types of data apart from the SMs (i.e. market data or GIS data), and their partial unavailability in the 3 pilots, the target was unrealistic.</p> <p>Furthermore, OEDAS does not have SMs installed in their grid, except in few exceptional cases, and therefore cannot be considered for this KPI.</p> <p>Finally, in a later stage it was defined the target to 10.000 SMs for each pilot, only for ELCE and EyPESA. This number also considers not only the basic consumption curves, but also other parameters from SMs useful for the different services.</p>
Involved partners	The involved partners are DSO’s partners EyPESA and ELCE, and the data lake manager (WEP).
Calculation process and Formula	For EyPESA, the selection of SM strongly differs on the service tested and the way of uploading its information it also differs depending on the service. Meaning that there’s a huge difficulty to count easily all SM shared. We will assume that for every SS shared, EyPESA was sharing information from all SM hanging from this SS. For this reason, firstly, it will be gathered a list of all SS that were used in the service using Smart Meters data. With this, and using EyPESA’s internal tools, it will be retrieve the amount of Smart Meters that are hanging from every SS.

KPI Name: Dimension of data providers and volume of data managed	
	$N^{\circ} \text{ Smart Meters} = \sum_i SS_i \left(\sum_j SM_j \right) + \text{supervisors}$ <p>Where i is the service number SS is the secondary substation j is the SS number SM is the number of Smart Meters hanging from every SS And supervisors are the number of substation meters</p> <p>Note that, only the services that are sharing SM information will be include in the calculation. And also if one SM is present in two or more services, this will be counted only once.</p>
Unit	Number of Smart Meters
Target	Data providers that are DSOs and with high SMs deployment have to totally provide data from at least 20.000 digital meters.
Results at the end of the project	<p>The number of SS used are gathered per service:</p> $N^{\circ} \text{ Smart Meters} = (S1.1 + S1.2) + S3.1 + S4.2 + S6.1 + \text{supervisors}$ $N^{\circ} \text{ Smart Meters} = 6629 + 8 + 2345 + 5 + 78 = \mathbf{9065 \text{ Smart Meters}}$ <div style="display: flex; align-items: flex-start;"> <div style="width: 50%;"> </div> <div style="width: 50%; text-align: center;"> </div> </div> <p style="text-align: center; color: #808080;">Smart Meters for service S1.1 and S1.2</p>

5.2 KPI 2.1: Data coming from renewable technologies

Table 51. KPI 2.1.

KPI Name:	Data coming from renewable technologies
KPI ID	2.1
Global objective	Technological choice and provision of tools contributing to the Digital Marketplace for Energy
Owner	OEDAS
Definition	<p>Considering the uptake of renewable energy, it is important to have available data from different renewable technologies to shape adequate services. This KPI consist in the number of data sources available from different technologies.</p> <p>As some of the residential RE Sources are connected to the distribution level and services and pilot are tackling distribution level, the scope of KPI is therefore extended to renewable technologies and new technologies; like Energy Storage Systems, Heat Pumps, EV Chargers and V2G Chargers.</p>

KPI Name: Data coming from renewable technologies									
Involved partners	The involved partners are demonstration sites.								
Calculation process and Formula	$\left[\frac{\sum \text{Renewable Energy Tech. Assets} + \sum \text{New Tech. assets}}{\text{No of Services in Pilot}} + \frac{\text{No of RE source types and new Tech types}}{\text{Services Using "RE Tech. and New Tech. Assets" datas}} \right] > 1$								
Unit	Ratio								
Target	<p>Data available from 1 renewable energy asset (wind, PV Hydro, Geothermal) and 3 new technologies (ESS, V2G Charger, Heat Pumps, DC Chargers, etc.).</p> $\left[\frac{A}{B} + \frac{C}{D} \right] > 1$ <p>Calculation result $\left[\frac{A}{B} + \frac{C}{D} \right] > 1$ should be more than 1,</p> <p>A: No of Renewable Energy Tech. Assets +No of New Tech. assets B: No of Services in pilot C: No of RE source types and New Tech types D: Services Using "RE Tech. and New Tech. Assets" datas in pilot</p>								
Results at the end of the project	<p>EyPESA has 248 PV's for self-consumption in the area shared and 5 PV systems in the offices; 1 AC Charger; and 1 Energy Storage Systems in the area shared. So, Parameter A is 248+5+1+1=255 and parameter C is 3 (different assets).</p> <table style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="padding-left: 20px;">A: No of Renewable Energy Tech. assets +No of New Tech. assets</td> <td style="text-align: right;">255</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding-left: 20px;">B: No of Services in pilot</td> <td style="text-align: right;">18</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding-left: 20px;">C: No of RE Tech types and new Tech types</td> <td style="text-align: right;">3</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding-left: 20px;">D: Services Using "RE Tech. and New Tech. Assets" datas in pilot</td> <td style="text-align: right;">10</td> </tr> </table> <p>Result:</p> $\left[\frac{255}{18} + \frac{3}{10} \right] = 14,46 > 1$	A: No of Renewable Energy Tech. assets +No of New Tech. assets	255	B: No of Services in pilot	18	C: No of RE Tech types and new Tech types	3	D: Services Using "RE Tech. and New Tech. Assets" datas in pilot	10
A: No of Renewable Energy Tech. assets +No of New Tech. assets	255								
B: No of Services in pilot	18								
C: No of RE Tech types and new Tech types	3								
D: Services Using "RE Tech. and New Tech. Assets" datas in pilot	10								

6 Lessons learned & Conclusions

6.1 Lessons learned – Pilot’s perspective

From pilot's perspective, BD4OPEM has been an enriching project in which EyPESA has been able to learn and discover new concepts such as data spaces and data marketplaces, and also to participate in the definition of several valuable aspects of the Marketplace. Moreover, other essential lessons learned from the pilot have allowed EyPESA to establish a set point of the data situation in the company and to discover unknown issues and relevant services that bring value to the electrical grid.

First, by having to supply a huge amount of data to different partners made the company realise the state of disorganisation and state of quality of the data gathered from the different assets of the grid. The outcome of this is a clear task for EyPESA to create a data architecture that unifies and brings together all data gathered from its sources. This organization facilitates the participation in data marketplaces, enabling a proper treatment of the data internally, more profitable collaboration with other partners, and a better predisposition to open innovation, but most of all, it can facilitate the extraction of information, and hence, the value inherent in the data.

Related to the issue raised before is the data transfer, and the rising concern of data interoperability and data transparency in the sector. This was extremely visible in two aspects. One refers to bad quality of data and different formatting issues that make it difficult in a lot of cases the extraction of proper results in the simulations of the services. And the other refers to the process of harmonisation needed that also put some difficulties in running the same service for different companies.

Finally, through the different services tested in EyPESA's pilot, the DSO was able to extract direct value that was solving specific issues such as the phase connection from the Smart Meters; and data gaps and outliers from timeseries data. Also, involvement and learnings solving different challenges such as grid planning schemes or degradation models. Finally, the opportunity to participate in the definition of future services around flexibility. All these innovative solutions help the company to explore different methods of solving challenges, and learn while doing from new tendencies and concepts that will let us pave the way to future opportunities.

6.2 Lessons learned – Service developer’s perspective

From the service developers' perspective, the Spanish pilot has been a rich source of challenges and learning experiences. The complexities encountered, such as data availability and quality issues, showcased the real-world hurdles that service developers may face when implementing solutions. The careful consideration of these challenges has provided insights into refining and optimizing services for future deployments and upgrades.

The identification of constraints, including data gaps and communication challenges in specific areas, serves as a crucial input for service developers to improve their algorithms and methodologies. The adaptability demonstrated by developers, such as adjusting to data sharing timelines based on seasonal variations, or more generally by adapting their services to the available data, reflects the project's commitment to overcoming challenges and delivering a high-quality project in the end.

6.3 General conclusions

The Spanish pilot, hosted within EyPESA's electrical grid, has proven to be a pivotal testing ground for the diverse range of services developed in the BD4OPEM project. Specifically, the city centre of Granollers served as a dynamic environment for multiple services due to its high density and diverse energy assets. The successful integration of data from MV lines, substations, and smart meters showcased the adaptability of the Marketplace platform in a real-world, urban setting.

Furthermore, including a rural area in l'Ametlla del Valles, Bigues, Santa Eulàlia de Ronçana, and Seva highlighted the project's commitment to addressing challenges in more decentralized environments.

In conclusion, the Spanish pilot within the BD4OPEM project has been a great demonstration site to validate the scalability, flexibility, and real-world applicability of the developed tools and services. The lessons learned from the diverse areas of deployment, each presenting unique challenges, contribute to the project's overall success. The collaborative effort with EyPESA, legal compliance with data protection regulations, and the proactive consideration of future grid needs in rural areas highlight the project's approach to smart grid innovation.

As we move forward, these insights will not only inform the continued refinement of the BD4OPEM platform but will also serve as a valuable resource for future smart grid projects and service developers looking to navigate the landscape of energy services deployment.

7 Annex A: Storylines

7.1 S1.1 – Topology

Contract service

1. Go to the Marketplace main page and go to the search bar and look the service "Topology and network analysis".
2. Select the service desired
3. Contract the service, following the default and/or required contract parameters. Upload the data as required.
4. Execution of the service

Usability testing

5. After executing the service, follow the indicated steps to test several aspects.
 - a. Go to <https://app.bd4opem.odit-e.com> and try to login.

Figure 122. Odit-e app

- b. If login succeed, you should see a map with all your secondary substations.

Figure 123. Map with all secondary substations

- c. Click on a substation. A panel should open and display all smart meters linked to the substation. If GPS coordinates are given, smart meters should also appear on the map.

Figure 124. Display of all smart meters connected to the selected substation

- d. You can then click on *Analyze network* or on *Network analysis* tab to open the network analysis. On the network analysis page, you should be able to:
- i. Change filter on map to sort substation by load rate, imbalance rate, etc.
 - ii. Select a substation by clicking on it

- iii. For a selected substation, see different graphs : single wired topology, imbalance current radar, voltage and load distribution, voltage and load time duration curves

Figure 125. Single wired topology, imbalance current radar, voltage and load distribution, voltage and load time duration curves

6. Fill the questionnaire provide following the results and experience perceived after following the previous steps.

7.2 S1.2 – Observability

Contract service

1. Go to the Marketplace main page and go to the search bar and look the service “Observability”.
2. Select the service desired
3. Contract the service, following the default and/or required contract parameters. Upload the data as required.
4. Execution of the service

Usability testing

5. After executing the service, follow the indicated steps to test several aspects.
 - a. Go to <https://app.bd4opem.odit-e.com> and try to login.

Figure 126. Odit-e app

- b. If login succeed, you should see a map with all your secondary substations.

Figure 127. Map with all secondary substations

- c. Click on a substation. A panel should open and display all smart meters linked to the substation. If GPS coordinates are given, smart meters should also appear on the map.

Figure 128. Display of all smart meters linked to the substation

- d. You can then click on *Observability* tab to open the low voltage network state estimation. On the observability page, you should be able to:
 - i. Change filter on map to switch between voltage or load state estimation.
 - ii. Select a substation by clicking on it
 - iii. For a selected substation, see different graphs: active and reactive load estimated and measured (if available)
 - iv. Once a substation is selected, you may select on the map a smart meter to get its voltage state estimation.

Figure 129. Voltage state estimation of the selected smart meter

6. Fill the questionnaire provide following the results and experience perceived after following the previous steps.

7.3 S1.3 – Predictive maintenance in electrical power systems

The service planned in the EyPESA pilot was the predictive maintenance through classification. Classification of the equipment into maintenance classes. Roughly the classes are divided in one that has high probability of failure and the other with lower probability. The equipment is classified according to the features that are available for a particular class of the system. For example, networking and energy grid equipment like smart meters, are often accompanied by an ITC system collecting and monitoring the state of the equipment. A number of logs and error logs are available, internal registers state, together with some sensor information like temperature, etc. All these information can be utilised together with time as features that make classification possible. On the other hand, to train the models that could be used for classification, targets are needed as well. The targets tell which equipment has failed, when and at what conditions. The features of failed equipment are needed as well. As a general requirement, more information is available on failed equipment, better will be the classification model for the equipment still in use.

The solution is then extended with features prediction in the next period and maintenance cycle. The classification is performed again on predicted features and the equipment classified in a class with a high probability of failure is then flagged in the service report and returned to the service user.

Specific EyPESA case

In the EyPESA case the target class of equipment was smart meter concentrators. A smart meter concentrator is a crucial component of advanced metering infrastructure (AMI) systems used in the utility industry, particularly for managing and monitoring electricity, gas, or water consumption in residential and commercial buildings. It plays a pivotal role in collecting data from multiple smart meters and transmitting it to the utility company or data center for analysis and billing purposes. Smart meter

concentrators are typically monitored for their performance and state as part of the overall management and maintenance of advanced metering infrastructure (AMI) systems. Monitoring concentrators is essential to ensure the reliability and effectiveness of the entire AMI network.

In Spain the concentrators are prone to failures in summer months, when the temperatures are high. High rate of failures is possible in this time of year. During the year 2023 a six-month period has been planned in the EyPESA pilot in the summer to monitor the performance of the concentrators and log the failures if they occur. Based on these data the predictive maintenance service was planned to be provided.

Service usage

The intended service usage was aligned with the S4.2 predictive maintenance service based on prediction as was implemented in ELCE pilot. The service user should select the service type, either prediction or classification. For the service with classification the following data contracts were needed:

- A set of validated features related to the class of equipment. The features can be numerical or categorical. More diverse but unrelated features is better.
- A set of targets aligned with the features. There should be diverse set of targets defined, with enough equipment with failures and the rest in normal operating state. The time of the failure should be quite exact to be able to relate the data with the features.

The data contract is sufficient for the service to be run as all the other services that are run directly through the BD4OPEM Marketplace interface and project based Analytic Service Management (ASM) platform. The results of the service run should be a report, accessed through the ASM web user interface.

7.4 S2.1 – Detection of Measurement Errors

Contract a service

1. Go to the Marketplace main page and go to the search bar and look for the service “*Detection of Measurement Error*”.

Detection of Measurement Error No feedback for this service

This service offers the possibility of analysing data and identifying the eventual anomalies that might exist. Depending on the ty...

[See more](#)

Service Provider
Intracom Telecom

Creation Date
27/10/2022

Involved partners:

- Intracom Telecom**
Role Service provider
- CITCEA - UPC**
Role Algorithm developer

Figure 130. Contracting DoMe S2.1

2. Select the service.
3. Contract the service, following the default and/or required contract parameters.
4. Execution of the service through the Marketplace or by login to the Marketplace and running <https://dome.aks-marketplace.bd4opem.eu/>

EyPESA data contracts for DoME

Description data → data contract id

- 2 weeks of BRP consumption data of EyPESA portfolio:
 - 621af311-1cc2-4488-9f5f-bbbe9b369f6b
- One year (2019) of BRP consumption data of EyPESA portfolio
 - 5deeedfa-17a2-4573-a87b-5161d38b1f59
- Transformer consumption (CT281): 1 week of active energy:
 - d672801e-70b5-4353-ae8a-262f1b273342
- Granollers office building (lab-tic)
 - 5b83ef9e-3d29-4cf4-864f-a077ac588cea
- Granollers PV generation (1 week)
 - e4eacd0c-854b-49db-8b35-b3702aaa157f

Usability Testing:

1. In the initial application front-end, select the **Projects**.

2. Then, create a new project to test data by clicking **"Add new project"**

3. Write the project name and select the contracted data to be cleaned.

Create New Project

Name*

Data Contracts ⓘ*

4. Inside a project, several scenarios can be created and tested. Create a new scenario and select all the desired parameters. Then save and run the application.

Update Scenario

Name*

Anomaly detection Anomaly deletion Missing detection Train data

Coefficient anomaly*

Missing method

Missing threshold*

Outliers threshold*

Results file name ⓘ*

5. Go to the results section.
 - a. There are two tabs: TimeSeries and KPIs.
 - b. In the **Time-Series tab**, untreated and cleaned data are shown for comparison.

Selected Scenario Results

c. The **KPIs tab** displays the total number of missing data and outliers present in the dataset.

Test more datasets by creating new scenarios or projects.

- d. In order to test the project data and modify and combine the parameters, the service user has to access the project folder (green button).
- e. Eliminate the project clicking the red button.

7.5 S3.1 – Grid disturbance simulations

UPC approach: Congestions forecast for day ahead

1. Contract the service with the demanded parameters.
2. You will get your contracts on top. Select the desired to investigate.

Figure 131. Contracting service

3. Go to *Demand Forecast* tab and browse to several loads from the breakdown list and check the demand forecasted for a few loads and evaluate the response for each plot.
 - i) Check first aggregated demand

Figure 132. Display of aggregated demand

ii) Scroll through the dropdown list and review the forecast of other loads.

Figure 133. Dropdown list and forecast of other loads

4. Move to *Congestions* and select different lines to analyze their congestions, if any. Select to show the forecasted behavior for *Line 1* and *Line 2*. Following, select the *download button* to get the results in excel format for further analysis.

Figure 134. Congestion line 1

Figure 135. Congestion line 2

5. Go to *Report* tab, scroll down to appreciate the probabilities of congestions for all the lines for the all times of the day. Finally, push the *download file* button to obtain the report in excel form.

Hour	Probability [%]	Overload [kA]
00:00	0	0.01802203358028783
01:00	0	0.01615798985327933
02:00	0	0.0148973888088889
03:00	0	0.01374496497102659
04:00	0	0.013015822695225
05:00	0	0.01228425993300662
06:00	0	0.01221607474872278
07:00	0	0.01289464356834296

Figure 136. Report tab

VUB approach: Congestion control in distribution grids

1. Go to the Marketplace main page (<https://marketplace.bd4opem.eu/>) and using the search bar, look for the service "Congestion control in distribution grids".

Congestion control in distribution grids
 Reduction of voltage violations by suggestive phase balancing
 ★ 4/5
 Number of feedbacks: 2

Involved partners:
 Vrije Universiteit Brussel
 Role Algorithm developer
 We Plus S.p.A.
 Role Service provider

Service Provider:
 Vrije Universiteit Brussel

Last updated on:
 01/09/2023

Figure 137. Congestion control in distribution grids

2. Select the desired service ('**See more**') and follow the instructions.
3. Contract the service, following the default and/or required contract parameters. Upload the data as needed.
4. Execution of the service through the Marketplace, make sure you are logged in as '**Service User**', see top right corner. Click on '🔗' to access the service :

Figure 138. My Services

Or after being logged in on the Marketplace, you can directly run the service by navigating to: <https://s31vub.bd4opem.eu/>.

5. **Usability Testing:** After executing the service, follow the indicated steps to test various aspects.

Initial screen displays the **'Dashboard'** including information such as the contract duration and latest update

NOTE: your contract ID appears at the top.

Figure 139. Display of contract ID

- a. Go to the **'Project Overview'** tab, there you will find a list of all the projects you created including details such as the amount of grids you added to each project and a description of the project.

Figure 140. “Project Overview” tab

This tab will return a blank page for first time users, the next steps will guide you through the project creation. Other actions such as editing and uploading can be undertaken as well, see next pages.

The first action is to create a new project. By clicking on the **‘Create new Project’** button, a pop-up screen will appear:

Figure 141. New project

Here you can select your uploaded grids (i.e. contracted data) and make a selection of the grids you want to use for the simulations. In the example, we contracted four grids for the service.

Another possibility is to edit an existing project. For instance if you wish to modify the description or add new grids. Therefore, under the column **‘Actions’** click on ‘:’ for the grid you want to make changes, and hereafter click on **‘Edit’**. The following pop-up screen will appear where you can perform your modifications:

Figure 142. Edit the project

- b. Once a grid is selected, you can access the '**View Detail**' button which offers an overview of the grids within the selected project, in this example 'My_second_project_00'. Next to the list of grids within the project, it also provides information on (i) the training status – i.e. if the forecasting models have previously been trained or not –, (ii) the amount of connections the grid has, etc.:

Figure 143. Display of the details - overview of the grids

- c. One can also check details of the grids through the '**View Detail**' button. There you can analyse each of these connections for the selected grid. On the bottom of the page, another '**View details**' button is displayed.

ID	Consumer	Type	S (kW)	No. Phases	S (RES)	Type RES	Consumption (kWh)
cons_001	unknown	unknown	6.468	3	none	none	6183.62899999997
cons_002	unknown	unknown	5.344	1	none	none	3124.7989999998863
cons_003	unknown	unknown	5.82	1	none	none	4893.879999999925
cons_004	unknown	unknown	4.184	1	none	none	4761.40000000004
cons_005	unknown	unknown	8.284	3	none	none	5518.569000000015
cons_006	unknown	unknown	6.232	1	none	none	3306.7569999999655
cons_007	unknown	unknown	6.496	1	none	none	4178.514999999987
cons_008	unknown	unknown	4.316	1	none	none	3037.960000000063
cons_009	unknown	unknown	5.572	1	none	none	3283.2969999999405
cons_010	unknown	unknown	3.388	1	none	none	3879.351999999957

Figure 144. Display of the details of the connections for the selected grid

The latter redirects you to the a graphical visualization of the consumer, allowing to inspect the “Consumption profile” from each consumer:

Figure 145. Consumption profile

As well as the “Voltage profile”:

Figure 146. Voltage profile

- d. Next, for a trained grid, you can either select '**Access Results**' on the '**Grid Overview**' tab or navigate through the menu in the left panel and click on '**Data Analysis**' to inspect both the "individual impact" and "feeder impact".

The '**Individual impact**' tab allows you to inspect the influence each connection point has on other users. A graph represents the deviation that the selected connection point caused to neighbouring connection points in terms of V per kW.

Figure 147. Individual impact

- e. On the other hand, provided that the grid topology is not at hand, the '**Feeder impact**' guides you through heat maps that cluster all the connections points into groups which are highly correlated to each other.

Arrows on the top help you to navigate through the graphs of each individual group. Initially, the complete overview is given.

NOTE: Be aware that for large grids with a high number of connections, this might results in unreadable plots! To avoid this, go to the individual groups.

Figure 148. Feeder Impact

- f. Finally, the '**Congestion Forecast**' tab presents the results of the forecasting simulations, see '**Grid violation**'. To inspect the influence of stochastic grid disturbances invoked by renewable energy sources such as PV systems or electric vehicles (EVs), you can use the penetration level [%] through respective dropdown menu². In case of the electric vehicles there is a distinction between "day" time or "night" time charging.

Figure 149. Grid violation

² Penetration degrees are defined as follows :

- A PV profile is appended on top of the consumption profile. These PV profiles are produced for each consumer individually, based on a reference profile in per unit. Each consumer has a profile allocated in which the annual yield corresponds to his annual consumption (ratio 1:1). Consequently, a penetration rate of 50% implies that the annual production amounts half the annual consumption.
- For the EVs: a reference EV charging profile is appended to the consumption profile.

As it can be derived from the figure, the amount of violations is given for the studied scenario, i.e. forecasted case including the PV and EVs, as well as for an optimization. The latter is an objective function that aims at reducing the amount of violations within the distribution network, through the application of suggestive phase swaps. A figure demonstrates the reduction of violations for the different consumer IDs.

- g. Another tab within the '**Congestion Forecasting**', is the '**Voltage Profiles**' tab. Here you can analyse the deviations in terms of voltage for a given connection, caused for the selected scenario (see previous tab). Results are given for the case pre- and post integration of the stochastic disturbances (i.e. PV and EVs).

Figure 150. Voltage profiles

- h. Finally, for a defined scenario – all results and figures can be downloaded in the '**Results**' tab.

Figure 151. Results

JSI approach: PQ-related disturbances

- 1) Go to the Marketplace main page and go to the search bar and look for the service “Grid disturbance simulations: PQ-related disturbances”.
- 2) Select the desired service.
- 3) Contract the service, following the default and/or required contract parameters. Upload the data as needed.
- 4) Execution of the service through the Marketplace or by login to the Marketplace and running <http://s31jsi.bd4opem.eu/>
- 5) Usability Testing: After executing the service, follow the indicated steps to test various aspects.
 - a) Initial screen shows the available contracts for this service. You can select the appropriate one.

S3.1 - Grid Disturbance Simulations

Contract Results KPI

Contracts:

	contractID	version	status	data_parameters	business_parameters.acc
0	18fd[REDACTED]	1	Complete	[object Object]	71[REDACTED]
1	c6b3[REDACTED]	1	Active	[object Object]	71[REDACTED]

Select contract:

18fd[REDACTED]

	0
contractID	18fd[REDACTED]
version	1
status	Complete
data_parameters	[[{"contractID": ""}]]
business_parameters.accountID	71[REDACTED]

Figure 152. Available contracts for Service S3.1 (JSI)

- b) Go to the Results tab where you will see the topology of the grid that was simulated. On the left sidebar, you can select the nodes in which you are interested. After choosing the nodes of interest, the graphs will be shown below the topology figure with initial and optimal values for selected nodes. Due to transparency, only 5 nodes can be chosen; otherwise, the graphs are overcrowded.

Figure 153. Grid topology

- c) Move to the KPI tab to see each node’s KPI. $KPI < 1$ means there was some improvement obtained with the measures taken. Since these are manual simulations, all possible measures are defined before simulation and only the optimal is shown.

Figure 154. KPI for Service S3.1 (JSI)

- d) On the left side, you have two buttons to download all the numerical data of the initial state of the grid and for optimal value in CSV format.
- 6) Fill out the questionnaire following the results and experience perceived after the previous steps.

7.6 S4.1 – Inconsistencies in energy balance and power voltage

Contract service

1. Go to the Marketplace main page and go to the search bar and look the service “*Inconsistencies in energy balance and power-voltage*”.
2. Select the service desired
3. Contract the service, following the default and/or required contract parameters. Upload the data as required.
4. Execution of the service

Usability testing

5. After executing the service, follow the indicated steps to test several aspects.
 - a. Go to <https://app.staging.bd4opem.odit-e.com/> and try to login.

Figure 155. Odit-e app

- b. If login succeed, you should see a map with all your secondary substations.

Figure 156. Map with all secondary substations

- c. Click on a substation. A panel should open and display all smart meters linked to the substation. If GPS coordinates are given, smart meters should also appear on the map.

Figure 157. Display of the all smart meters linked to the substation

- d. On the top right corner there is a “PTN” tab allowing you to access to the “*Inconsistencies in energy balance and power-voltage*” service
- Colored substations are the one for which the calculation could be performed. Click on a given substation to access to the analysis.
 - For a selected substation, see different information:

1. Table of the smart meters with **probability of bypassing** and **missing power probability** in the neighborhood of the meters

Smart meters list				
Sensor id	GPS	Bypass probability	Missing power probability	
filter data...				
27E54B2A1E54E7C69D520B16FCC491CDB04AEA0E	✓	0		43
77B262D2774D36976ACC1C066803A25B180A9DFE	✓	0		0
77C2AF2ADF9B6395C3332CD9AAB81F452293A4A	✓	0		10
D66C524871AA11C5F5C0F5075D46B51EA79FC13F	✓	0		0

Figure 158. Table of the smart meters with probability of bypassing and missing power probability in the neighborhood of the meters

The drop down menu allow to color the meter considering the level of these indicators

Figure 159. The drop down menu for coloring the meter considering the level of indicators

2. Load curve and boxplot of the power balance to identify the frequency and volume of non-measured energy in the secondary substation.
6. Fill the questionnaire provide following the results and experience perceived after following the previous steps.

7.7 S4.2 – Fraud patterns detection

UPC approach: Fraud patterns detection

1. Go to the Marketplace main page and go to the search bar and look the service “*Fraud Pattern Detection*”.
2. Select the service.

3. Contract the service, following the default and/or required contract parameters. Contract the required data.
4. Execution of the service through the Marketplace or by login to the Marketplace and running <https://s42upc.bd4opem.eu/> .

Usability Testing:

- 1) After executing the service, follow the indicated steps to test several aspects
 - a) Go to *Dashboard* tab to check the contract parameters. The *About* button provides a short and long description of the service. There’s also a *Contact us* button.

Figure 160. Contracts parameters for Servis S4.2 (UPC)

- b) Go to *Visualization* tab and check the *Recent Results*. You can sort them by *Probability [%]*, *Magnitude [kW]* or any other column. Select the *View Graph* button of one of the frauds to see the NTL daily curve. Change the number of entries (rows) by selecting it at the upper left part of the screen. Go to the *Filter* button to filter the table by type of fraud, magnitude or other variables. A fraud should be verified or denied after undergoing a field inspection to calculate the accuracy and improve the algorithm. The *Historical* tab registers all the detected frauds and not only the most recent ones. By denying a fraud, this should be deleted from the *Historical* tab the next time the service is executed. To download the visible results, select the button *Download XLSX* or *Download CSV*.

Figure 161. Visualization tab

SM ID *	Trafo ID **	Probability (%)	Type	Magnitude [kW]	Duration [Days]	Graph	Verify
	CIR4621546083	-	Other	217.8	30+	View Graph	<input type="button" value="Yes"/> <input type="button" value="No"/>
	ORM1149910124	61	Squatting	94.623	30+	View Graph	<input type="button" value="Yes"/> <input type="button" value="No"/>
SM: ZIV0040336439 - 73.05 %	ORM4991063500	52	Squatting	4.323	29	View Graph	<input type="button" value="Yes"/> <input type="button" value="No"/>
	CIR0308247054	52	Mining	55.272	22	View Graph	<input type="button" value="Yes"/> <input type="button" value="No"/>

Figure 162. Magnitude

Figure 163. Filter

- c) Go to *KPIs* tab to appreciate the total number of detected frauds, the power recovered by disconnecting the fraudulent consumer, the accuracy of the service and the distribution of *Types of fraud* of the contract. Select the *Save results* button to obtain the report in excel form.

Figure 164. KPI tab

- 2) Fill the questionnaire provided following the results and experience perceived after following the previous steps.

JSI approach: Fraud patterns detection

The Non-technical losses service developed by JSI is intended to support an investigator of the non-technical loss in his/her research. The tool requires bubble data for its processing. The bubble data is the data of all the smart meters and related transformer station in a given timeframe. The tool should be able to compute the loss as a difference between the substation meter consumption and the sum of all consumption of related smart meters. Besides, the data should cover a substantial period before the loss and the period till after the discovery of source of the losses. Of course, the tool can provide the results before discovery of the loss source.

In the sections below the Marketplace user interface will be used to acquire the data contract, service contract and to run the service with specific service technical parameters. The storyline will reveal how to access the service report. On the end some brief explanation will be given about the service results.

Data contract

- 1) First, we need a data contract for the service. On the "Search" page of the Marketplace, we search for "fraud pattern detection" data. The one shown in the below screenshot is the correct option.

Figure 165. "Data contract" tab

- 2) Click on "See more", then "Contract data" at the very bottom. Give the contract whichever name, for example "S4.2 data". For the data period, select today's date as "From", and whichever date in the future as "To". Finally, press "Submit".

Business parameters

Contract name

NB. This field does not accept special characters

Payment type

Contracted data period* ⓘ

Historical Real time

In case of historical data, the only payment type permitted is "One time"

From

To

NB. The contract dates 'From'/'To' need to correspond to the availability periods (or part of them) indicated in the data's 'Data set information' page

Offering type

Figure 166. Business parameters

- 3) Service Provisioning receives the data contract right after the "Submit" button is pressed. You should be able to see your data contract request in the "My Data" page, with the role "Data User". The contract status should be COMPLETE.

My contracted data and data requests Filter by status ▾

NB. Data contracts can be edited if the contract is in the status "Rejected". To see contracts in status rejected, use the "Filter by status" filter. Contracts may be edited, subject to approval from the DP. A DU who would like to edit a contract, may contact the DP using the action "Send email to DP", asking the DP to reject the contract

Show entries Search:

Contract ID	Contract date	Organisation	Data start date	Data end date	Contract Name	Status	Actions
99938ea0-7099-4ec1-a688-8ad480da012b	24/10/2023 13:17	JSI - E6	24/10/2023	31/12/2023	S4.2 data	COMPLETE	👁 ✎ ✉

Figure 167. Display of contracted data and data requests

- 4) However, to be able to use the data contract, it needs to be approved and activated by the Data Provider (in this case, JSI). Approving and activating the data contract will advance the contract status from COMPLETE to APPROVED, and then to ACTIVE. Once contract status is ACTIVE, it can be selected when contracting a service, as we will see shortly.

Service contract

- 1) Contracting a service follows similar steps as contracting data. Service S4.2 can be found on the Marketplace under the name "Fraud pattern detection". Under "Advanced search", we can also select "JSI - E6" organization to filter the results.

The screenshot shows a service card for 'Fraud pattern detection'. On the left is the logo of Institut 'Jozef Stefan' Ljubljana, Slovenia. The main title is 'Fraud pattern detection' with a subtitle 'A tool for fraud investigation and provisioning of fraud supporting evidence'. A blue 'See more' button is below the subtitle. To the right, it says 'No feedback for this service' and 'Involved partners: This service has no involved partners'. At the bottom, it lists the 'Service Provider' as 'JSI - E6' and the 'Last updated on' date as '18/10/2023'.

Figure 168. Contracting a service

- 2) Click on "See more", and then "Request new service" at the top of the page. We first fill in the business parameters, same as for the data contract. Contract name can be whatever, for example "S4.2 test contract [today's date] - ELCE". Leave "Payment type" as is, and select the contract period.

The screenshot shows the 'Business parameters' form. It has a title 'Business parameters' at the top. Below it are three main sections:

- Contract name ***: A text input field containing 'S4.2 test contract 24.10. - ELCE'. To its right is a 'Contract ID' field with a 'Contract ID' button. A note below says 'NB. This field does not accept special characters'.
- Payment type ***: A dropdown menu currently showing 'One time'.
- Contract period ***: Two date input fields labeled 'From' and 'To'. The 'From' field contains '10/24/2023' and the 'To' field contains '11/11/2023'. Both fields have calendar icons to their right.

Figure 169. Business parameters for Servis S4.2 (JSI)

- 3) Next, we select the technical parameters. Select one value for each technical parameter. A description of each parameter can be seen in the image. Since we selected the Slovenian pilot, we choose the "case" parameter accordingly.

pilot
The pilot to use

Type
Application

Values *

slovenian
eypesa

case
Based on pilot choice, choose the corresponding 'case' - on which data to run the service. Two additional parameters (loss_start and loss_end) are determined based on pilot and case choice. Cases bd4opem_elce_ntl_case_1 or _2 are applicable to Slovenian pilot, while the rest are applicable to EyPESA pilot.

Type
Application

Values *

bd4opem_elce_ntl_case_1

bd4opem_elce_ntl_case_2

balenya

canovelles

case115

case705

eulalia

Figure 170. Technical parameters for Servis S4.2 (JSI)

- 4) We then select the corresponding data contract. Find the “S4.2 data” (or whatever name you put) data contract, check it, and click “Confirm”. The data contract will not be present unless it was activated by the Data Provider. Be sure to also select “Yes” for “Enable immediate execution”, otherwise the service will not actually be run in the ASM module.

Contracted data

NB. Make sure that you have the data available for the service contract period.

- Flexibility forecast input data- own use
- Fraud pattern detection (NTL) input data- own use
- Fraud pattern detection (NTL) input data
- Flexibility forecast input data
- S5.3 data
- S4.2 data

Confirm

Edit

Check all

Uncheck all

Requested composition

This service has no compositions

Execution parameters

Enable immediate execution *

Yes

No

Figure 171. Contracted data for Servis S4.2 (JSI)

- Finally, click on the "Request service" button at the bottom. Similarly as for the data contract, Service Provisioning receives the contract right after the button is pressed. You should be able to see your service contract request in the "Service requests" table, found on the "My Services" page, with the role set to "Service User". The contract, provisioning and execution status should be as in the below image.

Service requests ⓘ

Filter by Contract status ▾ Filter by Provisioning status ▾ Filter by Execution status ▾

NB. Service contracts can be edited if the contract is in the status "Rejected". To see contracts in status rejected, use the "Contract status" filter. Contracts for which provisioning is not concluded yet, i.e., status "Ongoing", may be edited, subject to approval from the SP. A SU who would like to edit a contract, under the above-specified conditions, may contact the SP using the action "Send email to SP", asking the SP to reject the contract

Show 5 entries Search:

Service name	Organisation	Contract date	Contract name	Contract status	Provisioning status	Execution status	Actions
Fraud pattern detection	JSI - E6	24/10/2023 13:24	S4.2 test contract 24.10. - ELCE	COMPLETE	NOT IN PROVISIONING	NOT IN EXECUTION	

Figure 172. Service requests

Running the service

Similarly, to be able to use the service contract, it needs to be approved and activated by the Service Provider (in this case, JSI). Immediately after the contract is activated, an instance of the S4.2 service will be started in the ASM module. This will happen because the service is set to be auto instantiated *if* immediate execution was set to "Yes".

As soon as the contract is activated, i.e. the service starts executing in ASM, the Marketplace will provide us with a link to our front-end, where we can see the logs and results of the service. This link is accessible via the "Go to service" button, present in the corresponding entry in the "Service requests" table.

Service requests ⓘ

Filter by Contract status ▾ Filter by Provisioning status ▾ Filter by Execution status ▾

NB. Service contracts can be edited if the contract is in the status "Rejected". To see contracts in status rejected, use the "Contract status" filter. Contracts for which provisioning is not concluded yet, i.e., status "Ongoing", may be edited, subject to approval from the SP. A SU who would like to edit a contract, under the above-specified conditions, may contact the SP using the action "Send email to SP", asking the SP to reject the contract

Show 5 entries Search:

Service name	Organisation	Contract date	Contract name	Contract status	Provisioning status	Execution status	Actions
Fraud pattern detection	JSI - E6	24/10/2023 13:24	S4.2 test contract 24.10. - ELCE	ACTIVE	PROVIDED	NOT IN EXECUTION	Go to service

Figure 173. "Service requests" table

Clicking on the "Go to service" button takes us to our front-end.

Figure 174. Details page

If the service is still executing, it should be present in the "Running" tab. Clicking on the ID in the "Running" tab will take you to the "Details" page and stream any logs of the service.

If the service has finished, we should be able to find it in the tab "History". You can click on the refresh button to see whether it has. By clicking on the service ID in the "History" tab, the report i.e result of the service will be fetched and you will be automatically moved to the "Report" tab.

Figure 175. "Report" tab

Additionally, by clicking on the tab “Details”, you will be able to see the technical parameter values you selected, as well as any stdout and stderr logs of the service.

7.8 S5.1 – Flexibility Forecast

UPC approach: Flexibility forecast

1. Go to the Marketplace main page and go to the search bar and look for the service “Flexibility Forecast”.
2. Select the service desired.
3. Contract the service, following the default and/or required contract parameters. Upload the data as required.
4. Execution of the service. On the initial menu: create new execution.
 - a. Click on “Add Forecast Model”.

Figure 176. Flexibility models

- b. Fill the following information to initiate the forecast.

ADD FORECAST MODEL

Model Name:

Service Contract:

Data Contract:

Pilot:

Assets:

Training Dates: Start Date End Date

Execution Type:

Target Period:

Hour Range:

Granularity:

Figure 177. Adding forecast model

ADD FORECAST MODEL

Model Name:

Service Contract:

Data Contract:

Pilot:

Assets:

Training Dates: Start Date End Date

Execution Type:

Target Period:

Hour Range:

Granularity:

Save Model

Figure 178. Added forecasting mode

5. Save it and the model appear in your forecast models.

MY FLEXIBILITY MODELS

+ Add Forecast Model

MODEL NAME	STATUS	DATA CONTRACT	TRAINING DATES	ACTIONS
Testing	SUCCESS	388227b8-9d3d-425d-93a0-6532e024caed	2019-06-20 - 2019-12-29	Model Info Forecasts
Test EyPESA	SUCCESS	388227b8-9d3d-425d-93a0-6532e024caed	2019-06-20 - 2019-12-24	Model Info Forecasts
Test StoryLine	-	388227b8-9d3d-425d-93a0-6532e024caed	2019-06-20 - 2019-12-29	Model Info Forecasts

Figure 179. Forecast models

To make it run, click on the right arrow button.
 Changing its status to "pending":

Figure 180. Model info and forecasts pending image

and then to success, enabling the tabs "model info" and "forecasts" :

Figure 181. Flexibility Model info and forecasts

6. Usability Testing: On the initial menu: check previous executions.
 - a. Click on the "Model Info" tab, scroll down to discover the following:

Figure 182. "Model Info" tab

It will deliver the information on the selection and the training results (real flexibility estimated and the forecasted) with the corresponding KPIs.

- b. Select the forecast tab

FORECAST

Assets:

ESS, EV

Execution Type:

Once-off

Granularity:

60 minutes

Training Dataset Dates:

2019-06-20 : 2019-12-29

Horizon:

day ahead

METRICS

Mean Flexibility:

50 kWh

Total Flexibility:

150 kWh
[Download Data](#)

Figure 183. "Forecast" tab

It will deliver the information on a graph with the results of the forecast for the next day. Also, the metrics of flexibility are presented: total and mean flexibility values.

Click on "Download Data" to be able to export a CSV file with the forecasting results and on to download the chart.

JSI approach: Flexibility forecast

Being able to predict a customer's reaction to a price change is useful in a real-time power pricing setting where consumers are sensitive to changing rates. This study suggests estimation of aggregated load flexibility based on the historical price-response dynamics of consumers and demonstrates how one-way price signals can be utilized to control the aggregated electricity consumption.

The proposed approach requires aggregated historical consumption data along with the historical and current weather information to estimate "price-based" demand-side flexibility.

In the next sections the steps needed to contract the service and request execution are presented. On the end the service results obtainable through the report are briefly presented. Before dwelling into the service contracting, provisioning and execution a brief introduction to the flexibility model is given in the next section.

About the flexibility model

The model has been prepared during BD4OPEM project in cooperation with UiW (Use it Wisely) national project, led by Elektro Celje and supported by JSI. The UiW project has been supported by the Agency for Energy of Slovenia which enabled positive and negative critical peak network tariffs in a region of Elektro Celje network. During peak hours the network fee was 10 times higher as at ordinary hours. The Agency decree enabled 100 hours of positive critical peak tariff per year. Based on this the projects have organized 41 2 hours flexibility events in 2021.

The model has been built on a dataset containing the 15 minute-resolution electricity consumption dataset from 791 households in Elektro Celje region. The dataset time span was from September 1, 2019 to December 31, 2021. The dataset was trimmed by removing the customers with missing load and finally 462 customers were used for the analysis. The dataset contains 41 events of 2 hour duration scheduled on different times and days in the year 2021. We have also used the weather data such as temperature, precipitation and radiation of the same region as users to increase the accuracy of our forecast model.

Data contract

First, we need a data contract for the service. On the “Search” page of the Marketplace, we search for “flexibility forecast” data. There will be a few results, but we select “Flexibility forecast input data”.

The screenshot shows the search interface of the BD4OPEM marketplace. At the top, there is a search bar with the text "flexibility forecast" and an "Advanced search" button. Below the search bar, there are filters for "JSI - E6" and "Data Type". The search results section displays a data contract for "Flexibility forecast input data" from the "Institut 'Jozef Stefan' Ljubljana, Slovenija". The contract details include the data provider "JSI - E6" and the last updated date "09/10/2023". A "See more" button is visible next to the contract title.

Figure 184. Data contracting

To make a data contract, click on “See more”, then “Contract data” at the very bottom. Give the contract whichever name, for example “S5.1 input data” For the data period, select today’s date as “From”, and whichever date in the future as “To”. Finally, press “Submit”.

Business parameters

Contract name

NB. This field does not accept special characters

Payment type

Contracted data period* ?

Historical Real time

In case of historical data, the only payment type permitted is "One time"

From

To

NB. The contract dates 'From'/'To' need to correspond to the availability periods (or part of them) indicated in the data's 'Data set information' page

Offering type

Figure 185. Business parameters

Service Provisioning receives the data contract right after the "Submit" button is pressed. You should be able to see your data contract request in the "My Data" page, with the role "Data User". The contract status should be COMPLETE.

My contracted data and data requests Filter by status ▾

NB. Data contracts can be edited if the contract is in the status "Rejected". To see contracts in status rejected, use the "Filter by status" filter. Contracts may be edited, subject to approval from the DP. A DU who would like to edit a contract, may contact the DP using the action "Send email to DP", asking the DP to reject the contract

Show entries Search:

Contract ID	Contract date	Organisation	Data start date	Data end date	Contract Name	Status	Actions
2649f9e4-3e1c-442c-82d3-16b827ded603	11/10/2023 16:00	JSI - E6	11/10/2023	27/10/2023	S5.1 input data	COMPLETE	

Figure 186. Contracted data and data requests

However, to be able to use the data contract, it needs to be approved and activated by the Data Provider (in this case, JSI). Approving and activating the data contract will advance the contract status from COMPLETE to APPROVED, and then to ACTIVE. Once contract status is ACTIVE, it can be selected when contracting a service, as we will see shortly.

Service contract

Contracting a service follows similar steps as contracting data. Service S5.1 can be found on the Marketplace under the name "Flexibility forecast based on price signals". Under "Advanced search", we can also select "JSI - E6" organization to filter the results.

Figure 187. Servis contracting

Click on “See more”, and then “Request new service” at the top of the page. We first fill in the business parameters, same as for the data contract. Contract name can be whatever, for example “S5.1 test contract [today’s date]”. Leave “Payment type” as is, and select the contract period.

Figure 188. Filling business parameters

Next, we select the technical parameters. Select one value for each technical parameter. A description of each parameter can be seen in the image. The most important one to select is the pilot - this essentially determines whose data will be

used during execution. The parameter “pilot_strength” should be the approximate number of smart meters in the planned event.

Technical parameters *

NB. To add technical parameters to the contract, click on the “Values” (multi selection is permitted)

<p>pilot The pilot to use</p> <p>Type Application</p> <p>Values *</p> <p>slovenian eypesa oedas</p>	<p>pilot_strength Strength for the selected pilot</p> <p>Type Application</p> <p>Values *</p> <p>462</p>	<p>event_day Planned event start, given as ISO 8601 time</p> <p>Type Application</p> <p>Values *</p> <p>2021-11-18</p>
<p>event_duration Planned event duration, given in minutes</p> <p>Type Application</p> <p>Values *</p> <p>120 60</p>	<p>price_scale Price change, given as ratio between the price during the event and regular price during the event</p> <p>Type Application</p> <p>Values *</p> <p>20</p>	<p>population The population participating in the event, given in percent of all population</p> <p>Type Application</p> <p>Values *</p> <p>3500</p>

Figure 189. Technical parameters of the Service S5.1

We then select the data contract. Find the “S5.1 input data” (or whatever name you put) data contract, check it, and click “Confirm”. The data contract will not be present unless it was activated by the Data Provider. Be sure to also select “Yes” for “Enable immediate execution”, otherwise the service will not actually be run in the ASM module.

Contracted data

NB. Make sure that you have the data available for the service contract period.

- S5.3 input
- S5.1 weather data
- S5.1 metering data
- S4.2 input case 1
- Flexibility forecast input data- own use
- S5.1 input data

Confirm Edit Check all Uncheck all

Requested composition

This service has no compositions

Execution parameters

Enable immediate execution *

Yes
 No

Figure 190. Contracted data for the Service S5.1

Finally, click on the “Request service” button at the bottom. Similarly as for the data contract, Service Provisioning receives the contract right after the button is pressed. You should be able to see your service contract request in the “Service requests” table, found on the “My Services” page, with the role set to “Service User”. The contract, provisioning and execution status should be as in the below image.

Service requests ⓘ

[Filter by Contract status](#) |
 [Filter by Provisioning status](#) |
 [Filter by Execution status](#)

NB. Service contracts can be edited if the contract is in the status “Rejected”. To see contracts in status rejected, use the “Contract status” filter. Contracts for which provisioning is not concluded yet, i.e., status “Ongoing”, may be edited, subject to approval from the SP. A SU who would like to edit a contract, under the above-specified conditions, may contact the SP using the action “Send email to SP”, asking the SP to reject the contract

Show entries Search:

Service name	Organisation	Contract date	Contract name	Contract status	Provisioning status	Execution status	Actions
Flexibility forecast based on price signals	JSI - E6	11/10/2023 16:11	S5.1 test contract 11.10.	COMPLETE	NOT IN PROVISIONING	NOT IN EXECUTION	👁️ 📄 ✉️

Figure 191. Service requests

Running the service

Similarly, to be able to use the service contract, it needs to be approved and activated by the Service Provider (in this case, JSI). Immediately after the contract is activated, an instance of the S5.3 service will be started in the ASM module. This will happen because the service is set to be auto instantiated *if* immediate execution was set to “Yes”.

As soon as the contract is activated, i.e. the service starts executing in ASM, the Marketplace will provide us with a link to our front-end, where we can see the logs and results of the service. This link is accessible via the “Go to service” button, present in the corresponding entry in the “Service requests” table.

Service requests ⓘ

[Filter by Contract status](#) |
 [Filter by Provisioning status](#) |
 [Filter by Execution status](#)

NB. Service contracts can be edited if the contract is in the status “Rejected”. To see contracts in status rejected, use the “Contract status” filter. Contracts for which provisioning is not concluded yet, i.e., status “Ongoing”, may be edited, subject to approval from the SP. A SU who would like to edit a contract, under the above-specified conditions, may contact the SP using the action “Send email to SP”, asking the SP to reject the contract

Show entries Search:

Service name	Organisation	Contract date	Contract name	Contract status	Provisioning status	Execution status	Actions
Flexibility forecast based on price signals	JSI - E6	11/10/2023 16:11	S5.1 test contract 11.10.	ACTIVE	PROVIDED	NOT IN EXECUTION	Go to service 👁️ 📄 ✉️

Figure 192. “Service requests” table

Clicking on the “Go to service” button takes us to our front-end.

Figure 193. Details page

If the service is still executing, it should be present in the “Running” tab. Clicking on the ID in the “Running” tab will take you to the “Details” page and stream any logs of the service.

If the service has finished, we should be able to find it in the tab “History”. You can click on the refresh button to see whether it has. By clicking on the service ID in the “History” tab, the report i.e result of the service will be fetched and you will be automatically moved to the “Report” tab.

Figure 194. “Report” tab

Additionally, by clicking on the tab “Details”, you will be able to see the technical parameter values you selected, as well as any stdout and stderr logs of the service.

7.9 S5.2 – Flexibility aggregated services for BRPs

1. Go to the Marketplace main page and go to the search bar and look for the service “Flexibility Services for BRPs”.
2. Select the service desired.
3. Contract the service, following the default and/or required contract parameters. Upload the data as required.
4. Execution of the service
5. Usability Testing: After executing the service, check the following steps to explore and verify the different features
 - a. Check the first sub-service: “Day-ahead optimization” and explore the two tabs: “Forecast” and “Optimization”
 - b. In the “Forecast” tab, using the “Start Date”, “End Date” and “Frequency” it is possible to select the date range for the plot of the historical values. Using the “Select what to display” button it is possible to choose the forecasted variable to be displayed, between “Day-ahead marginal price”, “BRP demand” or “Total costs”. The first displays day-ahead forecasts of the chosen variable, whereas the second one allows to evaluate the performance of the model, comparing past predictions against real data. In the last section of the tab, KPIs of the historical performance are presented, according to the chosen error metric “MAPE (Mean Absolute Percentage Error)” or “R2(r square)”.

- c. In the “Optimization” tab, the results displayed in the “Forecast” tab are used to evaluate the day-ahead balancing optimization of the BRP. Insert the “Max cost” and “Flexibility price” inputs and verify that the

outputs change accordingly. The KPIs below summarize the results of this sub-service.

- d. Navigate to the "Self-balancing" page, where the results of the self-balancing optimization are displayed. The plots show respectively the predicted deviations against the system for the day-ahead, and the relative periods to activate flexibility. Summarizing the results, a KPI showing a percentage of the imbalances against the system is shown.

- 6. Fill the questionnaire provided following the results and experience perceived after following the previous steps.

7.10S5.3 – Flexibility aggregated services for DSOs

UPC approach: Flexibility-based AC OPF

1. Contract the service with the demanded parameters.
2. Select the pilot/grid.

Figure 195. "Pilot selection" tab

3. Upload the *daily forecast*. The daily forecast file corresponds to the excel file with the forecast for all loads for the next day. Select the date accordingly to such forecast. Then select *Submit*.

The forecast files are the following with their forecasted date:

- EyPESA: *Estabanell_forecast-1.xlsx (21-07-2023)*
- CELJE: *ELCE_forecast-1.xlsx (07-07-2023)*
- NUVVE: *NUVVE2_b_forecast-1.xlsx*
- OEDAS: *OEDAS_forecast-1.xlsx (13-07-2023)*

Figure 196. Selecting of forecasting data

4. The service will start the execution for that specific day. Wait until the service is completed, hence, *Successful*.

Figure 197. Daily forecast

5. Technical Testing: After executing the service, explore the performance factors of the period selected.
 - a. Select period. If you only have given data for one day, just select that day. (Like the example in this StoryLine)

- b. Evaluate the results provided in this tab by verifying the summary values of Requested Flexibility and Congested Lines.
- c. Scroll down and check the flexibility source ID dropdown list. Explore sources ID1 y ID2 and check their values.

Figure 198. Control screen

- d. Repeat the previous two steps for different available dates.
6. Click on the date on the calendar to get the visualizations of the results of that day.

Figure 199. Summary

- a. Change different times of the day. The figures depict the grid before and after the execution of the service. This corresponds to the use of the service to calculate the appropriate amount of flexibility to overcome the forecasted congestions in the grid.

Figure 200. Visualization

- b. Download figures for the most congested time of the day.
 - c. Following up the last step, make sure you can observe the image correctly after downloaded locally or in any other form.
7. Scroll down once again and position yourself in the preview of data.
- a. In this section you are you going to select different buses IDs and explore their behavior
 - b. Download the data in excel form.
 - c. Open data downloaded file and explore further results to make sure everything works.

Figure 201. Preview of DATA

JSI approach: Flexibility services for DSOs based on neural networks

Flexibility services for DSOs provide necessary services for the DSOs to schedule flexibility events in a region of their network. The services provide a prediction of consumption in the target region and propose an event schedule at the time of the peak.

The service requires historic data of the region's consumption and weather forecast for the region. The service has been used with the following weather parameters: temperature, radiation and precipitation. At least temperature should be available.

The prediction of the consumption depends on the available weather forecast. More days of the forecast are available, longer can be the consumption prediction. For example, in Elektro Celje Case, if there are seven days of weather prediction data available the consumption can be predicted for a week in advance. Since the consumption is based on smart-metering and the metering is considered to be D-1, the effective prediction is less than a week long. The number of days is further reduced since the D-1 data is usually not good enough for prediction. Large portions of the network data is available as D-2 data. In summary, an effective prediction is only 5 days long.

The predictions in this story line are shown on historic data so the service can be more easily evaluated. Working on the edge and predicting into the future requires a flowing stream of data.

In the next sections the steps needed to contract the service and request execution are presented. On the end the service results obtainable through the report are briefly presented.

Data contract

First, we need a data contract for the service. On the “Search” page of the Marketplace, we search for “flexibility services for dsos” data, as seen in the below screenshot.

Figure 202. Data contract

To contract this data, click on “See more”, then “Contract data” at the very bottom. Give the contract whichever name, for example “S5.3 input”. For the data period, select today’s date as “From”, and whichever date in the future as “To”. Finally, press “Submit”.

Business parameters

Contract name

NB. This field does not accept special characters

Payment type

Contracted data period* i

Historical Real time

In case of historical data, the only payment type permitted is "One time"

From

To

NB. The contract dates 'From'/'To' need to correspond to the availability periods (or part of them) indicated in the data's 'Data set information' page

Offering type

Figure 203. Business parameters

Service Provisioning receives the data contract right after the “Submit” button is pressed. The Service Provisioning details are shown in the text box below.

The following image shows the corresponding log entry in the SP module, indicating the data contract was received.

```

2023-09-25 10:27:57,953 - mongodb - INFO - Inserted to collection meta:
{
  "status": "DATA CONTRACT RECEIVED",
  "contractID": "d8f35293-229a-4a1a-9743-f3fe593963b2",
  "update_time": "2023-09-25 10:27:57.951766",
  "message": "Data contract received",
  "_id": {
    "$oid": "651160ad255bd467123eb04b"
  }
}
    
```

Figure 204. Data contract entry display

You should be able to see your data contract request in the “My Data” page, with the role “Data User”. The contract status should be COMPLETE.

My contracted data and data requests Filter by status ▾

NB. Data contracts can be edited if the contract is in the status "Rejected". To see contracts in status rejected, use the "Filter by status" filter. Contracts may be edited, subject to approval from the DP. A DU who would like to edit a contract, may contact the DP using the action "Send email to DP", asking the DP to reject the contract

Show 5 entries Search:

Contract ID	Contract date	Organisation	Data start date	Data end date	Contract Name	Status	Actions
d8f35293-229a-4a1a-9743-f3fe593963b2	25/09/2023 12:24	JSI - E6	25/09/2023	07/10/2023	S5.3 input	COMPLETE	👁️ ✎ ✉️

Figure 205. Contracted data and data requests

However, to be able to use the data contract, it needs to be approved and activated by the Data Provider (in this case, JSI). Approving and activating the data contract will advance the contract status from COMPLETE to APPROVED, and then to ACTIVE. Once contract status is ACTIVE, it can be selected when contracting a service, as we will see shortly.

Service contract

Contracting a service follows similar steps as contracting data. We first search for service S5.3, flexibility services for DSOs. Under “Advanced search”, we can also select “JSI - E6” organization to filter the results.

The screenshot shows the 'Start search for' interface with 'Data' and 'Service' tabs. The search query is 'flexibility services for dsos'. Filters include 'JSI - E6', 'Select a category', 'Select a sub category', and 'Select a partner'. A 'Search' button is visible. Below the search results, a service card is displayed for 'Flexibility services for DSOs based on neural networks' by 'Institut "Jozef Stefan" Ljubljana, Slovenija'. The card includes a 'See more' button, 'Service Provider' information (JSI - E6), and 'Last updated on' (13/09/2023). A note states 'No feedback for this service' and 'Involved partners: This service has no involved partners'.

Figure 206. Flexibility services for DSOs based on neural networks

Click on “See more”, and then “Request new service” at the top of the page. We first fill in the business parameters, same as for the data contract. Contract name can be whatever, for example “S5.3 test contract [today’s date]”. Leave “Payment type” as is, and select the contract period.

Business parameters

Contract name *

NB. This field does not accept special characters

Payment type *

One time
▼

Contract period *

From

09/25/2023
📅

To

10/07/2023
📅

Contract ID

Contract ID

Figure 207. Business parameters of the Service S5.3

Next, we select the technical parameters. Select one value for each technical parameter. A description of each parameter can be seen in the image. The most important one to select is the pilot - this essentially determines whose data will be used during execution.

pilot

The pilot to use

Type

Application

Values *

slovenian

eypesa

oedas

target

A list of variables in input data to be predicted. Only one variable is supported at the moment - "all"

Type

Application

Values *

[all]

weather_features

A list of features available in the weather data - ideally, "temperature", "radiation" and "precipitation". For EyPESA pilot, "radiation" is unavailable.

Type

Application

Values *

["temperature", "precipitation", "radiation"]

samples_per_day

Number of measurements per day - 96 for 15 minute intervals or 24 for one hour intervals. For Slovenian pilot, default is 96, for EyPESA and OEDAS pilots, default is 24.

Type

Application

Values *

96

24

predict_days

Number of days to predict

Type

Application

Values *

7

event_duration

The length of the event in minutes planned/considered, default is 120 minutes

Type

Application

Values *

120

60

full_hours

Schedule the event on full hours or not

Type

Application

Values *

true

false

Figure 208. Parameter selection

We then select the data contract. Find the "S5.3 input" (or whatever name you put) data contract, check it, and click "Confirm". The data contract will not be present unless it was activated by the Data Provider. Be sure to also select "Yes" for "Enable"

immediate execution”, otherwise the service will not actually be run in the ASM module.

Contracted data

NB. Make sure that you have the data available for the service contract period.

- Flexibility service for DSOs input data
- Fraud pattern detection (NTL) input data case 1 (test)- own use
- Fraud pattern detection (NTL) input data case 2 (test)- own use
- Fraud pattern detection (NTL) input data case 1
- Fraud pattern detection (NTL) input data case 2
- S5.3 input

Confirm

Check all

Edit

Uncheck all

Requested composition

This service has no compositions

Execution parameters

Enable immediate execution *

Yes

No

Figure 209. Stages

Finally, click on the “Request service” button at the bottom. Similarly as for the data contract, Service Provisioning receives the contract right after the button is pressed.

We can see the corresponding log entries in the SP module, indicating that the service contract was received, and in short, that everything is okay.

```

2023-09-25 10:32:14,442 - mongodb - INFO - Inserted to collection meta:
{
  "status": "SERVICE_CONTRACT_RECEIVED",
  "contractID": "ca85f245-f6da-45f7-8887-e0a8a40d853c",
  "update_time": "2023-09-25 10:32:14.440261",
  "message": "Service contract received",
  "_id": {
    "$oid": "651161ae255bd467123eb04d"
  }
}
2023-09-25 10:32:14,670 - mongodb - INFO - Inserted to collection meta:
{
  "status": "CONTRACT_AVAILABLE",
  "contractID": "ca85f245-f6da-45f7-8887-e0a8a40d853c",
  "update_time": "2023-09-25 10:32:14.668001",
  "message": "Service and data contracts available",
  "_id": {
    "$oid": "651161ae255bd467123eb04e"
  }
}
                
```

Figure 210. SP Module

You should be able to see your service contract request in the “Service requests” table, found on the “My Services” page, with the role set to “Service User”. The contract, provisioning and execution status should be as in the below image.

Figure 211. Service Requests

Running the service

Similarly, to be able to use the service contract, it needs to be approved and activated by the Service Provider (in this case, JSI). Immediately after the contract is activated, an instance of the S5.3 service will be started in the ASM module. This will happen because the service is set to be auto instantiated *if* immediate execution was set to “Yes”.

The following image shows a screenshot of running so-called pods (think of them as microservices) in the ASM module in our Kubernetes cluster. We can see that one of them is called “fs-dsos-<random strings>” - this pod is executing an instance of S5.3 i.e. flexibility forecast for DSOs service.

NAME↑	PF	READY	RESTARTS	STATUS
enqueue-64c8bb84fb-pl5hz	●	1/1	0	Running
fs-dsos-cdabd1a8f6-vj5dp	●	1/1	0	Running
job-launcher-9cbb8f5c8-2pd9r	●	1/1	0	Running
job-watcher-7986bfd5c-fxabc8	●	1/1	0	Running
rabbitmq-controller-f86r9	●	1/1	0	Running
scheduler-b6fc576d5-zft7l	●	1/1	0	Running
service-front-end-7646d746f6-74zks	●	1/1	0	Running
service-management-database-848495868c-8vnt8	●	1/1	0	Running
service-manager-59c78d78f7-czvvj	●	1/1	0	Running

Figure 212. Elasticity estimation screenshot for DSO's service

As soon as the contract is activated, i.e. the service starts executing in ASM, the Marketplace will provide us with a link to our front-end, where we can see the logs and results of the service. This link is accessible via the “Go to service” button, present in the corresponding entry in the “Service requests” table.

Service requests ⓘ

Filter by Contract status ▾ Filter by Provisioning status ▾ Filter by Execution status ▾

NB. Service contracts can be edited if the contract is in the status "Rejected". To see contracts in status rejected, use the "Contract status" filter. Contracts for which provisioning is not concluded yet, i.e., status "Ongoing", may be edited, subject to approval from the SP. A SU who would like to edit a contract, under the above-specified conditions, may contact the SP using the action "Send email to SP", asking the SP to reject the contract

Show 5 entries Search:

Service name	Organisation	Contract date	Contract name	Contract status	Provisioning status	Execution status	Actions
Flexibility services for DSOs based on neural networks	JSI - E6	25/09/2023 12:28	S5.3 test contract 25.09.	ACTIVE	PROVIDED	NOT IN EXECUTION	Go to service

Figure 213. Service requests status screen

Clicking on the "Go to service" button takes us to our front-end.

S5.3 Flexibility services for DSOs

Services Run service Cancel service Report Details

Running Scheduled History

Service name	Service provider	Type	Service ID	Status	Start of execution
fs_dsos	JSI	Immediate	fs-dsos-cdabd1a8f6	Running	Mon, 25 Sep 2023 10:51:19 GMT

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 872525

Powered by:

Figure 214. Details page

If the service is still executing, it should be present in the "Running" tab. Clicking on the ID in the "Running" tab will take you to the "Details" page and stream any logs of the service.

If the service has finished, we should be able to find it in the tab "History". You can click on the refresh button to see whether it has. By clicking on the service ID in the "History" tab, the report i.e result of the service will be fetched and you will be automatically moved to the "Report" tab.

Figure 215. "Report" tab

Additionally, by clicking on the tab "Details", you will be able to see the technical parameter values you selected, as well as any stdout and stderr logs of the service.

7.11S6.1 and S6.2 – Energy management at household or at community level and forecasting services

1. Go to the BD4OPEM Marketplace <https://marketplace.bd4opem.eu/> main page and go to the search bar and look for the service "**MESI: Energy Management System & Simulator and Forecasting**".

2. Select the service.
3. Contract the service, following the default and/or required contracted parameters and data contracts associated.
4. Execution of the service through the Marketplace or by login to the Marketplace and running <https://mesi.aks-marketplace.bd4opem.eu/>

Usability Testing

After contracting and executing the service, follow the indicated steps to test several aspects

1. In the initial application front-end, select "**Add New Project**"

MESI [My Projects](#)

MY PROJECTS

+ Add New Project

NAME	DATE CREATED	BUILDING INFO	TARIFF INFO	ASSETS INFO	EXECUTED	ACTIONS
------	--------------	---------------	-------------	-------------	----------	---------

2. In order to **create a new project**, provide the input required data to run the service regarding the project, buildings, tariff, asset information.

CREATE NEW PROJECT

1 **Project's info** 2 Building info 3 Tariff info 4 Asset info 5 Project was created!

PROJECT'S INFO

Name:

Project's Description:

Next Step >

3. After providing the data, project is created. Press "Finish"

4. Inside a project, create a **new scenario**.

5. Execute the optimization:
 - a. Details of the Scenario optimization

SCENARIO PARAMETERS DETAILS

SC-1

Scenario Description
Description

Select Building:

Type of Tariff: **3TD kW** Maximum Export Power: **70 kW** Maximum Capacity: **1000 kW**

Max Contracted Power for period 1: **70 kW** Max Contracted Power for period 2: **70 kW** Max Contracted Power for period 3: **70 kW**

Max Contracted Power for period 4: **70 kW** Max Contracted Power for period 5: **70 kW** Max Contracted Power for period 6: **70 kW**

Local Taxes: **0.015** Commercial Margin for retail company: **0.005 €/kWh** VAT: **0.21**

Select Asset:

Max Charging Power: **90 kW** Max Discharging Power: **90 kW** Max State of Charge of Battery (SOC): **189.9 kWh**

Min State of Charge of the Battery (SOC): **31.65 kWh** SOC Initial: **150 kWh** SOC Final: **150 kWh**

b. Run the optimization

MY SCENARIOS

Project's Description Description

NAME	DATE CREATED	STATUS	ACTIONS
SC-1	13/09/2023	Pending	<input type="button" value="⚙️"/> <input type="button" value="🔍 Details"/> <input type="button" value="▶ Run Simulation"/> <input type="button" value="🗑 Delete"/>

c. Check the results

←

MY SCENARIOS

Project's Description Description

+ Add New Scenarios

NAME	DATE CREATED	STATUS	ACTIONS
SC-1	13/09/2023	Success	Delete

Assets Diagram

NAV

d. Forecasting results

e. Electricity price for buying and selling

f. Total amount of electricity bought and sold

These are the optimized electricity consumption associated to each building after the optimization.

g. Battery optimization

These are the optimal control signals for the centralized battery in order to minimize the overall energy consumption.

h. KPIs

The Kpis are shown below. Also, the results can be downloaded into an Excel file.

7.12S7.1 – P2P trading

Contracting Service:

1. Go to the Marketplace main page and go to the search bar and look for the services provided by "ATOS".
2. Select P2P Trading.

3. Contract the smart meter data required by the service, and then contract the service, following the default and/or required contract parameters.

Usability Testing:

1. Login to P2P Trading <https://p2p.atos.bd4opem.eu/> from the service link (automatically re-directing to the marketplace to do the login) and then redirect back to the service, to view the Service User contracts for your organization.

2. Select the contract of interest and initialize it for the cooperative trading algorithm.

Contract management

CEC Service User Contract: 200cbd6b-318a-4a2a-9650-29ef9e2b5792 [View Contract](#)

Algorithm: Cooperative

Status: [Initialise](#)

Smart meter ID	Retailer	Sell Discount %	Buy Discount %
5147220	Retailer X	-	-
21008253	Retailer X	-	-
78287400	Retailer X	-	-

3. Wait at least 24 hours to select the Trading results tab to download the csv.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
1	smartmeterId	day	Cons.1	Cons.2	Cons.3	Cons.4	Cons.5	Cons.6	Cons.7	Cons.8	Cons.9	Cons.10
2	ES0113500000001180SE	13	10.163	12.979	10.084	11.48	12.784	14.823	14.892	14.798	17.835	15.973
3	ES0113500000001180SE	14	0.071	0.072	0.072	0.072	0.072	0.072	0.072	0.073	0.077	C
4	ES0113500000001180SE	15	8.094	8.073	7.973	7.887	9.605	9.742	7.799	12.29	11.494	14.395
5	ES0113500000001611BQ	13	0.072	0.072	0.072	0.073	0.072	0.074	0.072	0.073	0.072	C
6	ES0113500000001611BQ	14	5.171	5.112	8.364	10.738	11.563	9.397	10.729	13.806	13.544	15.865
7	ES0113500000001611BQ	15	0.069	0.072	0.072	0.071	0.072	0.072	0.072	0.077	0.087	0.001
8	ES0113000053634017CS	13	16.112	10.902	13.488	14.865	9.927	16.67	11.29	11.94	19.435	14.678
9	ES0113000053634017CS	14	8.12	7.985	7.979	8.645	11.149	7.788	7.801	9.32	16.026	18.147
10	ES0113000053634017CS	15	5.255	5.293	5.082	5.117	9.679	11.26	10.634	10.142	12.846	10.467

4. Check the trading cooperative trading algorithm has performed equal sharing of production and consumption figures, over one of the 24hour periods.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N
1	smartmeterId	day	Cons.1	Cons.2	Cons.3	Cons.4	Cons.5	Cons.6	Cons.7	Cons.8	Cons.9	Cons.10	Cons.11	Cons.12
2	ES011350000001180SE	13	10.163	12.979	10.084	11.48	12.784	14.823	14.892	14.798	17.835	15.973	19.356	21.523
3	ES011350000001611BQ	13	0.072	0.072	0.072	0.073	0.072	0.074	0.072	0.073	0.072	0	0	0
4	ES0113000053634017CS	13	16.112	10.902	13.488	14.865	9.927	16.67	11.29	11.94	19.435	14.678	11.375	10.947
5														
6			Prod.1	Prod.2	Prod.3	Prod.4	Prod.5	Prod.6	Prod.7	Prod.8	Prod.9	Prod.10	Prod.11	Prod.12
7	ES011350000001180SE	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	ES011350000001611BQ	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.009	1.345	4.79	10.363
9	ES0113000053634017CS	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10														
11			Trade.1	Trade.2	Trade.3	Trade.4	Trade.5	Trade.6	Trade.7	Trade.8	Trade.9	Trade.10	Trade.11	Trade.12
12	ES011350000001180SE	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-0.6725	-2.395	-5.1815
13	ES011350000001611BQ	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.345	4.79	10.363
14	ES0113000053634017CS	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-0.6725	-2.395	-5.1815

7.13S8.1 – Asset and investment planning

Contracting Service:

1. Go to the Marketplace main page and go to the search bar and look the service “Investment Planning”.
2. Select the service.
3. Contract the service, following the default and/or required contract parameters. Contract the required data.
4. Execution of the service through the marketplace or by login to the marketplace and running <https://s81upc.bd4opem.eu/>

Business parameters

Contract name UPC	Payment type One time
Contract period From 09/02/2023	To 09/02/2024

Technical parameters

Size of the grid
Number of busses/loads in the given grid

Type
Implementation

Values

Less than 50 loads Between 50 and 200 loads

More than 200 loads

Number of grids
The DSO may be interested in inspecting some networks.

Type
Implementation

Values

1 grid 2 or 3 grids Unlimited

Type of analysis
Type of power flow

Type
Application

Values

Single Date-Time Power Flow

Multiple Date-Time Power Flows

Usability Testing:

1. Go to Dashboard tab to check the contract parameters. The About button provides a short and long description of the service. There’s also a Contact us button.

Asset and investment planning

Antonio_Service_Test_1

UPC CITCEA (UPC)

About Contact us

Get in touch with the Service provider: We Plus

You have contracted the service with the following characteristics

Username UPC CITCEA (UPC)

Contract duration From 21/07/2023 to 21/07/2024

Execution parameters

On demand False

Technical parameters

Number of grids 1 grid

Size of the grid More than 200 loads

2. Go to the Stress Test TAB to start creating an expansion scenario.

Asset and investment planning

Antonio_Service_Test_1

UPC CITCEA (UPC)

Asset to stress Transformers

Asset name Choose...

Load increase Choose...

Reset Add

Display Actions

Asset to stress	Asset name	Load increase [%]

Type of powerflow Single Date Time Date Time Range

Select Date 05/03/2019 - 01:00

NB. When selecting the dates above, make sure that these dates are compliant with the actual availabilities of the data used.

Transformers Lines Bus voltage Run Power Flow

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 872525

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3. Stress the distribution Network by incrementing the loading % of the selected transformers. In this example case follow the configuration showed in the Display Planning Acting box of Fig.4.

4. Select the Power Flow analysis Type "Date Time Range"

5. Select date-time range for example. When selecting the dates, make sure that these dates are compliant with the actual availabilities of the data used.

6. Click on the “Run Power Flow” push button

The screenshot shows the 'Asset to stress' configuration page. The 'Asset name' is 'SS03' and 'Load increase' is '300%'. The 'Date Range' is set from '05/02/2019 - 00:00' to '08/02/2019 - 00:00'. The 'Run Power Flow' button is highlighted. Below the configuration, a table displays the results for various assets:

Asset ID	Transformer Name	Type	HV Bus	LV Bus	HV Deviation [pu] *	LV Deviation [pu] *	Loading [%]
3	SS03	0.4 MVA 20.5/0.4 kV	29	46	0.746	0.976	126.4237
8	SS08	0.25 MVA 20.5/0.4 kV	37	51	0.999	0.994	35.0478
15	SS15	0.4 MVA 20.5/0.4 kV	1	38	1.000	0.996	28.1206
11	SS11	0.4 MVA 20.5/0.4 kV	35	49	0.999	0.995	26.802
6	SS06	0.4 MVA 20.5/0.4 kV	56	57	0.999	0.996	20.0711

7. Go to the “Planning Actions” Tab, by clicking in the left side bar.

8. A new table of results with 3 different subtabs should be displayed, as showed in Fig.5. Verify also that the table results correspond with the GIS maps results displayed on the right side.

The screenshot shows the 'Asset List Results' page. The 'Planning Actions' tab is selected. A table displays the results for various planning actions:

Planning Actions	Asset Type	Name	CAPEX	OPEX
Parallel Line	NA2KSZY 1x185 RM/25 12/20 kV	L0	€7,656	€79
Parallel Line	NA2KSZY 1x185 RM/25 12/20 kV	L1	€1,104	€11
Parallel Line	NA2KSZY 1x185 RM/25 12/20 kV	L2	€5,775	€60
Parallel Line	NA2KSZY 1x185 RM/25 12/20 kV	L3	€5,303	€55
Parallel Line	NA2KSZY 1x185 RM/25 12/20 kV	L4	€11,974	€124

Below this table, another table displays the results for various assets, including a 'New Loading [%]' column:

Asset ID	Name	Type	HV Bus	LV Bus	HV Deviation [pu] *	LV Deviation [pu] *	New Loading [%]
17	SS03	0.4 MVA 20.5/0.4 kV	29	46	1.000	0.996	61.03025010171974
3	SS03	0.4 MVA 20.5/0.4 kV	29	46	1.000	0.995	63.63025091071474
8	SS08	0.25 MVA 20.5/0.4 kV	37	51	1.000	0.997	35.034632889461
15	SS15	0.4 MVA 20.5/0.4 kV	1	38	1.000	0.999	28.11416319752428

9. Finally click the KPIs TAB located on the left side bar. You can download the KPIs in a .xlsx format by clicking in the buttons below.

10. Click on the total cost (\$) TAB to see the following:

7.14S8.2 – Asset estimation optimization for microgrids

1. Go to the Marketplace main page (<https://marketplace.bd4opem.eu/>) and using the search bar, look for the service "Asset estimation optimization for microgrids".

The marketplace listing for 'Asset estimation optimization for microgrids' includes the following details:

- Service Provider:** Vrije Universiteit Brussel
- Creation Date:** 18/10/2022
- Involvement:** Vrije Universiteit Brussel (Role: Algorithm developer), We Plus S.p.A. (Role: Service provider)
- Feedback:** No feedback for this service
- Buttons:** 'See more' button

2. Select the desired service ('See more') and follow the instructions.
- NOTE: the contract period is the period during which the service will be accessible.
3. Contract the service, following the default and/or required contract parameters. Select the data as needed by checking the box of the data:

Contracted data

NB. Make sure that you have the data available for the service contract period.

vub_s31_internal_test_week

Once the service has been approved by the 'Service Provider' on the Marketplace you can proceed to the next steps:

4. Execution of the service through the Marketplace, make sure you are logged in as 'Service User', see top right corner. Click on '🔗' to access the service:

Or after being logged in on the Marketplace, you can directly run the service by navigating to: <https://s82vub.bd4opem.eu/>.

5. Usability Testing: After executing the service, follow the indicated steps to test various aspects.
 - a. Initial screen displays the 'Dashboard' including information such as the contract duration and latest update.

NOTE: your contract ID appears at the top.

- b. Go to the 'Asset Overview' tab where all your assets will be listed. On the left side, you can select the asset in which you are interested.

After choosing the asset of interest (e.g. 'TEST_BATT_SHOW_FUNCTIONALITY'), access the "View Detail" button. As user, you will be redirected to the 'Data Analysis' tab.

By selecting an asset, the tab in the left pane will also be accessible to navigate to directly. Here results are shown for the selected asset (in this example a battery energy storage system):

The provided information is restricted to an analysis of the provided data. In order to inspect the results from the optimization algorithm, go to the 'SOH Analysis'.

- c. Within the 'SOH Analysis' tab, a detailed overview of the (i) current battery capacity degradation, (ii) the expected lifetime that is reached and (iii) the expected remaining useful lifetime (RUL) by pursuing a similar operation, are displayed. Additionally, a graph displays the battery degradation over time:

d. Following tab, 'Degradation prognosis', gives an interactive graphical representation of the battery capacity degradation over time.

This for multiple operation regimes, i.e.:

i. Number of cycles/year:

ii. Change in average dept-of-discharge (DoD):

iii. Average (dis)charging current:

An option to download the graphs is available.

- e. To finalize, 'Degradation costs' tab let you interpret the costs of typical daily profiles on your battery degradation. In a first instance, four pre-defined typical profiles are displayed for a given Battery CAPEX unit cost in [€/kWh].

Service user have also the possibility to create their own daily profile for another Battery CAPEX unit cost. Therefore, use the slides on the "Create test daily profile [24h]" and change the value of the cost. To run the simulation, click on the green icon:

8 Annex B. Service testing & Service KPIs

8.1 S1.1 – Topology

Service	Service1.1 Topology
Algorithm provider	ODT
Solution provider	ODT
	Good performance ●
	Non-critical error ●
	Error detected ●

Release date 13/02/2023

Service testing summary

Marketplace testing

Table 52. Service1.1_ODT_Marketplace testing.

Functional Test ID	Functional Test	Test responsible	Check	Comments
Service1.1_ODT_MK.1	Service contracts management	ODT	●	The complete contractual workflow is working as expected
		EyPESA	●	

Functional and KPIs testing

Table 53. Service1.1_ODT_Testing Summary Table.

Pilot	Functional Test ID	Functional Test	Test responsible	Check	Comments
SLOVENIA	Service1.1_ODT_FT.1	Active service contracts collection	ODT	●	
	Service1.1_ODT_FT.2	Data collection	ODT	●	
	Service1.1_ODT_FT.3	LV networks topologies evaluation	ODT	●	
	Service1.1_ODT_FT.4	Results export	ODT	●	
	Service1.1_ODT_FT.5	Client's access	EyPESA	●	
	Service1.1_ODT_KPI	KPIs validation	ODT	●	

Usability testing

Table 54. Service1.1_ODT_Usability testing.

UI Critical errors
UI Non-critical errors
UI Recommendations

Marketplace testing

Table 55. Service1.1_ODT_MK.1 Service contracts management.

Marketplace Test Description	Test Actions	Test responsible	Check
1. Contract service	Find service in marketplace by searching it with one of the following keywords: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Topology, AI, digital twin, smart meters, correction GIS, rebalancing phase 	ODT	●
	Select service to see details about it	ODT	●
		EyPESA	●
	Contract the service	ODT	●
		EyPESA	●
	Validate contract (data validation)	ODT	●
EyPESA		●	

Service Functional and KPIs Testing Actions

Table 56. Service1.1_ODT_FT.1 Active service contracts collection.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Test responsible	Pilot	Check
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2. Active service contracts collection through the UnifiedAPI	List all the active and approved contracts	ODT	Spain	●
	Get the data tokens linked to the contracts	ODT	Spain	●

Table 57. Service1.1_ODT_FT.2 Data collection.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Test responsible	Pilot	Check
3. Data collection through the UnifiedAPI	Get contract data from the data lake	ODT	Spain	●
	Pre-process data in Odit-e format	ODT	Spain	●

Table 58. Service1.1_ODT_FT.3 LV networks topologies evaluation.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Test responsible	Pilot	Check
4. Low voltage networks topologies evaluation	Found a topology for each low voltage network	ODT	Spain	●
	Perform the network analysis of each low voltage network (data computation for each network analysis widget)	ODT	Spain	●

Table 59. Service1.1_ODT_FT.4 Results export.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Test responsible	Pilot	Check
5. Results export in Odit-e database and visualization	Save algorithms results in database	ODT	Spain	●
	Results are visible on the webapp	ODT	Spain	●
	Webapp credentials sent to the customer	ODT	Spain	●

Table 60. Service1.1_ODT_FT.5 Client's access.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Test responsible	Pilot	Check
6. Customer access to the results	The customer successfully connects to the webapp	ELCE	Spain	●
	The customer sees the results on the webapp	ELCE	Spain	●

Table 61. Service1.1_ODT_KPI KPIs validation.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Test responsible	Pilot	Check
7. KPIs (see table hereafter)	All KPI (excepted #5) are computed	ODT	Spain	●
	Validate KPI #1	ODT	Spain	●
	Validate KPI #4	ODT	Spain	●

Table 62. Service1.1_ODT_List of service KPIs.

#	KPI	Description	Calculation	Expected value
1	Computation time	The time between the start of execution of the service and the provision of the results, for one substation (~100 smart meters)	$t_{results} - t_{start}$	Should be under 5 minutes for 3 months of data
2	Number of meters analysed	Total number of meters analysed by the service through the platform	$\sum n_{meters}$	
3	GIS correction rate	Feeder and secondary substation prediction mismatch ratio	Total number of meters with a predicted feeder or secondary substation different than the GIS, relative to the total number of meters	Depends on GIS quality
4	Confidence index	A float between 0 and 1 output by the topology algorithm, assessing Odit-e's confidence in its prediction.	Average prediction confidence, output by the algorithm	Should be over 0,8
5	[Require field validation] GIS correction validation	Feeder and secondary substation correction validation rate	Number of validated correction propositions / Number of correction propositions	To be performed afterwards, and should be over 80%

Usability testing

UI Critical errors

Errors that affect the tangible/numeric results: graphs display, login error, etc.

Table 63. Service1.1_ODT_UI critical errors.

Critical errors	Screen shots and description	Reporter
Type of error (login....)		

UI Non-critical errors

Errors that do not affect the tangible/numeric results: font sizes, colors of graphs, limits of the axis, etc.

Table 64. Service1.1_ODT_UI non-critical errors.

Non-critical errors	Screen shots	Reporter
Type of error (font size....)		

UI Recommendations

Provide recommendations for improving the front-end UI

Table 65. Service1.1_ODT_UI recommendations.

Recommendations	Screen shots	Reporter
Recommendation 1		

8.2 S1.2 – Observability

Service	S1.2 Observability
Algorithm provider	ODT
Solution provider	ODT
	Good performance ●
	Non-critical error ●
	Error detected ●

Release date 13/02/2023

Service testing summary

Marketplace testing

Table 66. Service1.2_ODT_Marketplace testing.

Functional Test ID	Functional Test	Test responsible	Check	Comments
1.2_ODT_MK.1	Service contracts management	ODT	●	The complete contractual workflow is working as expected
		EYPESA	●	

Functional and KPIs testing

Table 67. Service1.2_ODT_Testing Summary Table.

Pilot	Functional Test ID	Functional Test	Test responsible	Check	Comments
SPAIN	1.2_ODT_FT.1	Active service contracts collection	ODT	●	Access to contract database has been successfully tested
	1.2_ODT_FT.2	Data collection	ODT	●	Data access through data lake has been successfully tested, the online analysis has been performed on manually ingested data
	1.2_ODT_FT.3	LV networks state estimation	ODT	●	Validated in expert testing session for UI, in D7.2 for results on EyPESA data, feeder's estimation not computed
	1.2_ODT_FT.4	Results export	ODT	●	Validated in expert testing session
	1.2_ODT_FT.5	User access	EYPESA	●	Validated in expert testing session
	1.2_ODT_KPI	KPIs validation	ODT	●	KPIs were computed offline on EyPESA data

Usability testing

Table 68. Service1.2_ODT_Usability testing.

UI Critical errors
NA
UI Non-critical errors
Number of significant figures
UI Recommendations
NA

Marketplace testing

Table 69. Service1.2_ODT_MK.1 Service contracts management.

Marketplace Test Description	Test Actions	Test responsible	Check
8. Contract service	Found service in marketplace by searching it with one of the following keywords: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Observability, machine learning, state estimation, voltage plan, real time, AI 	ODT	●
	Select service to see details about it	ODT	●
	Contract the service	EYPESA	●
	Validate contract (data validation)	ODT	●

Service Functional and KPIs Testing Actions

Table 70. Service1.2_ODT_FT.1 Active service contracts collection.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Test responsible	Pilot	Check
9. Active service contracts collection through the UnifiedAPI	List all the active and approved contracts	ODT	SPAIN	●
	Get the data tokens linked to the contracts	ODT	SPAIN	●

Table 71. Service1.2_ODT_FT.2 Data collection.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Test responsible	Pilot	Check
10. Data collection through the UnifiedAPI	Get contract data from the data lake for training the model	ODT	SPAIN	●
	Collect data regularly, before each state estimation	ODT	SPAIN	●
	Pre-process data in Odit-e format	ODT	SPAIN	●

Table 72. Service1.2_ODT_FT.3 LV networks state estimation.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Test responsible	Pilot	Check
11. Low voltage networks state estimation	Observability model qualified	ODT	SPAIN	●
	Voltage level estimation for each meter	ODT	SPAIN	●
	Estimation of the power flowing through the substations per feeder/phase	ODT	SPAIN	●

Table 73. Service1.2_ODT_FT.4 Results export.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Test responsible	Pilot	Check
12. Results export in Odit-e database and visualization	Save algorithms results in database	ODT	SPAIN	●
	Webapp credentials sent to the customer	ODT	SPAIN	●

Table 74. Service1.2_ODT_FT.5 User access.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Test responsible	Pilot	Check
13. Customer access to the results	The customer successfully connects to the webapp	EYPESA	SPAIN	●
	The customer sees the results on the webapp	EYPESA	SPAIN	●

Table 75. Service1.2_ODT_KPI KPIs validation.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Test responsible	Pilot	Check
14. KPIs (see table hereafter)	All KPI are computed each week	ODT	SPAIN	●
	All KPI are validated	ODT	SPAIN	●

Table 76. Service1.2_ODT_KPI table.

#	KPI	Description	Calculation	Expected value	Offline calculation
1	Observability rate of the smart meters voltage	Number of observed grid state values (voltages), with respect to all observable values in %.	Nb of observed value/Nb of observable value	>98%	>99% considering the threshold of 5% to be considered observed
2	Observability rate of the LV feeders currents	Number of observed grid state values (currents), with respect to all observable values in %	Nb of observed value/Nb of observable value	>98%	Feeder load estimation were not computed
3	Observability rate of the MV/LV substation apparent powers	Number of observed grid state values (apparent powers), with respect to all observable values in %.	Nb of observed value/Nb of observable value	>98%	39% considering the threshold of 15% to be considered observed
4	Accuracy of the load estimation at substation level	Comparison between estimated load at substation level and measured one with respect to nominal power	Mean absolute percentage error	<15%	21.7%
5	Accuracy of the load current estimation at low voltage feeder level	Comparison between estimated current load at feeder level and measured one with respect to feeder nominal current	Mean absolute percentage error	<20%	Feeder load estimation were not computed
6	Voltage estimation accuracy at meters level	Comparison between estimated voltage at feeder level and measured one	Mean absolute error	<3V	<1.2

Usability testing

UI Critical errors

Errors that affect the tangible/numeric results: graphs display, login error, etc.

Table 77. Service1.2_ODT_UI critical errors.

Critical errors	Screen shots and description	Reporter
NA		

UI Non-critical errors

Errors that do not affect the tangible/numeric results: font sizes, colors of graphs, limits of the axis, etc.

Table 78. Service1.2_ODT_UI non-critical errors.

Non-critical errors	Screen shots	Reporter
The number of significant figures should not be that high considering the precision of the state estimation		ODT

UI Recommendations

Provide recommendations for improving the front-end UI

Table 79. Service1.2_ODT_UI recommendations.

Recommendations	Screen shots	Reporter
The ability to see the profile of voltages between two points in the grid (also to graph the lines in the map).	NA	EyPESA
To be able to compare different Smart Meters in the same graph.	NA	EyPESA
Be able to include other parameters apart from voltage.	NA	EyPESA

8.3 S1.3 – Predictive maintenance

Not tested in EyPESA pilot.

8.4 S2.1 – Detection of Measurement Errors

Service	S2.1 Detection of Measurement Errors
Algorithm provider	UPC – Sara Barja Martínez
Solution provider	ICOM
	Good performance ●
	Non-critical error ●
	Error detected ●
Release date	31/07/2023

Service testing summary

Functional and KPIs testing

Table 80. Service2.1_UPC_Testing Summary Table.

Service	Functional ID	Test	Functional Test	Check	Comments
-	S21_UPC_FT.1	Create a project		●	Suggestion: is it possible to have more than one data contract per project?
	S21_UPC_FT.2	Check buttons: Open/ Edit/ Delete a project		●	
	S21_UPC_FT.3	Create scenario under a project		●	
	S21_UPC_FT.4	Create and run Scenario A		●	Suggestions: Add upper limit to missing/outliers thresholds. Change KPIs colors
	S21_UPC_FT.5	Create and run Scenario B		●	
	S21_UPC_FT.6	Create and run Scenario C		●	
	S21_UPC_FT.7	Create and run Scenario D		●	
	S21_UPC_FT.8	Create and run Scenario E		●	
	S21_UPC_EXEC.1	Execution time		●	

Usability testing

Table 81.Service2.1_UPC_Usability testing.

UI Critical errors
0 Critical errors
UI Non-critical errors
1 non-critical errors

UI Recommendations

1 UI recommendations/suggestions

Service Functional and KPIs Testing Actions

Table 82. Service2.1_UPC_FT.1 Functional Test Task 1.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
15. Create a project	Log-in to UI	●
	Press "Add new project" button	●
	All data contracts appear in the data contracts tab.	●
	The project is created sucesfully	●

Table 83. Service2.1_UPC_FT.2 Functional Test Task 2.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
16. Check buttons: Open/Edit/Delete a project	Check the open project buttom action works	●
	Check the update project buttom action works	●
	Check the delete project buttom action works	●

Table 84. Service2.1_UPC_FT.3 Functional Test Task 3.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
17. Create scenario under a project	Click the Open buttom.	●
	Click Add new scenario	●

Table 85. Service2.1_UPC_FT.4 Functional Test Task 4.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
18. Create and run Scenario A	Click the Open buttom.	●

	<p>Click Add new scenario. Name 1-anomalydetection. Below, the Scenario parameters.</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Update Scenario</p> <p>Name* test-3107-v1</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anomaly detection <input type="checkbox"/> Anomaly deletion <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Missing detection <input type="checkbox"/> Train data</p> <hr/> <p>Anomalies Parameters</p> <p>Anomalies Method Simple</p> <p>IQR Coefficient: 3 Simple Coefficient: 10</p> <p>Outliers threshold: 0.1</p> <hr/> <p>Missing data Parameters</p> <p>Missing method: Zero Missing threshold: 0.1</p> <hr/> <p>Results folder name* r1</p> </div> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outliers threshold and missing threshold. Limit these values between [0-1]. • Add the units. "Missing threshold [pu]" 	●
	<p>Run the scenario and get the results. Works.</p>	●
	<p>KPIs testing. For this scenario, the output of the UI is the same than the algorithm running locally.</p>	●
	<p>The results are correct. Missing values are imputed to Zero. Outliers are detected but not deleted, as stated in the test.</p> <div style="display: flex; flex-direction: column; align-items: center;"> </div>	●

Table 86. Service2.1_UPC_FT.5 Functional Test Task 5.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
19. Create and run Scenario B	Click Add new scenario. Name ScenarioB-anomalyDetectionDeletion Below, the Scenario parameters.	●

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 10px;"> <p>Name* v2</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anomaly detection <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anomaly deletion <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Missing detection <input type="checkbox"/> Train data</p> <hr/> <p>Anomalies Parameters</p> <p>Anomalies Method Simple</p> <p>IQR Coefficient: 3 Simple Coefficient: 10</p> <p>Outliers threshold: 0.1</p> <hr/> <p>Missing data Parameters</p> <p>Missing method: Zero Missing threshold: 0.1</p> <hr/> <p>Results folder name* r2</p> </div>	
	<p>Run the scenario and get the results. Works.</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 10px;"> <p>Anomalies are detected and deleted. Missing method = Zero is used in order to impute values to missing data and outliers detection and deletion.</p> </div>	●
	<p>KPIs testing. For this scenario, the output of the UI is the same than the algorithm running locally.</p>	●

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check

Table 87. S21_UPC_FT.6 Functional Test Task 6.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
<p>20. Create and run Scenario C</p>	<p>Click Add new scenario. Name ScenarioC</p> <p>Below, the Scenario parameters.</p>	<p>●</p>
	<p>Run the scenario and get the results. Works.</p>	<p>●</p>

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
	<p>KPIs testing. For this scenario, the output of the UI is the same than the algorithm running locally.</p>	

Table 88. S21_UPC_FT.7 Functional Test Task 7.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
<p>21. Create and run Scenario D</p>	<p>Click Add new scenario. Name ScenarioD</p> <p>Below, the Scenario parameters.</p>	

	<p>Run the scenario and get the results. Works.</p>	●
	<p>Repeat the test for missing method = 'mean'. Works.</p>	●
	<p>Repeat the test for missing method = 'median'. Works.</p>	●
	<p>Repeat the test for missing method = 'most frequent value'. Works.</p>	●
	<p>Repeat the test for missing method = 'random forest'. Works.</p>	●
	<p>Repeat the test for missing method = 'KNN'. Works.</p>	●
	<p>Repeat the test for missing method = 'Linear'. Works.</p>	●
	<p>Repeat the test for missing method = 'Quadratic'. Works. Repeat the test for missing method = 'Cubic'. Works. Repeat the test for missing method = 'Quintic'. Works.</p>	●
	<p>Repeat the test for missing method = 'Multivariate'. Works.</p>	●
	<p>KPIs testing. For these scenarios, the output of the UI is the same than the algorithm running locally.</p>	●

Table 89. Service2.1_UPC_FT,8 Functional Test Task 8.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
-----------------------------	--------------	-------

22. Create and run Scenario E	<p>Click Add new scenario. Name ScenarioE</p> <p>Below, the Scenario parameters.</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Name*</p> <input type="text" value="v5"/> </div> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; margin-top: 10px;"> <div style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/> Anomaly detection</div> <div style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/> Anomaly deletion</div> <div style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/> Missing detection</div> <div style="text-align: center;"><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Train data</div> </div> <hr/> <p style="text-align: center;">Anomalies Parameters</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Anomalies Method</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> <input type="text" value="..."/> </div> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; margin-top: 10px;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>IQR Coefficient</p> <input type="text" value="3"/> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Simple Coefficient</p> <input type="text" value="3"/> </div> </div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-top: 10px;"> <p>Outliers threshold</p> <input type="text" value="0,1"/> </div> <hr/> <p style="text-align: center;">Missing data Parameters</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Missing method</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> <input type="text" value="..."/> </div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-top: 10px;"> <p>Missing threshold</p> <input type="text"/> </div>	●
	<p>Run the scenario and get the results</p> <p>Now it works.</p>	●
	<p>KPIs testing. For this scenario, the output of the UI is the same than the algorithm running locally.</p>	●

Table 90. Service2.1_UPC_EXEC.1 Functional Test Task 9.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Execution time local/front-end	Check
23. Execution time	<p>Average executing algorithm for Use Cases.</p> <p>** In some scenarios, the execution time is less than 1 second for the UI.</p>	5 s/ 10 s **	●

Usability testing

UI Critical errors

Errors that affect the tangible/numeric results: graphs display, login error, etc.

Table 91. Service2.1_UPC_UI critical errors.

Critical errors	Screen shots and description	Reporter
Type of error (login...)		

UI Non-critical errors

Errors that do not affect the tangible/numeric results: font sizes, colors of graphs, limits of the axis, etc.

Table 92. Service2.1_UPC_UI non-critical errors.

Non-critical errors	Screen shots
I would not allow to write any negative value for the outliers and missing threshold → Done	
It would be nice that the end user could download these files. I could not find in the UI where to check the outliers and missing detection files. → Done	

UI Recommendations

Provide recommendations for improving the front-end UI

Table 93. Service2.1_UPC_UI recommendations.

Recommendations	Screen shots																								
<p>When creating an scenario, it would be nice that all the parameters for outliers, missing data have a brief description, like the information buttom in the Results-folder-name.</p> <p>Also, the missing threshold have a * but I don't know what this means (maybe a mandatory input?)</p> <p>These parameters description are in the deliverable D4.2. → not implemented yet</p>	<p>The screenshot shows two forms. The top form, 'Anomalies Parameters', has fields for 'Anomalies Method' (Simple), 'IQR Coefficient' (3), 'Simple Coefficient' (3), and 'Outliers threshold*' (0,1). The bottom form, 'Missing data Parameters', has fields for 'Missing method' (----) and 'Missing threshold*' (-6,9). Below these is a 'Results folder name*' field with '1-Scenario' and a 'Save' button.</p>																								
<p>Maybe delete ---- and set as a default None? → not need to implement this.</p>	<p>The screenshot shows the 'Missing data Parameters' form with the 'Missing method' dropdown set to '----'. A red error message is displayed below it: 'If train data is unchecked, a missing method must be selected.' The 'Missing threshold*' field is set to '0,1'.</p>																								
<p>It could be nice that for instance the clean data had a different line type (for instance ----- or -----) in order to see the raw data below the line (sometimes the two datasets are the same) → done</p>	<p>The screenshot shows a line chart titled 'DataSet' for 'Electricity (kWh)'. The y-axis ranges from 0 to 100,000. The x-axis shows dates from 2017-01-01 to 2017-01-07. Two data series are shown: 'Raw Data' (blue line with dots) and 'Clean Data' (green line with dots). The raw data shows several sharp peaks, while the clean data is a smooth line following the general trend.</p>																								
<p>In the scenarios view, it would be nice to clarify "missing imputation method". Also, We could add another column with the "outlier detection method" (simple vs iqr). → done</p>	<p>The screenshot shows a table titled 'Scenarios'. It has columns for '#', 'NAME', 'METHOD', 'STATUS', 'MISSING', and 'ACTIONS'. The 'METHOD' column is highlighted with a red box. The data rows are:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>#</th> <th>NAME</th> <th>METHOD</th> <th>STATUS</th> <th>MISSING</th> <th>ACTIONS</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>ScenarioA</td> <td>None</td> <td>SUCCESS</td> <td>3</td> <td>[Icons]</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>ScenarioB</td> <td>None</td> <td>SUCCESS</td> <td>3</td> <td>[Icons]</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>ScenarioC</td> <td>Zero</td> <td>SUCCESS</td> <td>3</td> <td>[Icons]</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	#	NAME	METHOD	STATUS	MISSING	ACTIONS	1	ScenarioA	None	SUCCESS	3	[Icons]	2	ScenarioB	None	SUCCESS	3	[Icons]	3	ScenarioC	Zero	SUCCESS	3	[Icons]
#	NAME	METHOD	STATUS	MISSING	ACTIONS																				
1	ScenarioA	None	SUCCESS	3	[Icons]																				
2	ScenarioB	None	SUCCESS	3	[Icons]																				
3	ScenarioC	Zero	SUCCESS	3	[Icons]																				

Recommendations Screen shots

The missing threshold parameter should also be desactivated. → **done**

The screenshot shows a configuration interface for 'ScenarioE'. At the top, there are checkboxes for 'Anomaly detection', 'Anomaly deletion', 'Missing detection', and 'Train data' (which is checked). Below this is the 'Anomalies Parameters' section, containing a dropdown for 'Anomalies Method', input fields for 'IQR Coefficient' (value 3), 'Simple Coefficient' (value 3), and 'Outliers threshold*' (value 0.1). The 'Missing data Parameters' section includes a dropdown for 'Missing method' and a 'Missing threshold*' input field (value 0.1), which is circled in red. At the bottom, there is a 'Results folder name' field with the value 'results-scenarioE'.

8.5 S3.1 – Grid disturbance simulations

UPC approach: Congestions forecast for day ahead

Service	S3.1 Grid Disturbance Simulation
Algorithm provider	UPC – Alejandro Hernandez
Solution provider	WEP
	Good performance ●
	Non-critical error ●
	Error detected ●
Release date	15/08/2023

Service testing summary

Functional and KPIs testing

Table 94. Service3.1_UPC_Testing Summary Table.

Pilot	Functional Test ID	Functional Test	Check	Test response	Comments
SPAIN	SPAIN_S3.1_UPC_FT.1	Data Ingestion	●		Brief description of the error detected

Pilot	Functional Test ID	Functional Test	Check	Test response	Comments
	SPAIN_S3.1_UPC_FT.2	Review forecasts Load	●		
	SPAIN_S3.1_UPC_FT.3	Evaluate behaviour Lines	●		
	SPAIN_S3.1_UPC_FT.4	Analyse Report Tab	●		
	SPAIN_S3.1_UPC_KPI.5	KPIs	●		
	PILOT_SP.3.1_UPC_EX.1	Execution times	●		

Usability testing

Table 95. Service3.1_UPC_Usability testing.

UI Non-critical errors
Font size
Limit axis
UI Recommendations
Provide recommendations for improving the front-end UI

Service Functional and KPIs Testing Actions

Table 96. Service3.1_UPC_FT.1 Functional Test Task 1.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
24. Data Ingestion	Make sure the data from the pilot is correctly ingested for the service.	●
	Verify there are no NaN values	●

Table 97. Service3.1_UPC_FT.2 Functional Test Task 2.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
25. Review Loads forecast	Check Aggregated Loads forecast plot	●
	Check dropdown list working Working	●

Functional Description	Test	Test Actions	Check
		<p>Comment: The caption should be "Choose a bus" or "Choose Load".</p>	
		Verify Load1 button from dropdown list to plot	●
		Verify Load2 button from dropdown list to plot	●
		Verify download file button	●

Table 98. Service3.1_UPC_FT.3 Functional Test Task 3.

Functional Description	Test	Test Actions	Check
26. Evaluate Lines behaviour		Check <i>Lines</i> tab button to be sent to new window	●
		Select <i>Line1</i> from dropdown	●
		Select <i>Line2</i> from dropdown	●
		Verify download file button	●

Table 99. Service3.1_UPC_FT.4 Functional Test Task 4.

Functional Description	Test	Test Actions	Check
27. Analyse Report Tab		Check <i>Report</i> tab button to be sent to new window	●
		Verify the results for all lines for all hours	●

	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;"> <p>Time period: 15/08/2023 - h24</p> <p>Choose a line: Line 15</p> <p>Show 5 entries</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 15%;">Hour</th> <th style="width: 15%;">Probability (%)</th> <th style="width: 15%;">Overload [kA]</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>0</td><td>0</td><td>0.01276375722826952</td></tr> <tr><td>1</td><td>0</td><td>0.01118695257600832</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>0</td><td>0.009875248962440275</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>0</td><td>0.009078616027253846</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>0</td><td>0.008296619363542215</td></tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Showing 1 to 5 of 24 entries</p> <p>Previous 1 2 3 4 5 Next</p> </div> <p>Comment: I think the table should show the 24 hrs for default, instead of needing to select the number of entries.</p> <p>Additionally, the hour column should be in hour format: e.g 00:00, 01:00, Also, the labels of the columns [Hour, Probability and Overload] should be centered.</p>	Hour	Probability (%)	Overload [kA]	0	0	0.01276375722826952	1	0	0.01118695257600832	2	0	0.009875248962440275	3	0	0.009078616027253846	4	0	0.008296619363542215	
Hour	Probability (%)	Overload [kA]																		
0	0	0.01276375722826952																		
1	0	0.01118695257600832																		
2	0	0.009875248962440275																		
3	0	0.009078616027253846																		
4	0	0.008296619363542215																		
	Download report in excel form	●																		

Table 100. Service3.1_UPC_KPI.5Functional Test Task 5.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
28. KPI	KPI benchmark/range comparison number of congestions found	●

Table 101. Service3.1_UPC_EX.1 Functional Test Task 6.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Execution time local/front-end	Check
29. Execution time	Executing algorithm for Use Case 1	10 s/ 60 s	●
	Training algorithm for algorithm	60 s/ 70s	●

Usability testing

UI Non-critical errors

Errors that do not affect the tangible/numeric results: font sizes, colours of graphs, limits of the axis, etc.

Table 102. Service3.1_UPC_UI non-critical errors.

Non-critical errors	Screen shots
Font size	Font sizes in the whole UI is good.

Limit axis	N/A
------------	-----

UI Recommendations

Provide recommendations for improving the front-end UI

Table 103. Service3.1_UPC_UI recommendations.

Recommendations	Screen shots
Recommendation 1	The recommendations have been made in section 1.

ANNEX

The results show no congestions, however, this is coherent with the input data used in this version of the testing.

VUB approach: Congestion control in distribution grids

Service	S3.1 Grid Disturbance Simulation
Algorithm provider	VUB – Rémy Cleenwerck
Solution provider	WEP
	Good performance ●
	Non-critical error ●
	Error detected ●

Release date 30/03/2023

Service testing summary

Functional and KPIs testing

Table 104. Service3.1_VUB_Testing Summary Table.

Pilot	Functional Test ID	Functional Test	Check	Test responsible	Comments
SPAIN	3.1_VUB_FT.1	Data ingestion	●	VUB	<i>Data manually uploaded + error with harmonized data (EyPESA data had only zero-values for the voltages. Not usable)</i>

3.1_VUB_FT.2	Review model training	●	VUB	
3.1_VUB_FT.3	Evaluate Data analysis	●	VUB	
3.1_VUB_FT.4	Analyse Congestion Forecasting	●	VUB	
3.1_VUB_KPI	KPIs	●	VUB	
3.1_VUB_EXEC	Execution time	●	VUB	

Comments:

Since the data for the Spanish pilot site (i.e., the harmonized data) had errors : only zero values for the voltages. The service could not be tested with their data. Therefore, to be able to test the service and get feedback, it was opted to use other data on the service in order to provide a demonstration of its capabilities.

Usability testing

Table 105. Service3.1_VUB_Usability testing.

UI Critical errors
Most errors solved in usability
One error persists : convergance of the simulation – error frond-end or back-end ? TBD
UI Non-critical errors
Samll details on the column names and data that is not present in the harmonized structure, and can thus be omitted.
UI Recommendations
Tornado diagram could provide more than 10 IDs.
Dropdown selection should only be the consumer ID, not including the `'_phase'`

Service Functional and KPIs Testing Actions

Table 106. Service3.1_VUB_FT.1 Data ingestion.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Pilot	Check
30. Data ingestion	Make sure the data from the pilot is correctly ingested for the service.	ELCE	●
		EYPESA	●
	Verify that during the 'project creation' : the selected grid data is appended to a project and the meta data (.json file) is correctly generated.	ELCE	●
		EYPESA	●
		ELCE	●

	Check if <i>'Grid Overview'</i> tab visualizes all the smart meter data (Consumer – No. Phases,..)	EYPESA	●
	Check if the visualization of the <i>'Voltage Profile'</i> for a selected smart meter ID (in a project) works.	ELCE	●
		EYPESA	●
	Check if the visualization of the <i>'Load Profile'</i> for a selected smart meter ID (in a project) works.	ELCE	●
		EYPESA	●

Table 107. Service3.1_VUB_FT.2 Review model training.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Pilot	Check
31. Review model training	Check if <i>'Run Simulation'</i> modifies the status of a selected grid, i.e. <i>'Trained'</i> : {YES / NO}.	ELCE	●
		EYPESA	●
	Check if <i>'scaler_x.pickle'</i> , <i>'scaler_y.pickle'</i> , <i>'trained_model.pickle'</i> are generated.	ELCE	●
		EYPESA	●

Table 108. Service3.1_VUB_FT.3 Evaluate Data analysis.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Pilot	Check
32. Evaluate Data analysis	Verify if plot is generated for a selected smart meter from dropdown menu <i>'Choose a connection'</i> in the <i>'Individual impact'</i> tab	ELCE	●
		EYPESA	●
	Verify if the cluster plot is shown when opening the <i>'Feeder impact'</i> tab	ELCE	●
		EYPESA	●
	Check if plots per group are shown when selecting the arrows next to the plot. [Only valid if multiple groups are listed.]	ELCE	●
		EYPESA	●
	Verify <i>'Export results'</i> function. [Downloads the meta data (.json file) and figures.]	ELCE	●
		EYPESA	●

Table 109. Service3.1_VUB_FT.4 Analyse Congestion Forecasting.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Pilot	Check
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33. Analyse Congestion Forecasting	Fill in other values for 'Degree of PV-penetration'.	ELCE	●
		EYPESA	●
	Fill in other values for 'Degree of EV-penetration'.	ELCE	●
		EYPESA	●
	Select another profile for 'Period of charging'.	ELCE	●
		EYPESA	●
	Inspect results after 'Run simulation' button is accessed (based on Degrees of PV/EV penetration and Period of charging). – ' <u>Voltage Profiles</u> ' tab	ELCE	●
		EYPESA	●
	Verify 'Export results' function. – ' <u>Voltage Profiles</u> ' tab [Returns .json file with info : no. of violations, suggested phase-swap and figure.]	ELCE	●
		EYPESA	●
Verify that a plot is generated based on the 'Select user id' button. – ' <u>Grid Violation</u> tab	ELCE	●	
	EYPESA	●	

Table 110. Service3.1_VUB_KPI KPIs.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Pilot	Check
34. KPIs	KPI benchmark/range comparison number of voltage violations forecasterd	ELCE	●
		EYPESA	●
	KPI benchmark/range comparison number of voltage violations reduced	ELCE	●
		EYPESA	●

Table 111. Service3.1_VUB_EXEC Execution time.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Execution time local/front-end	Check
35. Execution time	Executing algorithm for Use Case 1	XX s/ XX s	●
	Training algorithm for different models	3min / 15min	●

Usability testing

UI Critical errors

Errors that affect the tangible/numeric results: graphs display, login error, etc.

Table 112. Service3.1_VUB_Critical errors.

Critical errors	Screen shots and description	Reporter												
Accessibility tabs	- Service 'Dashboard' tab not accessible after scrolling to the others tabs, i.e. only when opening service ; error solved	Rémy Cleenwerck (VUB)												
Project creation	- 'Project overview' : project shows a value for the "no. grids" while after accessing the 'View details' it is empty. : error solved	Rémy Cleenwerck (VUB)												
Table generating wrong values after training the grid	<p>While training a grid inside a project, the service status changes to running and after to finished. However, the the 'Grid Overview' tab displays strange results, not the grids that were trained :</p> <p>I SOLVED : The problem the API that was populating the table and was not able to find the "project_meta.json" correctly. (Daniele Gastaldo – WEP)</p>	Rémy Cleenwerck (VUB)												
Error running simulation while the 'Analyse congestion' tab):	<p>Status changes in the marketplace :</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="486 1848 1225 1960"> <thead> <tr> <th>Title</th> <th>Message</th> <th>Notification date</th> <th>New</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Service execution - finished</td> <td>The service "Congestion control in distribution grids" with service code 151 finished its execution</td> <td>24/09/2023 08:59:03</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Service execution - running</td> <td>The service "Congestion control in distribution grids" with service code 151 is running as requested</td> <td>24/09/2023 08:58:33</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Title	Message	Notification date	New	Service execution - finished	The service "Congestion control in distribution grids" with service code 151 finished its execution	24/09/2023 08:59:03		Service execution - running	The service "Congestion control in distribution grids" with service code 151 is running as requested	24/09/2023 08:58:33		Rémy Cleenwerck (VUB)
Title	Message	Notification date	New											
Service execution - finished	The service "Congestion control in distribution grids" with service code 151 finished its execution	24/09/2023 08:59:03												
Service execution - running	The service "Congestion control in distribution grids" with service code 151 is running as requested	24/09/2023 08:58:33												

But simulation does not converge.

UI Non-critical errors

Errors that do not affect the tangible/numeric results: font sizes, colors of graphs, limits of the axis, etc.

Table 113. Service3.1_VUB_Non-critical errors.

Non-critical errors	Screen shots
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Type of consumer is not defined in harmonized data and could thus be hidden. 2. 'S_r' should be 'P' as it is active power and not apparent. 3. Type RES can not be found in the harmonized data and thus can be omitted. 4. 'S_r (RES)' also not in harmonized data so could as well be omitted. 	<p>Solution would be to change "Type (RES)" with "RES" and the column values could then be defined as True or False.</p>

UI Recommendations

Provide recommendations for improving the front-end UI

Table 114. Service3.1_VUB_UI recommendations.

Recommendations	Screen shots
<p>Tornado diagram should <u>not</u> be restricted to solely 10 users. (to be solved by algo. dev.)</p>	
<p>Float values in tables should be restricted to 3 digits (to be solved by algo. dev.) : Solved in algo.</p>	

- 'Select a value' could be changed in : "Select a consumer ID" ;
- The dropdown menu should display consumer IDs only and not including the phase e.g. `_1` or `_2`, `_3` ;

JSI approach: PQ-related disturbances

Since the service was not simulated, there will not be any appendix B for this service.

8.6 S4.1 – Inconsistencies in energy balance and power-voltage results

Service	S4.1 Inconsistencies in energy balance and power-voltage
Algorithm provider	ODT
Solution provider	ODT
	Good performance ●
	Non-critical error ●
	Error detected ●

Release date 13/02/2023

Service testing summary

Marketplace testing

Table 115. Service4.1_ODT_Marketplace testing.

Functional Test ID	Functional Test	Test responsible	Check	Comments
4.1_ODT_MK.1	Service contracts management	ODT	●	
		EYPESA	●	

Functional and KPIs testing

Table 116. Service4.1_ODT_Testing Summary Table.

Pilot	Functional Test ID	Functional Test	Test responsible	Check	Comments
SPAIN	4.1_ODT_FT.1	Active service contracts collection	ODT	●	
	4.1_ODT_FT.2	Data collection	ODT	●	
	4.1_ODT_FT.3	LV networks modelling	ODT	●	
	4.1_ODT_FT.4	Results export	ODT	●	
	4.1_ODT_FT.5	User access	EYPESA	●	
	4.1_ODT_KPI	KPIs validation	ODT	●	

Usability testing

Table 117. Service4.1_ODT_Usability testing.

UI Critical errors
UI Non-critical errors
UI Recommendations

Marketplace testing

Table 118. Service4.1_ODT_MK.1 Service contracts management.

Marketplace Test Description	Test Actions	Test responsible	Check
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36. Contract service	Found service in marketplace by searching it with one of the following keywords: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Non-technical losses, digital twin, AI, fraud detection, topology 	ODT	●
		EYPESA	●
	Select service to see details about it	ODT	●
		EYPESA	●
	Contract the service	ODT	●
		EYPESA	●
	Validate contract (data validation)	ODT	●
		EYPESA	●

Service Functional and KPIs Testing Actions

Table 119. Service4.1_ODT_FT.1 Active service contracts collection.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Test responsible	Pilot	Check
37. Active service contracts collection through the UnifiedAPI	List all the active and approved contracts	ODT	Spain	●
	Get the data tokens linked to the contracts	ODT	Spain	●

Table 120. Service4.1_ODT_FT.2 Data collection.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Test responsible	Pilot	Check
38. Data collection through the UnifiedAPI	Get contract data from the data lake for training the models	ODT	Spain	●
	Pre-process data in Odit-e format	ODT	Spain	●

Table 121. Service4.1_ODT_FT.3 NTL detections.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Test responsible	Pilot	Check
39. NTL detections	Low voltage networks models (Digital Twins) trained	ODT	Spain	●
	Energy balance evaluated for each substation with recorded data	ODT	Spain	●

	Bypass probability for each smart meter	ODT	Spain	●
	Nearby missing power probability for each smart meter	ODT	Spain	●

Table 122. Service4.1_ODT_FT.4 Results export.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Test responsible	Pilot	Check
40. Results export in Odit-e database and visualization	Algorithm results saved in database	ODT	Spain	●
	Results are available on the webapp	ODT	Spain	●
	Webapp credentials sent to the customer	ODT	Spain	●

Table 123. Service4.1_ODT_FT.5 User access.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Test responsible	Pilot	Check
41. Customer access to the results	The customer successfully connects to the webapp	EYPESA	Spain	●
	The customer sees the results on the webapp	EYPESA	Spain	●

Table 124. Service4.1_ODT_KPI KPIs validation.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Test responsible	Pilot	Check
42. KPIs (see hereafter)	KPI #1 is computed each week	ODT	Spain	●
	KPI #2 and #3 are validated after field validation	ODT	Spain	●

Table 125. Service4.1_ODT_List of service KPIs S4.1.

#	KPI	Description	Calculation	Expected value
1	Number of meters analysed	Total number of meters analysed by the service through the platform	$\sum \text{meters}$	-

2	Bypass accuracy	[Require field validation] Fraction of correct detected bypassed meters	Number of meters with correct detection / Total number of detection	>30%
3	NTL_nearby_accuracy	[Require field validation] Fraction of correct detections	Number of correct detections / Total number of detection	>30%

Usability testing

UI Critical errors

Errors that affect the tangible/numeric results: graphs display, login error, etc.

Table 126. Service4.1_ODT_UI critical errors.

Critical errors	Screen shots and description	Reporter
Type of error (login....)		

UI Non-critical errors

Errors that do not affect the tangible/numeric results: font sizes, colors of graphs, limits of the axis, etc.

Table 127. Service4.1_ODT_UI Non critical errors.

Non-critical errors	Screen shots	Reporter
Type of error (font size....)		

UI Recommendations

Provide recommendations for improving the front-end UI

Table 128. Service4.1_ODT_UI recommendations.

Recommendations	Screen shots	Reporter
Recommendation 1		

8.7 S4.2 – Fraud patterns detection

UPC approach: Fraud patterns detection

Service	S4.2 FRAUD PATTERN DETECTION
Algorithm provider	UPC – Marc Jené
Solution provider	WEP
	Good performance ●
	Non-critical error ●
	Error detected ●

Release date 01/09/2023

Service testing summary

Functional and KPIs testing

Table 129. Service4.2_UPC_Testing Summary Table.

Pilot	Functional Test ID	Functional Test	Check	Test respons.	Comments
EyPESA	EyPESA_4.2_UPC_FT.1	Functional Test Task 1	●	UPC	
	EyPESA_4.2_UPC_FT.2	Functional Test Task 2	●	UPC	Magnitude values use commas as decimal separators. SM ID field is not working in the Historical tab. Solved
	EyPESA_4.2_UPC_FT.3	Functional Test Task 3	●	UPC	
	EyPESA_4.2_UPC_FT.4	Functional Test Task 4	●	UPC	Problems with the Verify CTAs. Solved

EyPESA_4.2_UPC_FT.5	Functional Test Task 5	•	UPC	The table have some "hidden values" that make it impossible to sort by some variables. Errors also related to the decimal separators. Solved
EyPESA_4.2_UPC_FT.6	Functional Test Task 6	•	UPC	Downloading buttons not working. Solved
EyPESA_4.2_UPC_FT.7	Functional Test Task 7	•	UPC	Squatting fraud with negative values -> Change Technical Losses parameter to solve this. Solved
EyPESA_4.2_UPC_KPI.1	KPIs Task 1	•	UPC	The KPIs screen is not working at all. Solved

Usability testing

Table 130. Service4.2_UPC_Usability testing.

UI Critical errors
Decimal separators should be consistent and not compromise other functionalities. Solved, decimal separators are dots.
Verify CTA buttons should work properly. The buttons now work to verify/deny frauds and calculate the accuracy accordingly.
Downloading buttons are not working. Solved, they work now.
KPIs screen is not working. Solved and working.
UI Non-critical errors
Recent Results and Historical tables shouldn't have "hidden columns". The only hidden column now is SM ID, which is not used for sorting.
Squatting fraud have negative values -> Change Technical Losses parameter from 5% to 1% Done and results now don't have negative values.
UI Recommendations

Service Functional and KPIs Testing Actions

Table 131. Service4.2_UPC_FT.1 Functional Test Task 1.

Functional Description	Test	Test Actions	Check
43. <i>Dashboard:</i> Service first steps		Log-in to the UI through the BD4OPEM Marketplace is successful.	●
		Check the characteristics of the contract shown in the <i>Dashboard</i> .	●
		Test the <i>About</i> action box.	●
		Test the <i>Contact us</i> call to action.	●

Table 132. Service4.2_UPC_FT.2 Functional Test Task 2.

Functional Description	Test	Test Actions	Check
44. <i>Visualization:</i> Review Frauds' Information		<p>Check values from each column in the "Recent results" tab. All values should be coherent and appropriate.</p> <p>Comment: Magnitude values have decimal separators, while probability of fraudster (in 'SM'), has dot decimals.</p>	●
		<p>Check values from each column in the "Historical" tab. All values should be coherent and appropriate.</p> <p>Comment: SM ID field has [object Object] for every instance.</p>	●
		When a fraud appears in the "Recent results" tab it should also appear in the "Historical" tab with the same values.	●

Table 133. Service4.2_UPC_FT.3 Functional Test Task 3.

Functional Description	Test	Test Actions	Check
45. <i>Visualization:</i> Tab navigation (recent/historical)		Go to the “Recent results” tab. It should only show the results from the last execution (The example use case contains 5 grids).	●
		Go to the “Historical” tab. It should show the historical frauds with a “Detection date” column.	●

Table 134. Service4.2_UPC_FT.4 Functional Test Task 4.

Functional Description	Test	Test Actions	Check
46. <i>Visualization:</i> Verify functionality		<p>Mark one fraud as true (Verify = Yes) in the “Historical” tab.</p> <p>Comment: When clicking Yes, a text saying “! Something went wrong” appears. If switching to the <i>Recent Results</i> tab and going back to the <i>Historical</i> one, the verification mark disappears.</p> <p>Solved</p>	●
		<p>Mark one fraud as false (Verify = No) in the “Recent results” tab. Check whether it is shown in the “Historical” tab.</p> <p>Comment: Same thing as before. If switching to <i>Historical</i>, the fraud still appears as nothing happened.</p> <p>Solved</p>	●

Table 135. Service4.2_UPC_FT.5 Functional Test Task 5.

Functional Description	Test	Test Actions	Check																							
47. Visualization: Filter functionality		<p>In the <i>Recent Results</i> tab, sort the frauds by Probability and Type.</p> <p>Comment: Sorting by Probability works fine. However, since the Type appears in the dropdown, it is impossible to use it to sort the values.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>SM ID *</th> <th>Trafo ID **</th> <th>Probability [%]</th> <th>Magnitude [kW]</th> <th>Graph</th> <th>Verify</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>-</td> <td>ORM4991063500</td> <td>65</td> <td>2,997</td> <td>View Graph</td> <td>Yes No</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Type Squatting</p> <p>Duration [Days] 24</p> <p>Solved, only SM ID is shown in the dropdown now.</p>	SM ID *	Trafo ID **	Probability [%]	Magnitude [kW]	Graph	Verify	-	ORM4991063500	65	2,997	View Graph	Yes No	●											
	SM ID *	Trafo ID **	Probability [%]	Magnitude [kW]	Graph	Verify																				
	-	ORM4991063500	65	2,997	View Graph	Yes No																				
		<p>In the <i>Historical</i> tab, sort the frauds by Magnitude and Duration.</p> <p>Comment: Maybe because the Magnitude values use comma as separators, the sorting isn't properly performed. As above, the sorting by Duration isn't possible because it appears in the dropdown.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Detection Date</th> <th>Trafo ID **</th> <th>Probability [%]</th> <th>Magnitude [kW]</th> <th>Graph</th> <th>Verify</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>29/8/2023</td> <td>CIR4621546083</td> <td>-</td> <td>209</td> <td>View Graph</td> <td>Yes No</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>SM ID * [object Object]</p> <p>Type Other</p> <p>Duration [Days] 30+</p> <table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>29/8/2023</td> <td>CIR2081651126</td> <td>65</td> <td>2,285</td> <td>View Graph</td> <td>Yes No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>29/8/2023</td> <td>ORM4991063500</td> <td>65</td> <td>2,997</td> <td>View Graph</td> <td>Yes No</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Solved, by changing the decimal separators from comma to dots it works properly.</p>	Detection Date	Trafo ID **	Probability [%]	Magnitude [kW]	Graph	Verify	29/8/2023	CIR4621546083	-	209	View Graph	Yes No	29/8/2023	CIR2081651126	65	2,285	View Graph	Yes No	29/8/2023	ORM4991063500	65	2,997	View Graph	Yes No
Detection Date	Trafo ID **	Probability [%]	Magnitude [kW]	Graph	Verify																					
29/8/2023	CIR4621546083	-	209	View Graph	Yes No																					
29/8/2023	CIR2081651126	65	2,285	View Graph	Yes No																					
29/8/2023	ORM4991063500	65	2,997	View Graph	Yes No																					
	<p>Open the filter bubble by clicking on the button.</p>	●																								
	<p>Filter historical data by Magnitude (> 30 kW and < 100 kW)</p>	●																								
	<p>Filter recent data by Type</p>	●																								

Table 136. Service4.2_UPC_FT.6 Functional Test Task 6.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
48. Visualization: Download results	<p>Download results in .xlsx</p> <p>Comment: Button not working</p> <p>Solved</p>	●

	<p>Download results in .csv</p> <p>Comment: Button not working</p> <p>Solved</p>	●
	<p>Filter the dataset and download results from historical frauds due to "Plantation"</p> <p>Comment: Surprisingly, the button only works with filtered data, but not always.</p> <p>Solved</p>	●

Table 137. Service4.2_UPC_FT.7 Functional Test Task 7.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
<p>49. Visualization: View graph</p>	<p>Check the graph of a specific fraud due to Squatting. It shows the average daily load curve of the fraud. It is coherent.</p> <p>Comment: The graph contains negative values. Since this is not really coherent, the best way to solve it is by changing the Common Parameter 'techloss' from 5 to 1, assuming the technical losses of the grid are really small.</p> <p>Solved, after changing the percentage of technical losses the results look good.</p>	●
	<p>Check the graph of a specific fraud due to Plantation. It shows the average daily load curve of the fraud. It is coherent.</p>	●
	<p>The graph has the daily load profile of the fraud with hours in the X axis and Power in kW in the Y axis.</p>	●

Table 138. Service4.2_UPC_FT.8 Functional Test Task 8.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
<p>50. KPIs</p>	<p>Check detected frauds.</p>	●

	<p>Comment: Something occurs with KPIs, as they are not showed properly.</p> <p>Solved, there was something wrong with the json file the algorithm was using.</p>	
	<p>Check power recovered. Comment: Same as above. Solved</p>	<p>●</p>
	<p>Check accuracy. Comment: Same as above. Solved</p>	<p>●</p>
	<p>Check percentage of types of frauds. The labels should be consistent with the types from the list of frauds. Sum = 100%. Comment: Mining appears with a 12% even though there are no Mining frauds in the <i>Historical</i> screen. Solved</p>	<p>●</p>
	<p>Verify one of the detected frauds. Check if the KPIs are updated. Comment: Not tested due to previous errors. Solved</p>	<p>●</p>
	<p>Download pdf. Comment: Not working. Solved</p>	<p>●</p>

JSI approach: Fraud patterns detection

Service

S4.2 - Non Technical Losses

Algorithm provider

JSI – Dušan Gabrijelčič

Solution provider

JSI

Good performance ●

Non-critical error ●

Error detected ●

Release date 21/11/2023

Service testing summary

Functional and KPIs testing

Table 139. Service4.2_JSI_Testing Summary Table.

Pilot	Functional Test ID	Functional Test	Check	Test responsible	Comments
Spain	EyPESA_4.2_JSI_FT.1	Create data contract	●	EyPESA	
	EyPESA_4.2_JSI_FT.2	Activate data contract	●	JSI	
	EyPESA_4.2_JSI_FT.3	Create contract service	●	EyPESA	
	EyPESA_4.2_JSI_FT.4	Activate contract service	●	JSI	
	EyPESA_4.2_JSI_FT.5	Service execution and results	●	EyPESA	

Usability testing

Table 140. Service4.2_JSI_Usability testing.

UI Critical errors
/
UI Non-critical errors
/
UI Recommendations
/

Service functional and KPIs testings actions

Table 141. Service4.2_JSI_FT.1 Functional Test Task 1.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
1. Create data contract	Search for the data set "Fraud pattern detection (NTL) input data" on Marketplace. Click on "See more" and "Contract data".	●

	Enter business parameters and click "Submit"	●

Table 142. Service4.2_JSI_FT.1 Functional Test Task 2.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
2. Activate data contract	Approve the data contract from functional task 1 - data contract structure and parameters are okay	●
	Activate the data contract - data contract can now be used in service contracts	●

Table 143. Service4.2_JSI_FT.1 Functional Test Task 3.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
3. Create service contract	Search for the "Fraud pattern detection" service on the Marketplace. Click on "See more" and then "Request new service". 	●
	Enter business parameters	●
	Select the corresponding service parameters:	●

	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;"> <p>pilot The pilot to use</p> <p>Type Application</p> <p>Values *</p> <div style="display: flex; gap: 5px;"> slovenian eypesa </div> </div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin-top: 5px;"> <p>case Based on pilot choice, choose the corresponding 'case' - on which data to run the service. Two additional parameters (loss_start and loss_end) are determined based on pilot and case choice. Cases bd4opem_elce_ntl_case_1 or _2 are applicable to Slovenian pilot, while the rest are applicable to EyPESA pilot.</p> <p>Type Application</p> <p>Values *</p> <div style="display: flex; flex-wrap: wrap; gap: 5px;"> bd4opem_elce_ntl_case_1 bd4opem_elce_ntl_case_2 balenya canovelles case115 case705 eulalia </div> </div>	
	Select data contract created in functional task 1 and activated in functional task 2	●
	Click on "Yes" for "Enable immediate execution"	●
	Click on "Request service" to send the service contract	●

Table 144. Service4.2_JSI_FT.1 Functional Test Task 4.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
4. Activate service contract	Approve the service contract from functional task 3 - contract structure, business and technical parameters are okay, data contract selected and immediate execution enabled	●
	Activate the service contract - this will make an instance of the service	●
	ASM invoked	●
	Data accessed through the data lake	●
	Read technical parameters and run the service	●

*Comment:
Data has been uploaded in service Docker image*

Table 145. Service4.2_JSI_FT.1 Functional Test Task 5.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
5. Service execution and results	<p>Upon activation of service contract, click on "Go to service" button for the corresponding service contract, found in the "Service requests" table on "My Services" page for "Service User":</p>	●
	UI accessed after clicking "Go to service button"	●
	Notebook executed - service no longer in "Services" -> "Running" tab	●
	Click on service ID in "Services" -> "History" tab to fetch report	●

Usability testing

UI Non-critical errors

Errors that do not affect the tangible/numeric results: font sizes, colors of graphs, limits of the axis, etc.

Table 146. Service4.2_JSI_UI Non-critical errors.

Non-critical errors	Screen shots
/	

UI Recommendations

Provide recommendations for improving the front-end UI

Table 147. Service4.2_JSI_UI recommendations.

Recommendations	Screen shots
/	

8.8 S5.1 – Flexibility Forecast

UPC approach: Flexibility forecast

Service	S5.1 FLEXIBILITY FORECAST
Algorithm provider	UPC – Rafaela Ribeiro / Arthur Pasquet
Solution provider	ICOM
	Good performance ●
	Non-critical error ●
	Error detected ●
Release date	30/09/2023

Service testing summary

Functional and KPIs testing

Table 148. Service5.1_UPC_Testing Summary Table.

Pilot	Functional Test ID	Functional Test	Check	Test responsible	Comments
Spain	SPAIN_5.1_UPC_FT.1	History	●		
	SPAIN_5.1_UPC_FT.2	Data Selection	●		
	SPAIN_5.1_UPC_FT.3	Training model results	●		
	SPAIN_5.1_UPC_FT.4	Forecast results	●		
	SPAIN_5.1_UPC_KPI.1	KPIs	●		
	SPAIN_5.1_UPC_EXEC	Execution times pilot	●		

Usability testing

Table 149. Service5.1_UPC_Usability testing.

UI Non-critical errors
Font size
Limit axis
UI Recommendations
Include selection of “Positive Flexibility” or “Negative Flexibility”

Service Functional and KPIs Testing Actions

Table 150. Service5.1_UPC_FT.1 History.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
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1. History	List of previous runs can be observed	●
	"Model Info" and "Forecast" buttons return corresponding information	●
	Within "Model Info" functions as verified in Table 3.	●
	Within "Forecast" functions as verified in Table 4.	●

Table 151. Service5.1_UPC_FT.2 Data selection.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
2. Data selection	Selection of "EV" and/or "ESS" from droplist	●
	Selection of either "Positive Flexibility" or "Negative Flexibility"	●
	Date selection is more than 1 year and it exists on dataset	●
	If time resolution is lower than present in the data, the time resolution of the data is used.	●
	The last 7 days of data exist.	●
	The user can consult previous runs.	●

Table 152. Service5.1_UPC_FT.3 Training model results.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
3. Training model results	Summary of Data Selection correctly presented	●
	Table presents model results and real data comparison with correct units and title	●
	Plot presents the model results and real data comparison with correct units and title	●
	Selection of training line or input values on plot	●
	Interaction with plot lines is available	●
	Data download button delivers the file	●

Table 153. Service5.1_UPC_FT.4 Forecast results.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
	Summary of Data Selection correctly presented	●

4. Forecast results	Table presents the forecasted flexibility values for all times of the day with correct units and title	●
	Plot presents the forecasted flexibility values for all times of the day with correct units and title	●
	Interaction with plot line is available	●
	Metrics shown should be bigger or equal to zero	●

Table 154. Service5.1_UPC_KPI.1 KPIs.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
5. KPI	Use case 1 - Total flexibility value: 3521.69/>0	●
	Use case 1 - Average flexibility value: 5.13/>0	●
	Use case 1 - Average flexibility availability: 1.96/[0-100%]	●
	Use case 1 - Mean Absolute Percentage Error: 143.75/[0-100%]	●
	Use case 2 - Total flexibility value: 3521.69/>0	●
	Use case 2 - Average flexibility value: 5.13/>0	●
	Use case 2 - Average flexibility availability: 1.96/[0-100%]	●
	Use case 2 - Mean Absolute Percentage Error: 147.78/[0-100%]	●

Table 155. Service5.1_UPC_EXEC Functional Test Task 4

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Execution time local/front-end	Check
6. Execution time	Executing algorithm for Use Case 1	54 min / 60 s	●

Usability testing

UI Non-critical errors

Errors that do not affect the tangible/numeric results: font sizes, colors of graphs, limits of the axis, etc.

Table 156. Service5.1_UPC_Non-critical errors.

Non-critical errors	Screen shots
Font size	Nothing to declare.

Limit axis	Nothing to declare.
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UI Recommendations

Provide recommendations for improving the front-end UI

Table 157. Service5.1_UPC_UI recommendations.

Recommendations	Screen shots
<p>Recommendation 1</p>	<p>For forecast</p> <p>Add the unit on the Y axis</p>
<p>Recommendation 2</p>	<p>For model training the same</p>

JSI approach: Flexibility forecast

Service
Algorithm provider
Solution provider

S5.1 - Flexibility Forecast Based On Price Signals

JSI – Dušan Gabrijelčič

JSI

- Good performance ●
- Non-critical error ●
- Error detected ●

Release date 21/11/2023

Service testing summary

Functional and KPIs testing (Responsible: Algorithm dev)

Table 158. Service5.1_JSI_Testing Summary Table.

Pilot	Functional Test ID	Functional Test	Check	Test responsible	Comments
Spain	EyPESA_5.1_JSI_FT.1	Create data contract	●	EyPESA	
	EyPESA_5.1_JSI_FT.2	Activate data contract	●	JSI	
	EyPESA_5.1_JSI_FT.3	Create contract service	●	EyPESA	

	EyPESA_5.1_JSI_FT.4	Activate service contract	●	JSI	
	EyPESA_5.1_JSI_FT.5	Service execution and results	●	EyPESA	

Usability testing

Table 159. Service5.1_JSI_Usability testing.

UI Critical errors
/
UI Non-critical errors
/
UI Recommendations
/More interactive document.

Service Functional and KPIs Testing Actions

Table 160. Service5.1_JSI_FT.1 Functional test task 1.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
1. Create data contract	Search for the data set "Flexibility forecast input data" on Marketplace. Click on "See more" and "Contract data".	●
	Enter business parameters and click "Submit"	●

Table 161. Service5.1_JSI_FT.2 Functional Test Task 2.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
2. Activate data contract	Approve the data contract from functional task 1 - data contract structure and parameters are okay	●
	Activate the data contract - data contract can now be used in service contracts	●

Table 162. Service5.1_JSI_FT.3 Functional Test Task 3.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
3. Create service contract	<p>Search for the “Flexibility forecast based on price signals” service on the Marketplace. Click on “See more” and then “Request new service”.</p>	●
	Enter business parameters	●
	Select the corresponding service parameters:	●
		●
	Select data contract created in functional task 1 and activated in functional task 2	●
	Click on “Yes” for “Enable immediate execution”	●
	Click on “Request service” to send the service contract	●

Table 163. Service5.1_JSI_FT.4 Functional Test Task 4.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
4. Activate service contract	Approve the service contract from functional task 3 - contract structure, business and technical parameters are okay, data contract selected and immediate execution enabled	●

	Activate the service contract - this will make an instance of the service	●
	ASM invoked	●
	Data accessed through the data lake	● <i>Comment: Data has been upload ed in service Docker image</i>
	Read technical parameters and run the service	

Table 164. Service5.1_JSI_FT.5 Functional Test Task 5.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
5. Service execution and results	Upon activation of service contract, click on "Go to service" button for the corresponding service contract, found in the "Service requests" table on "My Services" page for "Service User": 	●
	UI accessed after clicking "Go to service button"	●
	Notebook executed - service no longer in "Services" -> "Running" tab	●
	Click on service ID in "Services" -> "History" tab to fetch report	●

Usability testing

UI Critical errors

Errors that affect the tangible/numeric results: graphs display, login error, etc.

Critical errors	Screen shots and description	Reporter
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/		
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UI Non-critical errors

Errors that do not affect the tangible/numeric results: font sizes, colors of graphs, limits of the axis, etc.

Non-critical errors	Screen shots
/	

UI Recommendations

Provide recommendations for improving the front-end UI

Recommendations	Screen shots
/	

8.9 S5.2 – Flexibility aggregated services for BRPs

Service	S5.2 Flexibility Services for BRPs
Algorithm provider	UPC – Adriano Caprara/ Sara Barja Martínez
Solution provider	ICOM
	Good performance ●
	Non-critical error ●
	Error detected ●
Release date	30/11/2023

Service testing summary

Functional and KPIs testing

Table 165. Testing Summary Table S5.2.

Pilot	Functional Test ID	Functional Test	Check	Test responsible	Comments
PILOT 1	SPAIN_S5.2_UPC_FT.1	Functional Test Task 1	●		Brief description of the error detected
	SPAIN_S5.2_UPC_FT.2	Functional Test Task 2	●		
	SPAIN_S5.2_UPC_FT.3	Functional Test Task 3	●		
	SPAIN_S5.2_UPC_EXEC	Execution times pilot 1	●		

Usability testing

Table 166. Service5.2_UPC_Usability testing.

UI Non-critical errors
Font size
Limit axis
UI Recommendations
Provide recommendations for improving the front-end UI

Service Functional and KPIs Testing Actions

Table 167. SPAIN_5.2_UPC_FT.1 Functional Test Task 1.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
51. Day-ahead optimization: "Forecast" tab	Explore different forecasting variables to be displayed, changing the input of "Select what to display". Verify that the shown plots represent the chosen variable.	●
	Verify the date range selection; by changing "Start Date" and "End Date" values, the visualizations should change accordingly	●
	Verify frequency selection; by changing the value the granularity of the visualizations should also change	●
	Verify that KPIs are updated when changing date range	●
	Verify that KPIs are updated when changing KPI metric button	●

Table 168. SPAIN_5.2_UPC_FT.2 Functional Test Task 2.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
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52. Day-ahead optimization: "Optimization" tab	Try different values for the inputs "Max cost" and "Flexibility cost", the plotted profiles should change accordingly	●
	Verify that the values are plotted for the 24 hours of the day ahead	●
	Verify that the KPIs are correctly displayed	●

Table 169. SPAIN_5.2_UPC_FT.3 Functional Test Task 3.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
53. Self-balancing	Verify that the values "Prediction of the imbalances" and "periods to activate flexibility" are plotted for the 24 hours of the day ahead	●
	Verify that the KPI "Percentage of BRP imbalances" is correctly displayed	●

Table 170. SPAIN_5.2_UPC_EXEC.1 Functional Test Task 4.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Execution time local/front-end	Check
54. Execution time	Generation of "Day-ahead optimization: forecast" visualizations	<20 s	●
	Generation of "Day-ahead optimization: optimization" visualizations	<20 s	●
	Generation of "Self-balancing" visualizations	<20 s	●

8.10S5.3 – Flexibility aggregated services for DSOs

UPC approach: Flexibility-based AC OPF

Service	S5.3 Flexibility Agg Services for DSOs
Algorithm provider	UPC – Alejandro Hernandez
Solution provider	ICOM
	Good performance ●
	Non-critical error ●
	Error detected ●
Release date	27/07/2023

Service testing summary

Functional and KPIs testing

Table 171: Testing Summary Table S5.3, UPC

Pilot	Functional Test ID	Functional Test	Check	Test responsible	Comments
Spain	SPAIN_X.X_PARTNER_FT.X	Functional Test Task 1	●	Alejandro Hernandez	Brief description of the error detected
	SPAIN_X.X_PARTNER_FT.X	Functional Test Task 2	●	Alejandro Hernandez	
	SPAIN_X.X_PARTNER_FT.X	Functional Test Task 3	●	Alejandro Hernandez	
	SPAIN_X.X_PARTNER_KPI.X	KPIs Task <i>n</i>	●	Alejandro Hernandez	
	SPAIN_X.X_PARTNER_EXEC	Execution times pilot 1	●	Alejandro Hernandez	

Usability testing

Table 172. Service5.3_UPC_Usability testing.

UI Non-critical errors
Font color
Axis label
UI Recommendations
Recommendations such as more informative messages for the user to understand some features of the interface should be considered. Darker tone of some fonts.

Service Functional and KPIs Testing Actions

Table 173. SPAIN_S5.3_UPC_FT.1 Functional Test Task 1.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
55. Data Ingestion	<p>Make sure the data from the pilot is correctly ingested for the service.</p> <p>Suggestion: Change the font of the daily forecast and forecast to a darker font. Current is very subtle.</p>	●

	Verify the data from the service S3.1 is correctly received	●
	Verify there are no NaN values	●

Table 174. SPAIN_S5.3_UPC_FT.2 Functional Test Task 2.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
	<p>Check Summary values shown. All of the values should be coherent and appropriate.</p> <p>Comment: Most congested lines not appearing</p>	●
56. Review daily results	<p>Explore different selection of flexibility sources. Try two and make sure the values change.</p> <p>Comment: Mean flexibility usage is not appearing</p>	●
	<p>Check the values shown for different dates selection. Choose at least two available dates and make sure the values change.</p> <p>Some values are missing display</p>	●

Table 175. SPAIN_S5.3_UPC_FT.3 Functional Test Task 3.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
57. Evaluate visualization	Select different times of the day, confirm the plots change	●
	Download figures for the most congested time of the day	●
	Confirm the images open correctly	●

Table 176. SPAIN_S5.3_UPC_FT.4 Functional Test Task 4.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
58. Preview of data	Select different buses IDs and explore their behaviour	●
	Download the data in excel form	●
	It can only be downloaded as a figure. Is it possible to change it also to Excel form?	●
	Confirm the downloaded dataset opens correctly	●

Table 177. SPAIN_S5.3_UPC_FT.4 Functional Test Task 5.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
59. Execute Use Case 1	Compare results given the set	●

Table 178. SPAIN_S5.3_UPC_KPI.5 Functional Test Task 6.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
60. KPI	KPI benchmark/range comparison Requested Flexibility in range of 20 to 50%	●
	KPI benchmark/range comparison congestion clearing in range of 80 to 100%	●

Table 179. SPAIN_S5.3_UPC_EX.6 Functional Test Task 7.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Execution time local/front-end	Check
61. Execution time	Executing algorithm for Use Case 1	10 s/ 60 s	
	Training algorithm for algorithm	60 s/ 70s	

JSI approach: Flexibility services for DSOs based on neural networks

Service	S5.3 - Flexibility Services For DSOs
Algorithm provider	JSI – Dušan Gabrijelčič
Solution provider	JSI
	Good performance ●
	Non-critical error ●
	Error detected ●

Release date 22/11/2023

Service testing summary

Functional and KPIs testing (Responsible: Algorithm dev)

Table 180. Service_S5.3_JSI_Testing Summary Table.

Pilot	Functional Test ID	Functional Test	Check	Test responsible	Comments
Spain	EyPESA_5.3_JSI_FT.1	Create data contract	●	EyPESA	
	EyPESA_5.3_JSI_FT.2	Activate data contract	●	JSI	
	EyPESA_5.3_JSI_FT.3	Create contract service	●	EyPESA	
	EyPESA_5.3_JSI_FT.4	Activate contract service	●	JSI	
	EyPESA_5.3_JSI_FT.5	Service execution and results	●	EyPESA	

Usability testing

Table 181. Service_S5.3_JSI_Usability testing.

UI Critical errors
/
UI Non-critical errors
/
UI Recommendations
/

Service Functional and KPIs Testing Actions

Table 182. Service5.3_JSI_FT.1 Functional Test Task 1.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
1. Create data contract	Search for the data set "Flexibility service for DSOs input data" on Marketplace. Click on "See more" and "Contract data".	●
	Enter business parameters and click "Submit"	●

Table 183. Service5.3_JSI_FT.2 Functional Test Task 2.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
2. Activate data contract	Approve the data contract from functional task 1 - data contract structure and parameters are okay	●
	Activate the data contract - data contract can now be used in service contracts	●

Table 184. Service5.3_JSI_FT.3 Functional Test Task 3.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
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3. Create service contract	<p>Search for the “Flexibility services for DSOs based on neural networks” service on the Marketplace. Click on “See more” and then “Request new service”.</p>	●
	Enter business parameters	●
	<p>Select the corresponding service parameters:</p>	●
	Select data contract created in functional task 1 and activated in functional task 2	●
	Click on “Yes” for “Enable immediate execution”	●
	Click on “Request service” to send the service contract	●

Table 185. Service5.3_JSI_FT.4 Functional Test Task 4.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
4. Activate service contract	Approve the service contract from functional task 3 - contract structure, business and technical parameters are okay, data contract selected and immediate execution enabled	●
	Activate the service contract - this will make an instance of the service	●
	ASM invoked	●
	Data accessed through the data lake	●
		<i>Comment:</i>

		<i>Data has been uploaded in service Docker image</i>
	Read technical parameters and run the service	

Table 186. Service5.3_JSI_FT.5 Functional Test Task 5.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
5. Service execution and results	<p>Upon activation of service contract, click on "Go to service" button for the corresponding service contract, found in the "Service requests" table on "My Services" page for "Service User":</p>	●
	UI accessed after clicking "Go to service button"	●
	Notebook executed - service no longer in "Services" -> "Running" tab	●
	Click on service ID in "Services" -> "History" tab to fetch report	●

8.11S6.1 – Energy management at household or at community level

Service	S6.1 Building Energy Management System
Algorithm provider	S6.2 Energy forecasting
Solution provider	UPC – Sara Barja Martínez
	ICOM
	Good performance ●
	Non-critical error ●
	Error detected ●
Release date	28/08/2023

Service testing summary

Functional and KPIs testing

Table 187. Testing Summary Table S6.1.

Pilot	Functional Test ID	Functional Test	Check	Test respons.	Comments
EyPESA	EyPESA_6.1_UPC_FT.1	Create a new project	●	UPC	
	EyPESA_6.1_UPC_FT.2	Under "Create a new project": Project info section	●	UPC	
	EyPESA_6.1_UPC_FT.3	Under "Create a new project": Building info section	●	UPC	
	EyPESA_6.1_UPC_FT.4	Under "Create a new project": Tariff info section	●	UPC	
	EyPESA_6.1_UPC_FT.5	Under "Create a new project": Asset info section	●	UPC	
	EyPESA_6.1_UPC_FT.6	Under "Create a new project": "Forecast info"	●	UPC	
	EyPESA_6.1_UPC_FT.7	Under "Create a new project": Project was created	●	UPC	
	EyPESA_6.1_UPC_FT.8	Create a new scenario under a Project	●	UPC	
	EyPESA_6.1_UPC_FT.9	Check the scenario results	●	UPC	i) Electricity prices are not shown in the UI plots.
	EyPESA_6.1_UPC_KPI.1	Scenario KPIs validation	●	UPC	
	EyPESA_6.1_UPC_EXEC.1	Execution time	●	UPC	

Usability testing

UI Critical errors

UI Non-critical errors

1 non-critical errors

--

UI Recommendations

0 UI recommendations

Service Functional and KPIs Testing Actions

Table 188. EyPESA_6.1_UPC_FT.1 Functional Test Task 1.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
62. Create a new project	Log-in to the UI through the BD4OPEM Marketplace is sucesfull	●
	Press "Add new project" button	●

Table 189. EyPESA_6.1_UPC_FT.2 Functional Test Task 2.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
63. Under "Create a new project": Project info section	Write Project name	●
	Write project description	●
	Click "next step" button	●

Table 190. EyPESA_6.1_UPC_FT.3 Functional Test Task 3.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
64. Under "Create a new project": Building info section	Select and upload the "Prosumer" file	●
	Comment on v2 : The electricity price file could be inside Tariff info section , with electricity price sell. (This is not critical, just some comment as improvement if it is easy to implement and if there is time to do it). → in v3 done	●
	Select and upload the "Generation Coefficient" file	●
	Click "next step" button	●

Table 191. EyPESA_6.1_UPC_FT.4 Functional Test Task 4.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
-----------------------------	--------------	-------

65. Under "Create a new project": Tariff info section	Select the "Scheme Price" path		●
	"Scheme Price" file is loaded correctly		●
	Click next step button		●

Table 192. EyPESA_6.1_UPC_FT.5 Functional Test Task 5.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check	
66. Under "Create a new project": Asset info section	Select the "Asset"	●	
	All available assets appear in the tab	●	
	"Asset" selected correctly	●	
	Select the "Param Batteries" path	●	
	"Param Batteries" file is loaded correctly		●
	Click next step button		●

Table 193. EyPESA_6.1_UPC_FT.6 Functional Test Task 6.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
67. Under "Create a new project": "Forecast info"	Select the FORECAST INFO	●
	Load the "Generation Forecast" file	●
	Load the "Forecast building 1" file	●
	Load the "Forecast building 2" file	●
	Load the "Forecast building 3" file	●
	Load the "Forecast building 4" file	●
	All files are loaded correctly	●

Table 194. EyPESA_6.1_UPC_FT.6 Functional Test Task 6.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
68. Under "Create a new project": Project was created	Validate the project was created successfully 	●
	Press "Finish" button	●

Table 195. EyPESA_6.1_UPC_FT.7 Functional Test Task 7.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
	Open the project that has been just created	●

	<p>Add new scenarios</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">●</p>
<p>69. Create a new scenario under a Project</p>	<p>Validate building info</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">●</p>
	<p>Validate tariff info</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">●</p>
	<p>Validate asset info</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">●</p>

	<p>ASSET INFO</p> <p>Select Asset: <input type="text" value="bat_1"/></p> <p>Max Charging Power (kW) <input type="text" value="90"/> Min State of Charge of the Battery (SOC) (kWh) <input type="text" value="31.65"/></p> <p>Max Discharging Power (kW) <input type="text" value="90"/> SOC Initial (kWh) <input type="text" value="150"/></p> <p>Max State of Charge of the Battery (SOC) (kWh) <input type="text" value="189.9"/> SOC Final (kWh) <input type="text" value="150"/></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Next Step ></p>									
	<p>Run the scenario created</p> <p style="text-align: center;">+ Add New Scenarios</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>NAME</th> <th>DATE CREATED</th> <th>STATUS</th> <th>ACTIONS</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>scenario1</td> <td>01/08/2023</td> <td>Not Started</td> <td> Run Simulation Delete </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	NAME	DATE CREATED	STATUS	ACTIONS	scenario1	01/08/2023	Not Started	Run Simulation Delete	●
NAME	DATE CREATED	STATUS	ACTIONS							
scenario1	01/08/2023	Not Started	Run Simulation Delete							
	<p>Press "Finish" button</p>	●								

Table 196. EyPESA_6.1_UPC_FT.9 Functional Test Task 9.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check								
<p>70. Check the scenario results</p>	<p>Click the "view results" button</p> <p style="text-align: center;">+ Add New Scenarios</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>NAME</th> <th>DATE CREATED</th> <th>STATUS</th> <th>ACTIONS</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>scenario1</td> <td>01/08/2023</td> <td>Success</td> <td> Run Simulation View Results Delete </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	NAME	DATE CREATED	STATUS	ACTIONS	scenario1	01/08/2023	Success	Run Simulation View Results Delete	●
NAME	DATE CREATED	STATUS	ACTIONS							
scenario1	01/08/2023	Success	Run Simulation View Results Delete							
	<p>(v3) The Download results button does not work: No file is downloaded. → (v4) now it works</p>	●								
	<p>(comment on last version v3) Is it possible to add a third graph with the electricity price for buying and for selling? This way, it is easier to understand why battery charges and discharges. → v4: The graph below is not the electricity price for buy and sell (It is the total amount of electricity bought and sold for building). However, it is good to keep this</p>	●								

graph, so I would suggest to add another one for the electricity prices.

To facilitate things, I have added to the `prosumer_str(timestamp).xlsx` output file (`result_prosumer` dataframe in the code) two new columns with the information of the electricity price for buying and selling (see how they look below).

→ Is it possible to create a new plot named "Electricity price for buy and sell" showing these two hourly prices?

	Elect price buy	Elect price sell
	0.3979927085148	0.04285
	0.4126782690429	0.038
	0.41176797871649995	0.03599
	0.4139613105474	0.03462

(v3) The result plots don't change if the scenario parameters change, or the electricity prices change. For all four scenarios run, they always show the same plot results and KPIs as well. → solved. Now it works

Check that the KPIs results are correct:

(v3) The KPIs are calculated for each building and for the whole local energy community. Here only the LEC are shown. Is it possible to provide also the information for the individual buildings? Maybe with a selection KPIs tab to show it? → pending to check from UPC side

Table 197. EyPESA_6.1_UPC_KPI.1.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
71. Scenario KPIs validation	Validate KPI #1: reduced cost (€). Make sure this KPIs matches the KPI local execution.	●
	Validate KPI #2: % electricity cost reduction. Make sure this KPIs matches the KPI local execution	●
	Validate KPI #3: % self-consumption. Make sure this KPIs matches the KPI local execution	●

Table 198. KPIs S6.1.

KPI Name	Description	Expected performance	Unit	Freq. update	Formula
Reduced cost (RC)	Electricity bill savings driven by the EMS optimisation	> 10 €/day	€	daily	$RC = \sum_t TotalEnergyConsumed \cdot ElectricityPrice - TotalEMSEnergyPurchasedGrid \cdot ElectricityPrice$
Percentage of electricity cost reduction (PRC)	Percentage of electricity bill savings driven by the EMS optimisation	10% -50%	%	daily	$PRC = \sum_t \frac{RC}{Total\ energy\ consumed \cdot ElectricityPrice}$
Self-consumption (SC)	Percentage of total energy consumed coming from local energy community's own generation sources (PV and batteries).	5% - 50%	%	daily	$SC = \sum_t \frac{Total\ Renewable\ energy\ generation}{Total\ energy\ consumed}$

Table 199. EyPESA_6.1_UPC_EXEC.1.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Execution time local/front-end	Check
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72. Execution time	Executing algorithm for Scenario 1	- s/ - s	●
	Executing algorithm for Scenario 2	- s/ - s	●
	Executing algorithm for Scenario n	- s/ - s	●

Usability testing

UI Critical errors

Errors that affect the tangible/numeric results: graphs display, login error, etc.

Table 200. Service6.1_UPC_Critical errors.

Critical errors	Screen shots

UI Non-critical errors

Errors that do not affect the tangible/numeric results: font sizes, colors of graphs, limits of the axis, etc.

Table 201. Service5.3_UPC_Non-critical errors.

Non-critical errors	Screen shots
<p>When looking at the results, here I would say "24h energy consumption and generation forecast", since the PV gen is also in the plot.</p> <p>→ done</p>	
<p>The Assets diagram is now up to date. → done</p>	

I would clarify a bit more this message, to add context why this happens. Also the data used from yesterday is only for some hours, not the entire 24hours. I would say something like this:

"Since the Spot Electricity Market has not yet closed, some hours of the simulation will be based on the electricity prices from the previous day. Do you want to proceed?"
→ pending to check by UPC

As it is now, the results are shown like this:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
1	soc	150	189.9	189.9	169.624941	141.298397	108.613104	84.136721	63.993973	47.5163023	31.65
2	charge_ener	41.7801047	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	discharge_en	0	0	18.6936041	26.1170741	30.1358402	22.5672247	18.5716137	15.1924124	14.6287307	0
4	buy_building	21.1879383	6.55166313	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.84866285
5	sell_building	0	0	0	2.61063901	4.01867831	1.39271224	0	0	0	0
6	buy_building	9.26618769	3.74803428	0.72097529	0	0	0	0.72551826	0.92830626	0.52966203	1.66402201
7	sell_building	0	0	0	0.50147937	1.1409311	0	0	0	0	0
8	buy_building	1.00453269	0.15331407	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	sell_building	0	0	0.22186909	0.3705671	0.4512216	0.30006556	0.21964879	0.22676751	0.33522619	0.20856339
10	buy_building	31.8764557	14.1650819	2.47578579	0.96892027	0	0.85801184	4.66522472	4.52469948	14.7004282	22.9368432
11	sell_building	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12											
13											
14											
15											
16											

Would it be possible to show the the results tabs like this? I think it is easier to visualize and play with, for the end-users

Is it possible to transpose the "Service Results" Excel file tabs?

	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
buy_building1	0	0	0.185643	0	0	0.206206647	2.818711762	0	
buy_building2	0	0	0.940179	0	0	0.221066679	5.179943879	0	
buy_building3	0	0	0.720975	0	0	0.221869085	2.475785787	0	
buy_building4	0	0	0.617366	0	0	0.221387727	4.5492252	0	
buy_building5	0	0	0.58136	0	0	0.221582838	5.511330257	0	
buy_building6	1.0328	0	1.039505	0	0	0.161464841	4.18442911	0	
buy_building7	6.500065	0	3.51126	0	0.151783	0	13.57959928	0	
buy_building8	5.317344	0	3.207168	0	0.077081	0	11.81705744	0	
buy_building9	5.120056	0	2.723972	0	0	0.04265158	21.72221891	0	
buy_building10	3.848663	0	1.664022	0	0	0.208563394	22.93684321	0	
buy_building11	1.578219	0	1.356746	0	0	0.345341804	19.18808942	0	
buy_building12	1.394643	0	0.721065	0	0	0.468374155	18.96628943	0	
buy_building13	0.271918	0	0.079143	0	0	0.537954149	18.23811106	0	
buy_building14	1.125938	0	0.438607	0	0	0.501348995	16.20966098	0	
buy_building15	3.551349	0	1.537671	0	0	0.32536483	18.89375035	0	
buy_building16	4.907884	0	2.37573	0	0	0.14536104	20.27287052	0	
buy_building17	35.70945	0	14.79998	0	1.503864	0	62.09848473	0	
buy_building18	39.31963	0	17.13108	0	1.812712	0	71.11908251	0	
buy_building19	8.878971	0	4.07176	0	0.074812	0	29.0444965	0	
buy_building20	7.83963	0	4.088102	0	0.105383	0	26.6301976	0	
buy_building21	7.007457	0	4.037249	0	0.128787	0	21.55099073	0	
buy_building22	5.002929	0	2.264858	0	0	0.074949534	10.68948964	0	
buy_building23	0	0	0.109303	0	0	0.358823115	1.418483167	0	
buy_building24	8.641395	0	3.636008	0	0.149502	0	11.83874437	0	

UI Recommendations

Provide recommendations for improving the front-end UI

Table 202. Service6.1_UPC_UI recommendations.

Recommendations	Screen shots
<p>It would be nice to be able to check the scenario parameters that have been set. Sometimes I didn't remember the values that I set, and when checking the results, it was a bit difficult to ensure. → done</p>	

8.12S7.1 – P2P trading

Service	S7.1 P2P Energy Trading
Algorithm provider	ATOS – Ross Little
Solution provider	ATOS
	Good performance ●
	Non-critical error ●
	Error detected ●
Release date	27/11/2023

Service testing summary

Functional and KPIs testing

Table 203. Service7.1_ATOS_Testing Summary Table.

Pilot	Functional Test ID	Functional Test description	Check	Comments
Spain	Spain_7.1_ATOS_FT.1	Service User login and list P2P SU contracts	●	
	Spain_7.1_ATOS_FT.2	Select & initialise contract	●	
	Spain_7.1_ATOS_FT.3	Download trading results after a 24 hour period	●	
	Spain_7.1_ATOS_KPI.1	KPIs	●	
	Spain_7.1_ATOS_EXEC	Execution time	●	

Usability testing

Table 204. Service7.1_ATOS_Usability testing.

UI Critical errors
UI Non-critical errors
UI Recommendations

Service Functional and KPIs Testing Actions

Table 205. Service7.1_ATOS_FT.1 Service User login and list P2P SU contracts

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
1. Service User login and list P2P SU contracts	SU performs successful federated login by clicking on P2P Trading url and then being redirected to the Marketplace login, and after successful login is automatically redirected back to the P2P Trading service.	●
	Upon being redirected back the SU is able to view all P2P Trading Service User contracts for their organization.	●

Table 206. Service7.1_ATOS_FT.2 Select & initialise contract

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
2. Select & initialise contract	SU selects P2P Trading contract of interest and checks its parameters and associated Data User contract parameters	●
	SU initialises the contract and confirms its state as active	●

Table 207. Service7.1_ATOS_FT.3 Download trading results after a 24 hour period

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check

3. Download trading results after a 24 hour period	SU selects contract to view trading results and downloads the csv	●
	Importing csv into excel and check that the trading figures are in accordance with the equality sharing cooperative trading algorithm specified in D5.4	●

Table 208: Service7.1_ATOS KPIs

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
4. KPI	Number of CEC members (smart meters) in a P2P Trading Service (minimum 3)	●
	Number of CEC members trading energy during 24 hour period (minimum 1)	●

Table 209: Service7.1_ATOS Execution time

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Execution time local/front-end	Check
5. Execution time	Executing algorithm	- s/ - s	●

8.13S8.1 – Asset and investment planning

Service	S8.1 Asset and Investment Planning
Algorithm provider	UPC – Antonio E. Saldaña González
Solution provider	WEP
	Good performance ●
	Non-critical error ●
	Error detected ●
Release date	22/03/2023

Service testing summary

Functional and KPIs testing

Table 210. Testing Summary Table S8.1.

Pilot	Functional Test ID	Check	Comments
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		Functional description	Test	
Spain	Spain_8.1_UPC_FT.1	Stress test tab display options	●	
	Spain_8.1_UPC_FT.2	Planning Action tab display options	●	
	Spain_8.1_UPC_FT.3	KPIs results	●	
	Spain_8.1_UPC_FT.4	Download results	●	
	Spain_8.1_UPC_FT.5	Execution time	●	

Usability testing

Table 211. Service8.1_UPC_Usability testing.

UI Non-critical errors

Font size:

- Font size of the two tables (Asset List Results and Results of the Power Flow) in the Planning Actions TAB need to be the same.
- Color of the row could be better if it showed in red only if the value is higher than 100%. Orange color between 99% and 61 % and below 60% in yellow color. (But this action is not critical)
- The maximum decimals of the New Loading % column need to be 4 (Planning Actions TAB).

Limit axis:

No comments

UI Recommendations

Instead of having the PU legend in the top of the table in the middle of the push buttons:

I propose to move the legend (* The [pu] expression means "per unit" ...) to the bottom of the table. Also put the push button (Transformer, Lines, Bus Voltage) closer to the table. Please see an example of the image below:

Asset ID	Transformer Name	Type	HV Bus	LV Bus	HV Deviation [pu] *	LV Deviation [pu] *	Loading [%]
3	SS03	0,4 MVA 20,5/0,4 kV	29	46	0,999	0,978	123,4327
8	SS08	0,25 MVA 20,5/0,4 kV	37	51	0,999	0,994	35,0478
15	SS15	0,4 MVA 20,5/0,4 kV	1	38	1,000	0,996	28,1206
11	SS11	0,4 MVA 20,5/0,4 kV	35	49	0,999	0,995	26,802
6	SS06	0,4 MVA 20,5/0,4 kV	56	57	0,999	0,996	20,0711

Showing 1 to 5 of 17 entries Show 10 entries

Previous 1 2 3 4 Next

* The [pu] expression means "per unit"

Service Functional and KPIs Testing Actions

Table 212. SPAIN_8.1_UPC_FT.1 Stress test Tab display options.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
73. Stress test Tab display options	Select the "Name" options from the "Stress Test" tab to display all the transformer names. Make sure that all the names are written correctly.	●
	Select the "Expansion" option from the "Stress Test" tab to display the loading percent. Make sure that values are displayed correctly (Ex. 5%, 10%, 15%).	●
	Make sure that after adding (by clicking the add button) the expansion of the asset, the planning actions must be displayed in the table located in the right side of the UI. Make sure is displayed correctly .	●
	Select "Single Date Time" in the Type of power flow options. Make sure that you can select only one single date and time using the calendar option. Select a random Date-time (specify range of possible dates).	●
	Select "Multiple Date Time" in the Type of power flow options. Make sure that you can select two range of date and times (from and to) using the calendar option. Select a random range of date-times (specify range of possible dates).	●

Table 213. SPAIN_8.1_UPC_FT.2 Planning Actions Tab Display Options.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
74. Planning Actions Tab Display Options	Click the "Planning Actions" Tab (from the main left column). Make sure that there is no error in the time series or single power flow simulation.	●
	After running the power flow simulation, the planning actions must be displayed in the table located in the bottom side of the UI. Make sure is displayed correctly .	●

	Make sure the GIS map is displayed correctly (zoom in and out, view results of the asset and coordinates correspond to the pilot).	●
	After running the power flow simulation, the results of the planning power flows must be shown in table formats, divided in 3 tabs (Transformers, Lines and Bus voltages). Make sure that all the assets names, types and results are shown correctly.	●

Table 214. SPAIN_8.1_UPC_FT.3 KPIs results.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
75. KPIs results	Click the "KPIs" Tab (from the main left column). Then, select the "Total Decongestion" tab option (selected by default), and 3 KPIs options should display in a pie graph format (Decongestion in Lines %, Decongestion in Transformers % and Value Improvements). Make sure that the graphs are displayed correctly by selecting different asset types.	●
	Select the "Total Cost" tab option. Three different Investment Cost (CAPEX, OPEX and TOTEX) as a fixed number should be displayed. Make sure that the values are displayed correctly and the currency is in Euros.	●

Table 215. SPAIN_8.1_UPC_FT.4 Download results.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Check
76. Download results	Download results by clicking in the Save Results button (.xlsx and .csv).	●
	Make sure that the file corresponds to the KPIs displayed in the UI.	●

Table 216. SPAIN_8.1_UPC_FT.5 Execution time.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Execution time local/front-end	Check
77. Execution time	Executing algorithm for Use Case 1 (Annex)	10 s / 60 s	●

8.14S8.2 – Asset estimation optimization for microgrids

Service	S8.2 Assesst estimation optimization for microgrids
Algorithm provider	VUB – Wouter Parys
Solution provider	WEP
	Good performance ●
	Non-critical error ●
	Error detected ●
Release date	14/09/2023

Service testing summary

Functional and KPIs testing

Table 217. Testing Summary Table S8.2.

Pilot	Functional Test ID	Functional Test	Check	Test responsible	Comments
SPAIN	8.2_VUB_FT.1	Data ingestion	●	VUB	<i>Data manually ingested</i>
	8.2_VUB_FT.2	Review asset overview	●	VUB	
	8.2_VUB_FT.3	Evaluate SOH analysis	●	VUB	
	8.2_VUB_FT.4	Evaluate degradation prognosis	●	VUB	
	8.2_VUB_FT.5	Evaluate degradation costs	●	VUB	
	8.2_VUB_KPI	KPIs	●	VUB	
	8.2_VUB_EXEC	Execution time	●	WEP	

Usability testing

Table 218. Service8.2_VUB_Usability testing.

UI Critical errors
UI Non-critical errors
UI Recommendations
Labels on the plots could be better, sometimes it is difficult to understand the graph.

Service Functional and KPIs Testing Actions

Table 219. Service8.2_VUB_FT.1 Data ingestion.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Pilot	Check
78. Data ingestion	Make sure the data from the pilot is correctly ingested for the service.	EYPESA	●
		OEDAS	●
		VUB	●
	Verify that that the meta data (information of the 'asset type', the 'SOH primary param.' and SOH) is correctly represented	EYPESA	●
		OEDAS	●
		VUB	●

Table 220. Service8.2_VUB_FT.2 Review asset overview.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Pilot	Check
79. Review asset overview	Check if 'View detail' re-directs the page to the 'Data Analysis' tab of the selected asset.	EYPESA	●
		OEDAS	●
		VUB	●
	Verify that the specifications given in the 'Data Analysis' tab correspond to the ones from the 'Asset Overview'.	EYPESA	●
		OEDAS	●
		VUB	●
	Check if the visualization changes if another asset is selected.	EYPESA	●
		OEDAS	●
		VUB	●

Table 221. Service8.2_VUB_FT.3 Evaluate SOH analysis.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Pilot	Check
80. Evaluate SOH analysis	Verify that all results generated by the simulations are visualized in the 'SOH details' tab.	EYPESA	●
		OEDAS	●

		VUB	●
	Check that the results are plotted for both cases, as a function of the cycles and as a function of the years.	EYPESA	N/A
		OEDAS	N/A
		VUB	N/A
	Verify that the tab works for each asset (display, changes in values etc.).	EYPESA	N/A
		OEDAS	N/A
		VUB	N/A
	Verify that if the asset is a different type i.e. Battery versus PV system, that the titles change.	EYPESA	●
		OEDAS	●
		VUB	●

Table 222. Service8.2_VUB_FT.4 Evaluate degradation prognosis.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Pilot	Check
81. Evaluate degradation prognosis	Check that names and option changes as a function of the type of selected asset, i.e. should only be valid for a Battery	EYPESA	●
		OEDAS	●
		VUB	●
	Verify that the plots do adapt as a function of the selection (i) Number of cycles per year, (ii) Changes in average DoD or (iii) Average (dis)charging current.	EYPESA	●
		OEDAS	●
		VUB	●
	Check if 'Download data' downloads the data in the correct format and if the latter is interpretable once downloaded.	EYPESA	●
		OEDAS	●
		VUB	●
	Check if the 'Download image' downloads the same image as shown on the UI.	EYPESA	●
		OEDAS	●
		VUB	●

Table 223. Service8.2_VUB_FT.5 Evaluate degradation costs.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Pilot	Check
82. Evaluate degradation costs	Check if all the costs are represented for typical profiles (pre-loaded profiles).	EYPESA	●
		OEDAS	●
		VUB	●
	Verify that the 'Degradation costs' tab changes as a function of the selected asset type.	EYPESA	●
		OEDAS	●
		VUB	●
	Evaluate if dragging the data points (top figure), changes the degradation costs	EYPESA	●
		OEDAS	●
		VUB	●

Table 224. Service8.2_VUB_EXEC Functional Test Execution Time.

Functional Test Description	Test Actions	Execution time local/front-end	Check
83. Execution time	Executing algorithm for Use Case 1	< 1min	●
	Training algorithm for different models	3min / 15min	●

Usability testing

UI Critical errors

Errors that affect the tangible/numeric results: graphs display, login error, etc.

Table 225. Service8.2_VUB_UI critical errors.

Critical errors	Screen shots and description	Reporter
	N/A	

UI Non-critical errors

Errors that do not affect the tangible/numeric results: font sizes, colors of graphs, limits of the axis, etc.

Table 226. Service8.2_VUB_Non-critical errors.

Non-critical errors	Screen shots
<p>Results tend to appear the same for the different options (in the 'Degradation prognosis' tab) :</p> <p>However, the test data might have been restricted to a short period.</p>	

UI Recommendations

Provide recommendations for improving the front-end UI

Table 227. Service8.2_VUB_UI Recommendations.

Recommendations	Screen shots
<p>Provide better labels (x-axis and y-axis)</p>	<p>All plots</p>

9 References

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